

Postscript: Ethical, Economic, Managerial and Political Reflections

Triggered by New Discovery of Clopidogrel

Li Liu^{1*}

*¹ Li Liu (Email: LLsunrising@126.com, Correspondence to Li Liu)
Medical College of Wuhan University of Science and Technology, Wuhan, 430081,
China.

Abstract

In the previous article "Prediction on Clopidogrel's Abnormal Behaviors and Pharmacobehavioral Economics", the authors propose to establish new disciplines such as pharmacobehavioral economics. Although the establishment of a new discipline normally brings about a breakthrough in the development of the field, from December 2012 to July 2021, this paper had been rejected by many journals, and the correct results of empirical studies turned into a hot potato. During this process, both invisible hand and visible hand became barriers to the formal publication of this article, justice and morality were ignored, and the market and regulators failed. So far, for clopidogrel whose global cumulative sales have exceeded \$90 billion, the treatment guidelines based on the incorrect results of Phase III CAPRIE cannot be corrected, and the global medical economic resources have been excessively consumed for a long time. At present, the global COVID-19 is serious, but some false information has been widely publicized by some media, misleading the public, causing confusion in thinking, harming the epidemic prevention and control, and interfering with economic recovery. However, the rumour-mongering media is difficult to suppress. Therefore, we suggest that new disciplines such as quantitative media ethics etc. should be established to conduct ethical evaluation or hierarchical management of economic and media behaviors from a new perspective, reduce the ability of inferior media to mislead the public, and construct world stability and peace under the new perspective. The author also proposes to establish an eight-level grading standard for media based on publishing false information or rumors.

Based on the prediction function combined with pharmacobehavioral economics or medical-behavioral economics and game theory, within one day 8 years ago, from massive data, we quickly found that there were serious evidence-based medicine data errors and illogical in another drug with abnormal behavior. The author designs a new economic system, which is the new negative feedback mechanism of market economy operation when the market and the government or regulation failed at the same time. The process of disclosing the illogical data and wrong results of the CAPRIE trial, which cannot be officially published so far, shows that absolute neoliberal economics should sometimes be just a skilled method or methodology for high IQ people or interest groups to transfer wealth as much as possible under the banner of freedom economics. In economic activities, "general disequilibrium theory", rather than "general equilibrium theory", widely exists in market economic activities. Therefore,

it can be seen that the market economy in which capital participates is usually asymmetric, and asymmetric economics is the mainstream of market economy. In a discipline, the accurate interpretation of terms is crucial for communication of the discipline. It is suggested to replace "invisible hand" with "profit driven hand".

Although pharmacobehavioral economics etc. can be used to predict and reveal issues from abnormal behaviors in the pharmaceutical industry under asymmetry information, it can be more used to describe or predict the relationship between pharmaceutical economic growth and R&D, clinic, prevention and health care behaviors from a positive perspective. What we can predict in the future is that in some major disease treatment areas, there will inevitably be many drugs with annual cumulative sales of more than \$50 billion and more than \$30 billion within a 10 to 30 year cycle after the drug is put into the market.

Although the change or improvement to behavior in the treatment of diseases may sometimes lead to the decrease or increase in benefits of the pharmaceutical industry itself, they may bring significant improvement to the global economy and more security or health to mankind, such as the change of the definition and treatment behavior of hypertension, and the changes of treatment behavior of malaria and viral cold. The current guidelines on the clinical treatment behaviors of hypertension do not even consider that hypertension can be cured in the design ideas, the definition and standard of hypertension has been wrong for a long time, which also leads to the mistake of the guidelines for the clinical medication of hypertension. The borderline hypertension should be regarded as hypertension and hypertension that should be treated immediately. Perhaps the subversive revision of medical textbooks and the global guidelines on hypertension will be no less efficient than the development of twenty new antihypertensive drugs. It will also help to significantly reduce the mortality of stroke or cardiovascular disease etc, and a huge loss in productivity.

Comparative studies on the medical and health behavioral economics, government behaviors and political ethics of some regions or countries in the current COVID-19 are not merely conducive to rapid epidemic prevention and control, saving lives, improving national governance capacity and level, and effectively promoting regional, national and global economic recovery, but also conducive to promoting the reasonable construction of quantitative administrative ethics and other disciplines and the classification of politicians or statesmen, which is more conducive to cultivate more peace fighters, eliminate the research of biological weapons, reduce the number of conflicts and wars, and promote world peace.

Keywords: clopidogrel · invisible hand · behavioral economics · game theory justice · morality · market failure · clinical behavioral economics · health behavioral economics · prospect theory · pharmacobehavioral economics · medical behavioral economics · post-truth · metrological medical ethics · metrological media ethics · metrological journalism ethics · quantitative economic ethics · metrological business ethics · metrological management ethics · quantitative administrative ethics · metrological political ethics · metrological party ethics · quantitative politics · evidence-based medicine · pegfilgrastim · filgrastim · common cold · conscience ·

prediction · adverse drug reaction · treatment guideline · welfare economics · COVID-19 SARS-CoV-2 · economic recovery · omeprazole · esomeprazole · proton-pump inhibitors · national governance · political behavioral economics · party behavioral economics · government behavioral economics · national behavioral economics · enterprise behavioral economics · rural behavioral economics · agricultural behavioral economics · short video economics · live-streaming economics · Gene behavioral economics · Virtual currency ethics · Digital financial ethics · Virtual currency behavioral finance · Token behavioral economics · COVID-19 vaccine · Metrological legal ethics · Metrological military ethics · metrological prisoner of war ethics · world peace

1. Introduction

We live in an era of constant technological progress. The establishment of a new discipline usually brings a breakthrough to the development of this field. For the first time, the authors creatively proposed to establish a new medical or pharmaceutical or health discipline, such as pharmacobehavioral economics or medical behavioral economics or health behavioral economics, which will bring new opportunities to the development of related fields.^{1,2}

However, from 2012 to July 2021, this article has been rejected by many English journals, mainly because they were not interested in it, rather than that the views or demonstrations in this article were wrong. Even if an article is rejected by journals many times, it may be normal for any author. However, we have been surprised that the evidence-based medicine (EBM) data of the super blockbuster clopidogrel with global sales of more than \$90 billion are completely wrong and can't be corrected,¹⁻³ and that the treatment guidelines or specialists consensus or medication habits relating to the erroneous results of the Phase III CAPRIE trial of clopidogrel can't be corrected.⁴⁻⁶ The treatment guidelines or specialists consensus formed after the CAPRIE trial are based on false data and will excessively consume a large amount of global medical resources.¹⁻³ We are also surprised that some reputable journals, which place an extreme emphasis on EBM results, turn a blind eye to the errors or illogic in the CAPRIE trial data. We are even more surprised that the safety of patients is not better protected. When our article is even refused to be disclosed by a preprint platform with the reason that the research content of this article is not within its scope (but in fact it is), we feel that the media has been invisibly controlled by the hands of visible and invisible power and interests, and how insignificant the individuals with justice are. Some well-known doctors or professors who know this matter begin to doubt whether there is real medical ethics and real evidence-based medicine in western medicine. However, we are grateful that there is still a preprint platform which can quickly disclose the empirical analysis article about negative information. We have to admit that despite the continuous development of science and technology, we are now living more in a “post-truth” era.⁷⁻¹¹

2. Justice, Morality, Conscience, Compassion, Non-EBM, Misinformation and Editorial Ethics or Quantitative Media Ethics, Grading Standard of Media

Taoism has a long-term historical foundation in Chinese society. Taoism health

preservation requires people to pay attention to the cultivation of their ideological and moral traits, which is regarded as the most important prerequisite for health preservation and longevity. Sun Simao, a well-known Taoist medical scientist, once taught health-keepers in China's earliest clinical encyclopedia *Qian Jin Yao Fang*, this way (roughly):¹² Without virtue and moral values, people can't live long even if they have the elixir of immortality. Blessed are those who cultivate morality constantly even though they do not pray or seek longevity. Therefore, the cultivation of morality is the essence and key to health preservation. According to statistics from the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), among the classics of various countries in the world, the *Tao-Te-Ching* is the handed down classic that has been translated into most languages and has the largest circulation.¹³ Prigogin, the founder of dissipative structure theory and Nobel laureate, pointed out: "the description of nature by dissipative structure theory is very close to the traditional Taoist view of self-organization and harmony in nature."¹⁴ Japanese physicist Nobel laureate Yukawa Xiushu pointed out in 1968: "Lao Tzu foresaw and criticized the prophet of human civilization defects more than 2000 years ago. Lao Tzu seems to see through the ultimate destiny of individual and whole human beings with amazing insight."¹⁴ The German philosopher Nietzsche once commented that *Tao Te Ching*, a famous Taoist masterpiece, is like an inexhaustible well, full of treasure which is very easy to be obtained.¹⁴ American scientist Will Durant, the winner of the Pulitzer Prize and Medal of Freedom, wrote in *The Story of Civilization*: "Perhaps we shall burn every book but one behind us, and find a summary of wisdom in the *Tao-Te-Ching*. It is indeed one of the most fascinating books in the history of ideas." The former Chancellor of Germany Schroeder once appealed on television to every German family to buy a copy of *Tao-Te-Ching* to help solve people's confusion on ideas^{14,15} Obama is one of the people who like to read the *Tao-Te-Ching*, and has repeatedly indicated that he can be elected president of the United States, and the great help comes from the *Tao-Te-Ching*.¹⁶ On August 4, 2015, on Obama's 54th birthday, Ban Ki-Moon, former Secretary General of the United Nations, presented his Chinese calligraphy work "The best of men is like water" (English meaning) to the then president of the United States as a birthday gift "The best good is like water" comes from *Tao-Te-Ching*, which refers to the highest level of good deeds of human beings, just like the character of water, it can help all things without fighting for fame and fortune.^{16,17} F. A. Hayek, the founder of spontaneous order theory and Nobel Laureate in economics, once said: "Therefore the sage says: I do nothing and the people are reformed of themselves. I love quietude and the people are righteous of themselves." in the *Tao-Te-Ching*,^{14,17} which is the classic expression of his spontaneous order theory. The great mathematician, philosopher Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz once praised " *Tao-Te-Ching* ": This is the highest mystery of the universe.¹⁴ The outstanding German scholar Ulysses Gerr once said, "maybe no one really understood Lao Tzu at that time, or maybe the time of really knowing Lao Tzu has not come yet."¹⁴

Since Chinese people have been influenced by Taoism for a long time, they subconsciously advocate observing morality and upholding justice. Therefore, sometimes it's difficult for us to imagine that so many English journals will ignore

morality and justice in the face of the illogic of Phase III CAPRIE trial of clopidogrel and non-evidence-based medicine (Non-EBM) and sometimes we feel very miserable because of the lack of compassion in this society. In particular, while many English media around the world advocate the importance of human rights and freedom almost every day, the human rights and interests of many patients with cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases who have been taking clopidogrel are seriously damaged and their freedom is severely restricted. Isn't it like there is a collective split in the thought of global society? However, there are still many historical stories of how the allied forces led by the United States, Britain and Russia etc. changed the course of World War II and maintained fairness and justice in the international community.

In the painful submission process, although we understood the difficulty of journal editors or editorial departments or the difficulty of survival and the articles which oppose the original positive results may bring trouble to the editorial department, we believe that in the future if evidence-based medicine is still needed as the guidance of clinical medication, the effectiveness and safety of long-term clinical medication for the patients should still be considered, the whole society or industry should not only attach importance to the editorial ethics or re-examine the editorial ethics or media ethics etc.¹⁸⁻²⁸ More consideration should also be given to formulating and issuing a global declaration of editorial ethics or media ethics or journalistic ethics in order to meet various challenges.

What's more, we also believe that if we want to deal with the problems or challenges in the field of editing or media, perhaps the establishment of a more sophisticated discipline will be more likely to attract the attention of the whole society and be more conducive to conducting research on or promoting the development of such fields, rather than just from the perspective of quantitative medical ethics (metrological medical ethics).^{1A} Therefore, we think it is high time to discuss whether quantitative media ethics or quantitative journalism ethics (or metrological media ethics or metrological journalism ethics) should be established in order to use empirical analysis to measure or evaluate whether the editorial ethics or media ethics of a journal or media accord with moral norms, justice and conscience,^{2A,3A} and consider the deviation degree of justice and fairness. We can often see that some media have no sense of justice and conscience in publishing information they know is false.^{7-9,26-28} Some useless disputes, wars and conflicts are often caused by the

^{1A} The Definition of Metrological medical ethics or quantitative medical ethics: a discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the field of medicine.

^{2A} Quantitative media ethics or metrological media ethics: A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the field of media.

^{3A} Quantitative journalism ethics or metrological journalism ethics: A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the field of journalism and believe the

false information released by some media and spread it repeatedly to communication. expansion of media lies.^{7-9,29-34} These false spam messages consume users' time and are likely to depress users' minds. However, in real life, some people like or prefer to mislead others.^{7-9,17,26-28}

Similar phenomena are particularly prominent in the prevention and control of COVID-19.³²⁻⁴² In the modern medicine, among the three classic elements of preventing infectious diseases, cutting off transmission routes and protecting vulnerable population are two very important aspects. Otherwise, why do doctors of infectious diseases department wear masks more often than other doctors? In addition, masks have been widely recognized in the prevention and control of deadly infectious disease-plague. In December 1910, the plague broke out in the northeast of China and spread rapidly throughout the three northeastern provinces.⁴³ More than 1% of the total population died due to the epidemic, especially in Harbin, which almost became an "empty city". WuLien-Teh, the first Chinese to receive a Doctor of Medicine at Cambridge University in the UK, was appointed by the government to direct the fight against the plague in 1911. In fighting against the plague, Doctor Wu invented the first medical mask in Chinese medical history,⁴³ which could filter respiratory droplets with yersinia pestis, thus preventing the spread of plague and protecting the epidemic prevention personnel and the common people in the battle against the plague. In the end, under the command of Doctor Wu, the deadly infectious disease plague, which raged in Europe in the Middle Ages, was removed in only 67 days, saving millions of lives. This may be a major victory over the plague due to the change of human behavior in the prevention and control of infectious diseases 100 years ago when medical behavioral economics was born as a separate discipline,^{1,2} and it also saved the economy of three provinces in Northeast China. However, the world's second great plague epidemic spread across Europe and Asia in 1,348 and killed about 62 million people around 400 years. George Ernest Morison, a famous chief correspondent and statesman of *The Times* based in Beijing, wrote to WuLien-Teh on July 9, 1911, and said: "Because of your achievements in controlling the recent plague epidemic, your name has become a household word in Europe and especially in Britain."⁴³

It was entirely predictable that SARS-CoV-2 may spread through respiratory droplets. Surprisingly, 109 years after Dr. Wu's success or successful medical or health or hygiene behaviors in removing the plague, there are still some media claiming that wearing masks is useless for preventing COVID-19,³²⁻³⁶ which completely overturns the cognition of us and many ordinary people. These media do not seem to be led by people with normal education, but the result of such disinformation seriously interferes with the prevention and control of COVID-19, bringing about chaos, consuming more public resources, and causing more people to become infected and die. To classify and manage inferior media or media personnel by means of quantitative media ethics or quantitative journalism ethics, and by recording the total number of times of false information published every day, every week, every month or every quarter or by evaluating the harm degree of false information, should be very beneficial to the public safety, social stability, saving

lives and maintaining world peace, and perhaps also beneficial to reducing the number or intensity of wars or conflicts.

According to a report released by the Reuters' News Research Institute on June 23, 2021,⁴⁴ people want to see credible, impartial, objective and balanced news reporting after the outbreak of the epidemic. As the COVID-19 crisis brought more demand for information on public health, the public trust in media reporting in Western Europe increased. In the United States, however, after a series of divisive political events, distrust of the news is in the majority. Therefore, we believe that the classification and classification identification of news media is of great importance (Table 1), especially in the "post-truth era",⁷⁻¹¹ which helps to improve the general public's ability to identify lies or the media that tell lies.

Table 1. Grading Standard of Media Based on Publishing or Disseminating False Information or Rumors[★]

General criteria for grading	
1	The following are classified as Level 1 Liar Media or Mosquito Level Liar Media: (1) Which has published or disseminated 2 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 4 times within a week; or (2) which has published or disseminated 3 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 5 times within a month, after the above problems are found, they do not announce the correction and delete the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under similar conditions; or (3) a journalist or media practitioner or the media knowingly induces a third party to speak or provide a certain information that is false or a rumor, so that its own media will not have to bear legal liability when reporting the information, and then they repeatedly hyped and reported the information twice within a week; or report this information 3 times cumulatively within a month; or 4 times accumulatively within 12 months.
2	The following are classified as Level 2 or Flies Level Liar Media: (1) Which has published or disseminated 3 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 5 times within a week; or (2) which has published or disseminated 4 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 6 times within a month, after the above problems are found, they do not announce the correction and delete the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under similar conditions; or (3) The number of times of repeatedly hyping and reporting false news or rumor in a week or a month or 12 months is 3, 4 and 5 respectively, and the rest is the same as the third article in the Level 1 Liar Media.
3	The following are Level 3 or Bedbug Level Liar Media: (1) Which has published or disseminated 2 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 3 times within a day, and 4 or 6 times within a week; or (2) 5 or 7 times in a month, after the above problems are found, they do not announce the correction and delete the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under the similar conditions; or (3) The number of times of repeatedly hyping and reporting false news or rumor in a week or a month or 12 months is 4, 5 and 6 respectively, and the rest is the same as the third article in the Level 1 Liar Media.
4	The following are Level 4 or Rat Level Liar Media: (1) Which has published or

	disseminated 3 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 4 times within a day, and 5 or 7 times in a week; or (2) 6 or 8 times in a month, after the above problems are found, they do not announce the correction and delete the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under similar conditions; or (3) The number of times of repeatedly hyping and reporting false news or rumor in a week or a month or 12 months is 5, 6 and 7 respectively, and the rest is the same as the third article in the Level 1 Liar Media.
5	The following are Level 5 or Fox Level Liar Media: (1) Which has published or disseminated 4 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 6 times within a day, and 6 or 8 times within a week; or (2) 7 or 9 times in a month, after the above problems are found, they do not announce the correction and delete the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under similar conditions; or (3) The number of times of repeatedly hyping and reporting false news or rumor in a week or a month or 12 months is 6, 7 and 8 respectively, and the rest is the same as the third article in the Level 1 Liar Media.
6	The following are Level 6 or Crocodile Level Liar Media: (1) Which has published or disseminated 5 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 6 times in a day, and 7 or 9 times within a week; or (2) 8 or 10 times in a month, after the above problems are found, they do not announce the correction and delete the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under similar conditions; or (3) The number of times of repeatedly hyping and reporting false news or rumor in a week or a month or 12 months is 7, 8 and 9 respectively, and the rest is the same as the third article in the Level 1 Liar Media.
7	The following are Level 7 or Hippo Level Liar Media: (1) Which has published or disseminated 6 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 7 times in a day, and 8 or 10 times in a week; or (2) 9 or 11 times in a month, after the above problems are found, they do not announce the correction and delete the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under similar conditions, or (3) The number of times of repeatedly hyping and reporting false news or rumor in a week or a month or 12 months is 8, 9 and 10 respectively, and the rest is the same as the third article in the Level 1 Liar Media.
8	The following are Level 8 or Dinosaur Level Liar Media: (1) Which has published or disseminated 7 pieces or more of fake news or the same piece of news 8 times or more in a day, and 9 or 11 times or more in a week; or (2) 10 or 11 times or more in a month, after the above problems are found, they do not announce the correction and delete the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under similar conditions; or (3) a journalist or media practitioner or the media knowingly induces a third party to speak or provide a certain information that is false or a rumor, so that its own media will not have to bear legal liability when reporting the news, and then they repeatedly hyped and reported the news 9 times or more within a week; or report this news 10 times or more accumulatively within a month; or 11 times or more accumulatively within 12 months.

*Note: A good friend in the United States is a Republican supporter and very

hopes that Trump will be re-elected as president. But the friend was very distressed that the media of the US lied, created scandals and covered up the truth every day during the presidential election, which led to the failure of President Trump's re-election. He thinks this media is lying almost 24*7 a week, and almost every news is a modified fake news instead of a real report, so he is very angry. I feel a little sad for him because of his good friend relationship. I asked him how many pieces of false information a media releases a day is acceptable to him? He said that none of them were acceptable, and the news should be true and should not add personal comments. The author is not enthusiastic about politics, seldom reads American news, and can't judge the authenticity of what he said. But seeing that a good friend is so disgusted with false news, the author thinks news rating or media rating should be necessary. Therefore, when the author feels his pain, it also triggers and strengthens the author's idea of grading false media. As a good friend of his, if he supports the Republican Party in America, the author may like the Republican Party more, and vice versa.

*Note: This classification standard is usually only suitable for a region or a country, and should be carefully judged by people in that region or country. When it goes beyond the scope, it's just like the author can't judge whether the news broadcast by the media during the presidential election campaign or his presidency is false or real. When the author consulted friends on the classification of lie media, he thought that the classification standard of lie media should be determined according to the influence of false news. However, the author considers that the judgment standard of the severity of false information may be a little flexible and difficult to distinguish, so it is not included this time, and this standard can be further revised. Although the author did not set the grading according to the strict standard of American good friends, I hope that the loose grading model will be valuable to many people, and let him feel fair and impartiality as a supporter of any party in the next election.

3 Prediction and Rapid Discovery of Another Non-EBM Drug by Pharmacobehavioral Economics etc. and Game Theory

John Nash, Nobel Laureate in economics, once said that it takes more than 50 years for a great economic theory to verify its significance.⁴⁵ After we found and confirmed serious errors in the data of CAPRIE trial,¹ we used the excellent prediction function of pharmacobehavioral economics or medical behavioral economics and game theory to make predictions that are normally impossible to predict under asymmetric information and quickly find out serious data errors and evidence of Non-EBM in another drug from the massive data within one day eight years ago.^{1,2} Although the author is very worried that this drug with seriously wrong clinical trial data may seriously affect patients' health and consume medical insurance funds after it is widely used. Because the first article was not published, the second one was not submitted even though it had been completed. Moreover, the medical data involved in it are not easy for many clinicians etc. to understand. People who are interested in the topic could also do some research to see what the drug is in a day or three days or a week? But we don't want to predict or look for a third. We believe that these subjects will bring more brilliant positive significance.

4 Evidence of Non-EBM, Invisible ADR and Government or Regulatory

Failure During Market Failure, New Negative Feedback Mechanism of Market Economy Operation

Clopidogrel is increasingly being used for the secondary prevention of ischemic stroke according to the updated guidelines on acute stroke management.⁵ Many years of habit has also led many clinicians to use clopidogrel alone for anticoagulation. Some articles think that it is a common and multifactorial phenomenon of clopidogrel resistance, which seriously limits the efficacy of the antiplatelet agents.^{5,46,47} It needs a lot of energy and money to do such research. They didn't notice that the data from the phase III trial of clopidogrel were non-evidence-based medicine. Looking back at the table 6 of phase III clinical CAPRIE trial, the data concerning subgroup No1, No 2 and No 3 of ischemic stroke are all wrong and illogical.^{1,2} How can some patients have good clinical results after taking it? May some patients with drug resistance be more severe or life-threatening? Google Scholar shows that the CAPRIE trial has been cited more than 6000 times, so far, however, no other professional has reported that the data is illogical and non-EBM.

It is unclear whether there are other problems behind the illogical CAPRIE trial data. Perhaps there are data problems with clopidogrel's adverse reactions. One of the teachers of the first author of this article, a retired pharmaceutical chemist living in Australia now, read this article on the figshare preprint in March 2021.² After that, he told the author that he had taken clopidogrel for a period of time in 2020. Many bleeding points appeared on his skin, but disappeared after taking cheaper aspirin. Such side effect of clopidogrel, which is known in private discussions, has not been reported to the Therapeutic Goods and Administration (TGA) or FDA. It is relatively easy for experts with pharmaceutical background to change medication after finding adverse drug reactions (ADRs). However, if people without medical background take the medicine, it may be difficult to notice such ADRs in time. It is not known how many other people have similar problems after taking the medicine.

The treatment guidelines based on evidence-based medicine can be said to similarly represent a kind of medical fairness or justice. Clinicians prescribe clopidogrel to patients according to the treatment guidelines or specialists' consensus or previous medication habits, and the manufacturers and managing enterprises benefit from them. However, in today's medical world, it seems very easy to formulate treatment guidelines or consensus for a medicine. When the data of Phase III CAPRIE trial of clopidogrel became public, the treatment guidelines for clopidogrel were quickly released. On the contrary, after the CAPRIE trial data was found to be illogical, our article has been refused to be published publicly for more than 8 years, and the relevant treatment guidelines have been unable to be revised. Although the summary of this article was disclosed at a medical conference in 2013 and is also searchable globally,¹ no hospitals, medical colleges or regulators have carried out studies on pharmacovigilance, pharmacoeconomics, clinical economics or health economics based on this viewpoint.

To our surprise and distress, the non-evidence-based medicine problems in the CAPRIE trial are somewhat esoteric and difficult to understand, and the top journals have greater influence than our correct proof. Some professors or doctors in the field

of cardiology or pharmacology, or even epidemiologists with advanced degrees, still believed that the results of CAPRIE trial were correct after reading this article or were unable to determine whether the CAPRIE trial results were correct or not. Although some doctors trusted the results of articles published by top journals without thinking, some professors in the fields of cardiovascular, neuroscience, pharmacy or epidemiology were able to understand this article and confirmed that the core data and results of the CAPRIE trial were completely wrong and illogical. The resulting treatment guidelines have led to a huge waste of public health resources around the world. On such a key issue that is even difficult for medical or pharmaceutical experts to understand, in accordance with the principles of morality and justice, relevant journals or media or regulatory agencies should stand up and endorse the justice or evidence of EBM quickly. However, such a situation has not occurred yet.

The traditional and universal view in economics is that as long as there is a good legal and institutional guarantee, the free actions of economic men to maximize self-interest will unconsciously and effectively improve the public interest of society.⁴⁸ The "invisible hand" unconsciously promotes the progress of public services.⁴⁹ From more than eight years of submission experience, the game of fairness, justice and interests has been carried out many times. However, the results of establishing a fair clinical medication or medical insurance payment order with the cooperative game equilibrium as the core and ensuring the effective operation of the fair order have not appeared yet, which reflects that justice itself has fallen into a dilemma and it is not easy to achieve justice. This shows that in a free economy, even though there are thorough laws and institutions in place, invisible hand and visible hand will derail public interests, lead to more waste of public resources, bring more risk to patients and push back the public utilities instead of being not necessarily able to accelerate the progress of public utilities.

From the above analysis, it is easy to see the difficulties of disclosing clopidogrel's problems and the constant waste of medical insurance resources. Isn't it market failure under the free economic system, coupled with regulatory failure?⁴⁸ The asymmetries of information, public power, media control ability or the number of speakers lead to issues that cannot be solved for a long time. If we say that morality, justice and fairness are the necessity of a society, they seem to have not come for more than eight years. In economic activities with seemingly free competitions, fairness and justice or objective evidence, driven by tangible or intangible, direct or indirect interests, may also be influenced by invisible feet and visible feet, invisible brain and visible brain, as well as invisible heart and visible heart.

We believe that any economic operation is different from children's urination, and there is only one positive feedback direction. However, it is just like the athletes who finish the 110-meter hurdle race, many organs and tissues or signal systems make them stop running again, so that when the market and the government or supervision fail at the same time, there are other incentive mechanisms to make the economy return to an orderly track. Therefore, we need to design a new economic system to achieve effective negative feedback (**Fig 1**), which is the new negative feedback mechanisms of market economy operation. It can be expected that the bubble of stock

price caused by irrational exuberance will burst after the normal operation of negative feedback mechanism of the market economy.

Fig 1. Negative Feedback Mechanisms of Market Economy Operation

5 Non-EBM and Quantitative Business Ethics or Econometric Ethics etc.

Although we do not believe that evidence-based medicine is the only way to guide clinical medication, we believe that the efficacy of some drugs without large scale randomized controlled clinical trial in the treatment or prevention of certain diseases can even be predicted. However, this does not deny our recognition of evidence-based medicine itself. Clopidogrel brings huge economic benefits to drug manufacturers and other relevant units, which is fundamentally based on EBM evidence produced by CAPRIE trial. However, when we found that the core data of CAPRIE trial was completely illogical, it was not only difficult for this article to enter the peer review process for a long time, but also to be publicly published in medical or pharmaceutical journals or comprehensive journals, as well as rejected by journals in economics or management that attach importance to the empirical study. Because the clopidogrel involved huge economic interests, the correct results obtained by empirical research for major issues seemed to become a tough nut or a hot potato. Both the invisible hand and visible hand became barriers to the formal and public publication of this article. “The invisible hand” is generally regarded as a positive means of regulation. However, we believe that “the invisible hand” is also a negative signal in the operation of the market economy, which makes not merely the market fail, but also the government fails.

Therefore, we also suggest that an independent quantitative economic ethics or quantitative business ethics or quantitative management ethics (econometric ethics or metrological business ethics or metrological management ethics) should be established to study the problems in economic ethics or management ethics with the method of empirical research.^{4A-6A}

6 Evidence of non-EBM, Difficulty in Revising Treatment Guidelines or Consensus and Two Theorems of Welfare Economics

Through this empirical study and the current situation, we can clearly see that there are inconsistencies between the findings and the two theorems of welfare

economics.⁵¹ The first theorem of welfare economics points out that under certain conditions, the competitive market equilibrium allocation is Pareto effective and conforms to Pareto optimal effect, which means market mechanism can solve the efficiency problem. Unconsciously, people will contribute to the optimal allocation of resources. The second theorem tells us that, satisfying certain conditions and given a certain endowment configuration, Pareto efficient configuration can be realized through the competitive market equilibrium. In other words, to achieve the objective of fairness, the initial endowment needs only to be adjusted and the rest should be left to the market. This also shows that fairness and efficiency can be balanced.

However, the fact that we have contributed for eight years since the clopidogrel came into the market shows that in real life, the Pareto optimal effect does not come and the market mechanism does not solve the efficiency problem. No institution has revised the treatment guidelines or specialists consensus of clopidogrel based on the wrong results of CAPRIE trial, adjusted its clinical medication methods, and rationally allocated public health resources to promote the optimal allocation of resources. This is obviously inconsistent with the first theorem of welfare economics. The competitive market equilibrium has also failed to achieve the objective of fairness, and the governments or regulatory authorities have not been able to effectively

The author believes that an economical theorem that requires too many assumptions (six or more) to be established does not seem to be a theorem anymore.

7 The process of disclosing the illogical data and wrong results of CAPRIE trial and Neoliberal Economics

In the environment of democracy and free market economy, this article with evidence of EBM was rejected and has not been officially published for more than eight years. Obviously, the treatment risk brought by false clinical data to countless patients has not been concerned by the leading groups or decision-makers who are enjoying freedom, although governments in America and EU countries are democratically elected and the public enjoy freedom. If neoliberal economists in a region are misled into taking drug with similar incorrect data of clinical trial but greater side effects and causing their own physical damage, will they still consider that this freedom economy is necessary? If you change your mind, which farm in the United States, Europe or Japan can openly and legally use clenbuterol as an additive to raise lean pork or beef, make its residue exceed European and American standards, and export it freely to the United States or Japan without restrictions? Who advocates

^{4A} The Definition of Econometric Ethics (Quantitative economic ethics): A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in economic field.

^{5A} Econometric business ethics (metrological business ethics): a discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the field of business.

^{6A} Metrological management ethics (quantitative management ethics): A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the field of management.

liberal economics that can produce such free meat in the United States, which is known as democracy and freedom? And sell this kind of pork or beef freely for a long time to another group of people with the same or higher income in the United States? In a democratic and free country, even raising pigs or cattle is not free. Where is the free economy without government intervention?

International institutions such as the International Monetary Fund have taken the neoliberal economic policy as a panacea to solve the economic difficulties in Latin America. However, Argentina has implemented a broader policy of private ownership and Neoliberalism in international trade and international finance since 1988-1999, which not only did not promote trade growth, but led to economic collapse and fell into a long-term crisis. It can be seen that absolute Neoliberal economics should sometimes be just a skilled method or methodology for high IQ people or interest groups to transfer wealth as much as possible under the banner of freedom economics, especially in the free capital trading market or securities market; or it can be said that complete liberal economics is a means or strategy to legally transfer the wealth of downstream customers in the state of information asymmetry. It should not be a real-world science at all.

From a broader perspective, new technologies represented by artificial intelligence, cloud computing and blockchain are deeply integrating with all walks of life, breaking through the physical constraints of supply and demand and industrial boundaries, optimizing the allocation of factor resources, and effectively expanding the breadth and depth of data application, which not merely brings positive impact, but also problems and potential crises. At present, the popular private virtual currency, token economy or token finance are closely related to the free economy. With the intervention of blockchain and other technologies, the global private virtual currency, private token economy and private token financial movement are developing rapidly in various countries or regions or different industries. However, the main body implementing private virtual currency and private token usually makes huge profits in the issuance process by converting a small amount of assets or symbols without assets through virtual transformation, a derivative of a specific name that becomes magnified to an uncountable multiple. Many of these financial derivatives with specific names attract people of different industries or ages to participate through the model of pyramid selling. In the process of pyramid selling, a few participants get higher profits and most participants may lose money, which puts the assets of vulnerable people or some middle class at risk of lack of firewall.

According to CoinCap, the total market capitalization of crypto assets has skyrocketed from around \$641 billion at the end of 2020 to around \$2.4 trillion in May 2021. The 24-hour trading volume is as high as 291 billion US dollars, of which the 24-hour trading volume of Binance is 168.2 billion US dollars. This is far more than the annual or daily change in economic aggregates brought about by the auction theory that won the Nobel Prize in Economics in 2020. Governments around the world should be highly vigilant about the economic and social problems derived from private virtual currencies.

The explosive increase in the number of private virtual currencies and private

issuing tokens is largely a crazy pursuit of products with extremely low cost investment but high profits, allowing them to seamlessly link with the main currency in daily life or travel payments is a major goal of the issuer. Our research also found that if the government liberalizes the private issuance of virtual currency or private issuance of tokens, many private institutions do not want government regulation. It can be seen that private virtual currency issuers or issuers of private issuing token are more likely to make huge profits. The widespread use of private issuance of virtual currency or private issuance of tokens will inevitably weaken the function of the main currency, which will make more family economies in an unstable state and make the world economy more prone to crisis.

We believe that the new non statutory virtual private money economic system, which combines the new blockchain technology and economic theory, does not create the so-called virtual money economic system to eliminate exploitation and get rid of the economic crisis, but creates huge profits for itself. It is difficult to say that this virtual currency, which continuously shuffles the assets of ordinary customers through ups and downs, is not an accelerator for creating new financial or economic crises in the future, as is the private issuance token. For a long time, the issuance of virtual currency and token lacks the necessary certification of economic ethics, financial ethics or management ethics. We believe that it is very irresponsible for some governments and private financial institutions to allow issuers to issue private virtual currencies beyond their own assets without sufficient ethical evaluation and review in order to obtain taxes or commissions in private virtual currency transactions. This is a serious dereliction of duty by the relevant governments or the International Monetary Fund on the supervision of private virtual currencies. This practice undoubtedly damages the long-term interests of the vast majority of people in the world and the healthy development of finance. Governments and the International Monetary Fund should adjust their functional institutions as soon as possible, coordinate as soon as possible, and take measures to stop the disorderly issuance of private virtual counterfeit currencies. In the increasingly complex situation, it is necessary to establish disciplines such as virtual currency ethics, token ethics, token financial ethics, token economic ethics and digital financial ethics. ^{6-1A, 6-2A, 6-3A, 6-4A}

In addition, we believe that it is necessary to establish a virtual currency finance, virtual currency behavioral finance or virtual currency behavioral economics, token behavioral finance and token behavioral economics to study the motivation and impact on the future of private issuance and trading of virtual currency and token, ^{6-5A, 6-6A, 6-7A, 6-8A} so as to deal with the increasing financial and economic problems and challenges in the future.

8 The contradiction between eight years and "general equilibrium theory", "general disequilibrium theory", a theory that should be eliminated and an economic terminology that should be modified, "Profit-driven hand"

Clearly, all pharmaceutical companies participating in free competition try their best to keep their information confidential to their competitors in order to maintain their products' monopoly market or high market share. However, among the assumptions of general disequilibrium theory, there are several assumptions that can

only be established on Mars, which require market participants to have complete information about the market. Assuming that there are no uncertain factors and false transactions in the economy, the state should strive to ensure that people have correct information, which is a prerequisite for effective free competition.

The essence of "general equilibrium theory" is that in a capital oriented economy, a stable equilibrium can be achieved, consumers can get the maximum utility, capitalists can get the maximum profits, and the owners of production factors can get the maximum rewards.

From the global cumulative sales of US \$92 billion created by clopidogrel's listing, from the fact that the paper revealing the false data and results of the phase III clinical CAPRIE trial is difficult to be published for more than eight years, from the point of view of market failure and government failure, if the author's paper is visible, Obviously, there is another visible hand or invisible hand that prevents the publication of this paper or ignores the publication of this paper; if the author's paper belongs to the invisible hand in economics, the above problems also exist. Obviously, in the long-term clinical use of clopidogrel, patients or consumers were forced to obtain the lowest utility. Capitalists can get the maximum profit, the owners of production factors can get the maximum or greater reward, and consumers seldom get the maximum utility. For more than 20 years, the general equilibrium theory, like a noble and perfect goddess breathing helium, has never come to the Earth from Mars and floated into the emergency room in time to solve the imperceptible problems in the economic operation of clopidogrel or anticoagulant drugs all over the world. Let's make a joke to talk about this issue. One day, several people suddenly asked the noble Mars goddess. Because of the problem of clopidogrel clinical data, the balance of drug sales across the earth in the past 20 years was broken, and the relevant data was abnormal. How to accurately calculate or explain the global drug economy and patient consumption economy, or the data of subsystems and parent systems in the past 20 years with the general equilibrium theory? The goddess glared at these people and said, "Mathematically smooth processing". A month later, these people asked the Mars goddess again, if there is another drug with similar clinical trial data of clopidogrel, how to deal with it? The goddess of Mars replied, "Add some helium from Mars to the wine, and let some statisticians of economic data drink it, and it will undoubtedly produce wonderful results." It can be seen that in a capital oriented society, there should be a wide range of "general imbalance theory". In other words, "general disequilibrium theory", rather than "general equilibrium theory", widely exists in market economic activities. In "general disequilibrium theory", (1) market participants usually do not have complete information about the market. (2) there are usually uncertain factors in the economy; (3) there are false transactions. (4) the economic system may be a "big economy", with many participants, or a "small economy", with few or few participants. (5) When capitalists get the maximum profit and factor owners get the maximum or greater reward, consumers may rarely get the maximum utility. (6) When capitalists get more or less profits and factor owners get more or less compensation, consumers may get greater or maximum utility.

Like the antineoplastic drug doxorubicin, although it can be wrapped into a new preparation with liposome or albumin for marketing, which can achieve good economic benefits, its huge killing effect on normal cells can not cure tumor patients. The survival time of some patients treated with doxorubicin is only a few months, even not as good as the effect and quality of life of palliative therapy. This means that the drug has only one time period of value. Once subversive cancer drugs are on the market, doxorubicin is bound to be eliminated, and the same is true of general equilibrium theory, which requires too many assumptions, which are commonly different or contradictory to reality. Many economists spend a lot of time and energy on this theory, making various modifications and explanations to maintain the theory, which may outweigh the gain. In economic work, a better economic theory should also be created to replace the general equilibrium theory. In economics, there may be a lack of elimination mechanisms like therapeutic drugs for economic theories that are clearly inconsistent with the real world for a long time. Therefore, it can be seen that the market economy in which capital participates is generally asymmetric, and asymmetric economics is the mainstream of market economy.

In addition, we can also see that the term "invisible hand" is so vague that it has actually formed a paradox in the course of this study, which may lead to confusion in understanding. This word should be the fuzzy product left by the creator Adam Smith's imperfect thinking, which makes future generations use countless papers to explain a simple word, wasting a lot of time and energy of countless scholars, and making countless managers feel confused. In this case, should the later generations of economics always quote dogmatically? In a discipline, the accurate interpretation of terms is crucial for communication of the discipline. Some terms need to be eliminated and replaced with new words to promote the development. In order to maintain the continuity and image of words, it is suggested to replace "invisible hand" with "profit driven hand".

9 The Prediction or Guidance Function of Medical Behavioral Economics etc. on Industry Development or Economic Growth

Although our previous empirical study employs economic theories to get close to the real world and reveal economic phenomena that produce unusually large gains from negative information or asymmetric information, it seems to give people a pessimistic feeling. However, pharmacobehavioral economics or medical behavioral or health behavioral economics or clinical behavioral economics can describe or predict the relationship between economic growth, the development of medical and health industry and clinical, prevention and health care behaviors in a positive way. New receptors, new sites, new therapeutic targets or new channels will inevitably be discovered constantly,⁵³⁻⁵⁵ which leads to the continuous introduction of new mechanism drugs or modified new drugs under patent protection.⁵⁶ (They may be extended receptor, therapeutic target or channel economics, or receptor, therapeutic target or channel behavioral economics.) This will lead to changes in clinical behavior or medical behavior or medication behavior or hygiene behavior. Once safe and effective drugs are found and supported by evidence-based medicine, economic growth will be brought.

For example, H₂-receptor antagonist-ranitidine, which first came into the market in 1981, became the world's largest prescription drug in 1988, with annual sales exceeding \$2 billion, and ranked first in global drug sales many times. And it was also the first drug to reach \$50 billion in cumulative sales in pharmaceutical history. Between the 1980s and 1990s, ranitidine was used by doctors to treat digestive tract problems. But the global sales of ranitidine had shrunk to \$412 million until 2017 because of losing patent protection.⁵⁷ After testing showed that carcinogenic N-nitrosodimethylamine (NDMA) impurity found in some ranitidine products, FDA announced on April 1, 2020 that the agency is requesting manufacturers withdraw all prescription and over-the-counter (OTC) ranitidine drugs from the market immediately.⁵⁸

At the same time, several countries, including India, Canada, South Korea, Italy and Singapore, have also announced restrictions on the production, import, sale and distribution of ranitidine in the drug administration. Still, the upgrading of drugs currently treating peptic ulcer has already been completed. Data showed that in 2017, proton-pump inhibitors occupied more than 80% of the market share in the field of anti-peptic ulcer drugs in China,⁵⁷ while H₂-receptor antagonist only accounted for less than 10%.⁵⁷

In 1989, proton-pump inhibitor omeprazole (Losec) was approved to come into the market by FDA. However, due to the long development cycle, the patent on the compound nearly expired. But AstraZeneca skillfully used the patent law and drug administration policy in the United States, and took advantage of the better stability behavior of a hydrate molecule of the drug to extend the exclusivity period of Losec over and over again, which has turned omeprazole into a blockbuster product with cumulative annual sales of more than \$52 billion in 2107.⁵⁹

After the S-isomer-esomeprazole [In 2000, the oral drug esomeprazole magnesium (Nexium) was marketed in Sweden,⁵⁹ and in 2003, esomeprazole sodium for injection came into the market] came into the market and soon replaced the omeprazole market where the patent expired, making it the most successful isomer development precedent. Although Nexium showed only a 3% improvement in clinical trial efficacy against Losec,⁶⁰ annual sales of esomeprazole rose from \$580 million in 2001 to a peak of \$5.2 billion in 2010, thanks to the successful marketing by AstraZeneca and the shift of doctors' interest from H₂ receptor antagonists to proton pump inhibitors. Despite sales in 2019 dropping to \$1.483 billion without patent protection, total global annual sales from 2001 to 2019 had exceeded \$65 billion.⁶¹ Still, it is inevitable that there will be new anti-peptic ulcer drugs with new mechanisms or best curative effect whose cumulative annual sales exceed those of omeprazole or esomeprazole. So far, the global cumulative annual sales of all proton pump inhibitors, including lansoprazole, rabeprazole, pantoprazole, ilaprazole, etc., have exceeded US\$180 billion. This concentratedly reflects the huge economic value produced by the change in the treatment behavior of peptic ulcer etc.

Peg-filgrastim is an improved drug of feiglistin, a polyethylene glycol-conjugated form of granulocyte colony-stimulating factor.⁵⁹ Through PEG modification, the half-life of the drug is greatly prolonged. The injection interval was more than 14

days. Although pegfilgrastim and filgrastim are equally effective, after upgrading, the compliance of peg-filgrastim was greatly improved, which activated the drug demand and extended the life cycle of the product. As a result of the change of drug administration behavior, the global cumulative annual sales of pegfilgrastim had exceeded US \$52.2 billion by 2017.⁵⁹

What can be predicted in the future is that in the cycle of 10 to 30 years after the launch of drugs, in some major disease treatment fields, there will inevitably be drugs with annual cumulative sales of more than \$50 billion and more drugs with annual cumulative sales of more than \$30 billion, which will promote the economic development of this field. In the future, new anti-peptic ulcer drugs will also replace today's proton pump inhibitors. And the pharmaceutical enterprises, which have lost their original leading position in this segment, may become a chaser, or try to achieve new growth through mergers and acquisitions, or may decline. But even if the original leader falters, there will surely be other companies with new therapeutic mechanism drugs or modified new drugs that can manage well to replace them in the main therapeutic areas, and the industry itself is unlikely to falter as long as the population remains relatively stable.

At present, the global sales of antitumor drugs have exceeded \$152 billion,⁶² and even the highly toxic doxorubicin with the change of dosage form to liposome, its global sales exceeded \$1 billion in 2019.⁶³ However, in clinical practice, most anti-tumor drugs need combination therapy or sequential therapy to maintain the life of patients with a low quality of life. However, with the progress of medical science, most of the current mainstream antitumor drugs, such as doxorubicin and cis-platinum, will be mostly eliminated once appropriate antitumor target is found or new treatment strategies are implemented. As the clinical treatment of oncotherapy increases from the current sequential therapy to a monotherapy model, a significant change in the efficiency of oncotherapy is inevitable, and new economic growth in this field should be anticipated.

Due to the need for prevention, it is an inevitable event that the global sales of COVID-19 vaccines will exceed US\$ 100 billion in three years. Preventive behavior has led to structural changes in the profitability of the pharmaceutical industry's segments in the near future.

It can be seen that the cumulative sales of drugs involved in the changes in medical or health behavior caused by only dozens of drugs have increased by more than US \$ 1.15 trillion.²

10 The Change of Medical Behavior, perhaps decrease of Industry Income, but the Significant Improvement of Global Economy or Security or Health

Although the change or improvement of medical behavior in the treatment of diseases may sometimes lead to the decrease or increase of benefits on the pharmaceutical industry itself, they may bring significant improvement to the global economy and more security to mankind. However, this kind of project is sometimes difficult to achieve only under the market economy mechanism, which needs the economic support of the government.

10.1 Changes in malaria treatment behaviors

For example, malaria has brought a heavy economic burden to individuals and countries,^{64,65} the global distribution of GDP per capita shows a significant correlation between malaria and poverty, and the economic growth rate of malaria endemic countries is low.⁶⁶ However, after 70 years of efforts, China has been awarded a malaria-free certification from WHO, which is a remarkable achievement for a country that reported 30 million malaria cases annually in the 1940s.⁶⁷ However, the vast majority of the pharmaceutical factories that produce anti-malaria drug have stopped production because there is no economic benefit in producing these drugs, although antimalarial drugs reduce the transaction costs of society.

10.2 Changes of treatment behaviors in common cold or seasonal influenza

Pharmacobehavioral economics or medical behavioral economics or healthy behavioral economics or clinical behavioral economics etc.(Including: Behavioral economics of Traditional Chinese Medicine or Chinese Medicine Behavioral Economics^{7-1A}) can be said to be a combination of science, technology and art. What we often see is that under normal circumstances, it usually takes four days to a week for ordinary people or even some doctors to recover from a cold, and some of them have to suspend work or study,⁶⁸ and 44.5% of respondents in the USA reported work/school absenteeism (usually 1-2 days) during a cold.⁶⁹ However, viral cold is regarded as a self-limiting disease in medicine.⁷⁰ Some popular science knowledge or media even suggest not taking medicine after catching a cold,^{71,72} but to fight it by drinking more water and sleeping more, and waiting about 5-7 days for the cold to recover.^{71,72} However, the author believes that there is a certain degree of medical error in the formulation that common cold is regarded as a self-limiting disease. As a result, a few people may be forced to start expensive long-term treatment, and some even lose their lives, because they do not take effective treatment, causing the virus to invade the heart or kidney, inducing myocarditis, or nephritis or nephrotic syndrome etc.^{73,74} More than ten years ago, it usually took a few days for the author to recover from a cold. After that, once the author has a viral cold or seasonal influenza, he usually does not need to suspend work and is usually cured in about one day. If it takes more than 2 days to be cured, the author must repeatedly reflect on why he has not done well. Why didn't you take medicine in the best therapeutic time window and so on (The best treatment time window should typically be within half an hour.)? And you must be vigilant to make mistakes next time. However, it is usually difficult for ordinary people to reach the author's level of medical care.

In fact, colds or seasonal flu are a global burden. In 2001, the economic cost of productivity loss caused by common cold is close to US \$25 billion,⁷⁵ of which \$16.6 billion, \$8 billion and \$230 million are attributed to on-the-job productivity loss, absenteeism and caregiver absenteeism respectively. The average annual total economic burden of influenza to the healthcare system and society in the United States was \$11.2 billion (\$6.3-\$25.3 billion),⁷⁶ of which the number of days of lost productivity is 20.1 million. The average annual number of emergency room visits caused by influenza in China is 3 million,⁷⁷ the number of excess deaths from respiratory diseases is 90,000, and the total economic burden related to influenza is 26.381 billion yuan(\$4.08 billion). Perhaps the medical community of some countries

or regions may carry out some randomized double-blind controlled trials according to the situation of drugs approved by their own countries, and then develop multiple specific programs to rapidly treat common cold or influenza that is prone to occur in daily life.

If the treatment cycle for colds or seasonal influenza can be remarkably shortened, it should certainly help to reduce the burden of medical insurance and the loss of productivity, not simply for a regional or national economy, but also its social benefits will be significant.

10.3 The subversive or revolutionary or breakthrough changes in hypertension treatment behaviors, the hypertension standard and definition?

In medicine or pharmacy, sometimes finding an effective and subversive treatment strategy may even be better than the economic and social benefits of developing ten new drugs. At present, hypertension is the largest life-threatening disease in the world and one of the most common diseases in China. The prevalence of hypertension is 18.0 - 44.7%.⁷⁸ Over the past two decades, pharmacology textbooks have very seriously expounded the views that hypertension is incurable, long-term medication and lifetime therapy is needed.^{79,80} However, the author unexpectedly found a few years ago that some hypertension can still be cured if the treatment is reasonable. After stopping the therapeutic drugs, there is no need to take any antihypertensive drugs for several years. When there is no external factor, it usually will not lead to the recurrence of hypertension within 3-4 years, but the end point of treatment should not be within 140 / 90mmHg according to the current Chinese standard of hypertension, it must be reduced and stabilized to the normal value 3-10 years before the onset. In addition, the body should not have other abnormal sensations at the same time, just like before the abnormal blood pressure.

In 2017, the American Heart Association (AHA) revised the hypertension standard or guideline to define hypertension as $\geq 130 / 80$ mmHg, replacing the previous 140 / 90mmHg hypertension diagnostic standard. This is the first time that the AHA and the American College of cardiology (ACC) have redefined hypertension in 14 years.⁸¹ This change will make the prevalence of hypertension among adults aged 18 and over in American reach 45.4%.⁸¹ Although some people believe that this will lead to overtreatment of hypertension, the author believes that this standard value is still high or unreasonable, and it should be revised again. The standard of hypertension should take the long-term normal value before onset as the normal standard. If there is a fluctuation of 5-6%, whether hypertension occurs after excluding accidental factors should be considered, especially for the population aged between 18-60 years. For example, if the long-term normal value of blood pressure before onset is 110/70mmHg, even if the blood pressure reaches 168/146mmHg after onset, it should be reduced and stabilized to 110 /70mmHg even after several months of treatment, so as to be considered reasonable and reduce to the normal level. After treatment, many people may think that their blood pressure falls below the hypertension standard (AHA), for example, 125/79 mmHg is normal. As a result, they may form chronic hypertension, but need long-term medication or lifelong medication. Of course, lowering the standard means that insurance companies need to pay more

fees in the short term, but if patients with early hypertension can be cured, they may not need to take any antihypertensive drugs for several years. In addition to the possible decline in the benefits of the antihypertensive sector of pharmaceutical companies, the economic benefits of medical insurance companies and patients should be greatly improved, and the burden of the nation should also be greatly reduced. The data that needs to be known is that 67 million Americans suffer from high blood pressure, which costs the nation US\$47.5 billion each year.⁸² The American Heart Association estimated that the cost of cardiovascular disease (CVD) care and productivity losses are projected to rise from \$555 billion in 2015 to \$1.1 trillion in 2035.⁸³

There are similar errors or problems in the definition of hypertension in the 2018 ESC / ESH guidelines.⁸³⁻¹ The definition of hypertension should not be $> 140 / 90$ mmHg, and the starting point of initial treatment of hypertension should not wait until blood pressure $\geq 140 / 90$ mmHg. Any blood pressure that exceeds the patient's average normal blood pressure 3-10 years ago should be considered as hypertension. The high normal value of blood pressure (130-139/85-89mmHg) should be hypertension, rather than a deceptive "normal value", so effective measures should be taken to actively treat it, otherwise it may form chronic hypertension and damage target organs. If an 18-year-old patient's average normal blood pressure three years ago was in a range of $(90 / 60 \text{ mmHg} \leq, \geq 120 / 80 \text{ mmHg})$, the current blood pressure range (120-129 / 80-84mmHg) should not be regarded as normal, and effective measures should be taken for treatment, otherwise it may form chronic hypertension and damage target organs.

The current guidelines for the clinical treatment of hypertension do not even consider that hypertension can be cured in the design ideas (Not only does it include the World Health Organization's guidelines for the treatment of hypertension on August 24, 2021),⁸³⁻² which also leads to the mistake of the guidelines for the clinical medication of hypertension. The first occurrence or early stage of hypertension should be cured as soon as possible. If the antihypertensive effect of a single drug is not ideal, combined administration or other effective means should be considered as soon as possible. However, many people believe that since medical textbooks and clinical treatment guidelines for hypertension recognize that hypertension needs lifelong drug treatment, resulting in behavioral inertia of treatment in some people when hypertension occurs for the first time. They hardly treat or treat for the purpose of cure, just think that it should be controlled to a certain range, which is just misled by the guidelines. More importantly, the definition and standard of hypertension have been wrong for a long time, which makes many people's blood pressure rise for a long time instead of being considered hypertension. Under the guidance of this long-term misconception, this not merely leads to increasing patients with hypertension, but also makes it more and more difficult to control. Although a large-scale research organized by WHO, reported by the Lancet on August 24, 2021, found that the number of patients with hypertension aged 30-79 doubled from 648 million to 1,278 million in the 30 years from 1990 to 2019,⁸³⁻² the author believes that the number of real patients with hypertension in the planet far exceeds 1,278 million. This has also made the

whole society pay a fairly high price and countless lives for hypertension and stroke induced for decades. Economic and productivity losses are likely to exceed \$1 trillion.

At present, the purpose of antihypertensive treatment or the important issue of antihypertensive treatment is not to reduce blood pressure itself, but whether antihypertensive treatment can enhance the quality of life (live better) or live longer. However, this guiding ideology seems rational, but it hinders the correct treatment of hypertension.

If the terminology hypertension continues to be used in patients with elevated blood pressure, the meaning and treatment guidelines of the borderline hypertension should be altered. The blood pressure of patients in the critical hypertension range should be hypertension, but in this blood pressure range, the patient's subjective abnormal feeling may not be obvious. However, even so, effective treatment measures should be taken to restore and stabilize the blood pressure to the patient's average normal blood pressure range 3-10 years ago(usually within a range of 90 / 60 mmHg \leq , \geq 120 / 80 mmHg). Their hypertension may be considered cured.

It should be noted that rapidly reducing blood pressure to a specific normal value may not cure hypertension to a certain extent. Usually, another drug or other effective measures (including acupuncture, sports, adjustment of living habits,etc.) should be required to solve the root causes of elevated blood pressure and eliminate its adverse effects on the system. At the same time, the patient's behavior, exercise and diet should meet or basically meet the requirements of health management.

The author believes that some patients suffering from hypertension can be cured like gastritis, gastric ulcer and duodenal ulcer. Of course, the cured gastric ulcer may also relapse due to patients' irregular diet. It is necessary to take anti-peptic ulcer drugs famotidine tablets or omeprazole enteric-coated capsules etc. again until they are cured again, so is hypertension.

Albert Einstein once said that, “the mere formulation of a problem is far more essential than its solution”. However, before the issue is solved, countless people must have doubts, not to mention such a big problem in the textbooks. If the core experts responsible for the formulation of hypertension guidelines in the European or American Medical Association do not believe the standpoints and challenge it. If any fund can support this clinical trial research, it is advisable to establish three trial groups in the United States, Europe and China to carry out comparative clinical trials respectively, or carry out a separate confirmatory clinical trial on the cure rate of hypertension with clinical medication behavior or medical behavior changes in China alone, so as to observe whether the current hypertension guidelines of WHO, Europe, the United States and China can be subversive revised in the future.

In order to quickly obtain the verification results, it is advisable to select 40 ~ 60 non-hospitalized subjects with basically normal weight, aged between 30 ~ 50 years and first onset of hypertension for a small sample verification trial. And a compliant hospital and a compliant CRO company will be selected to carry out relevant research, so that relevant operations and processes can comply with the laws and regulations of their respective countries or organizations, and the research can pass the ethical review of applicable hospital. Subjects in the United States and Europe were treated

according to their own clinical guidelines for hypertension. In China, a team led by the author treated the subjects under the supervision of the hospital and CRO company. The continuous administration period of the subject's first treatment shall not exceed four months. The cure standard of hypertension was determined as that there was no recurrence of hypertension within one year after the initial withdrawal and the blood pressure measured on three particular days for three consecutive weeks did not rise to the borderline hypertension again. After healing, the blood pressure should be within the average normal blood pressure range of patients 3-10 years ago (usually within $90 / 60 \text{ mmHg} \leq$, $\geq 120 / 80 \text{ mmHg}$). The cure rate and the frequency of taking antihypertensive drugs again within one year after the initial withdrawal of the three groups of subjects should be compared. If the subjects in the Chinese trial group have another attack of hypertension within one year after the withdrawal of the drugs, and the results show a cure rate of less than 30%, the clinical trial may be regarded as unsuccessful.

Perhaps the subversive or breakthrough revision of medical textbooks and the global guidelines for the treatment of hypertension will be no less efficient than the development of twenty new antihypertensive drugs, or start a new era of curing hypertension. It will also help to significantly reduce the mortality of stroke or cardiovascular disease etc, and a huge loss in productivity.

11 Current Medical Behavioral Economics in COVID-19's Control, Economic Recovery and Ethics in National Governance

We think that we may need to examine pharmacobehavioral economics or medical behavioral economics or health behavioral economics from a far-sighted view.^{1,2} The research object of these new disciplines is not limited to directly generating benefits to promote the economic stability or growth of the industry or region. The prevention of diseases or the assurance of people's health is more important because it is connected to the economic stability or growth of multiple countries or the whole world, or the improvement of national governance or global governance capabilities. The current expansion of the COVID-19 pandemic has made many countries worry about a severe and prolonged global recession. The strategies of combating the outbreak are also closely linked to preventing a prolonged global recession and promoting economic recovery. If some politicians can set aside political baggage, self-interest, act in good faith and conscience, they can be like the water described in the *Tao-Te-Ching*, and effectively learn from the successful medical and health practices of some countries, specifically China, in the prevention and control of the COVID-19 outbreak, it will play an important role in saving lives and the rapid recovery of the global economy.

11.1 Medical or Health behavioral economics in COVID-19's control and the ability to transfer experience" of India, ethics or party ethics and party behavioral economy etc. in national governance

Nowadays, under the circumstances that physical isolation is difficult to be fully implemented; most countries put too much hope on the nationwide vaccination of COVID-19 vaccine or herd immunity to deal with the epidemic of people non-infected with SARS-CoV-2, which is tough to say that there is no view defect in

this strategy. The current production rate of COVID-19 vaccine cannot keep up with the rate of human infection with SARS-CoV-2, which will inevitably lead to the lag of prevention among the public, while the number of patients infected with the virus variant strain is increasing. This makes it hard for the number of new infections to decline steadily once the epidemic breaks out on a large scale, which is particularly prominent in India. Beginning on April 15, 2021, India has added 200,000 to 400,000 confirmed cases for 30 consecutive days,⁸⁴ and the number of daily confirmed deaths has been the first in the world for several consecutive days. In India, now even more than a year after the global outbreak, a large shortage of oxygen and oxygen cylinders have led to many patients' deaths.⁸⁵

According to Soumya Swaminathan,⁸⁶ chief scientist of the WHO, in an interview with CNN on April 26, due to the insufficient capacity of nucleic acid test, only about 2 million people in India are tested every day, while the average test positive rate in the whole India is 15%. On May 20, the positive rate of Goa (Population: 1.45 million) reached an astonishing 43%.⁸¹ The population of Goa is only about 1/7 of that of Wuhan, but the number of confirmed cases of SARS-CoV-2 infection is far more than that of Wuhan. Karnataka (Population: 61.09 million) ranked second in India with a positive rate of 32%.⁸⁷ Many medical or WHO experts also questioned the accuracy of the Indian government's figures, suggesting that the actual number of cases might be 10 to 30 times higher and the actual number of deaths might be two to five times higher.⁸⁸ One day in April 2021, the mayor of North New Delhi, the capital, said more than 600 people died each day, but the number reported was about 300,⁸⁹ which means someone deliberately underestimated the death toll. According to a joint investigation by four *New York Times* reporters,^{90, 91} 41 cases of COVID-19-related deaths were reported in Bhopal, a major city in central India, within 13 days in mid-April 2021. However, reporters' investigation into the city's crematoria and cemeteries where the bodies of COVID-19-related deaths were handled according to the regulations found that more than 1,000 people died during the same period. Even some crematorium operators have called on the government to truthfully disclose the number of deaths from COVID-19. In rural areas of India, where the epidemic has been particularly severe, some families have been exterminated by COVID-19,⁹² and the bodies of a large number of novel coronavirus-infected victims have been dumped into the Ganges. People in rural areas of India have difficulty using the Internet and finding people to help them on Twitter after being infected. On May 18th, The Economic Times of India reported that three quarters of 5,400 inhabitants of Basi, a village just 1.5 hours' drive from the capital New Delhi, had fallen ill in the past three weeks because of no doctors, health facilities or oxygen. More than 30 people had died and patients were being sent to big cities. Unfortunately, many did not make it to the hospital.⁹²

Chandan Nimje, a 67-year-old retired senior civil servant in India, risked his life to cremate more than 1,300 unclaimed dead bodies died from COVID-19.⁹³ However, one day in April 2021, both he and his wife were infected, but the volunteers of KCYF could not even find an empty bed in the public government hospital. So they had to go to an expensive private hospital, but the doctor told them

to find the expensive and scarce drug Tocilizumab by themselves. At last, he spent all his savings but failed to save their lives. Ironically, on the 8th day of Nimje's death, a local official called his son and said Tocilizumab was available.⁹³ His family and the volunteers of KCYF were very disappointed. The founder of KCYF said that he had helped the family to prepare a lawsuit in the Bombay High Court against the local officials and the commissioners of the National Management Council for the neglect that caused the death of Nimje. "Our thousands of volunteers couldn't find aid for Nimje. Just imagine how difficult it will be for ordinary people due to the attitude of the authorities," said the founder.

However, Wuhan City, which has a population of 11 million, is temporarily designated as the first outbreak of COVID-19 epidemic in the world. Although the positive rate of serum antibodies was 3.2% to 6.9%.⁹⁴⁻⁹⁶ At that time, a large number of patients with very mild or mild symptoms but temporarily with negative nucleic acid test results were reversed by effective means outside the hospital, and some asymptomatic or mild patients who could not receive nucleic acid test at that time but might actually have positive nucleic acid test results were reversed too, making it possible that until now, the final confirmed cases in Wuhan are 50,340 and the total confirmed deaths are 3,869.⁸⁴ The data is supposed to be accurate. According to the article from BMJ, Wuhan experienced approximately 6,000 new deaths in the first quarter of 2020 compared with that of the first quarter of 2019, with 3,653 deaths from COVID-19, 920 from other pneumonia and 1,400 deaths from other chronic diseases.⁹⁷ Wuhan completely controlled the epidemic in 4 months under the circumstances of little experience. The contrast between Wuhan and India is stark. Wuhan's economy is now running well, growing by 58% in the first quarter of 2021 compared with the same period last year.⁹⁸ The first author of this article, together with Prof. Qing Guo (from Zhejiang Chinese Medical University) and Prof. Shangqin Liu (Zhongnan Hospital of Wuhan University) etc, proposed a new strategy for COVID-19 pandemic control for the first time in January 2020 [treatment and preventive strategy of cluster shunt and group-dredging management, drug-blocking preventive measures and rapid discovery, rapid prevention, rapid treatment, rapid isolation(4R-DPTI). Some modifications have been made in the process of implementation.] In the process of submission, on February 1, 2020, we received a letter from the chief editor of a world-renowned medical journal, requesting that the strategy be shared with WHO and local government authorities. We immediately replied and agreed. In fact, one of the corresponding authors of this article, Prof. Qing Guo from Zhejiang Chinese Medical University, happened to spend the traditional Spring Festival holiday in Yichang City, Hubei Province at that time. However, regardless of the danger, he personally assisted the government in combating COVID-19 in Yichang, and promoted the implementation of this strategy. Although Yichang is a famous tourist city with a permanent population of about 4,137,900, with the world-famous Three Gorges Dam, and only about 2 hours' drive away from Wuhan by high-speed railway, the total confirmed cases was only 931 until now,⁸⁴ ranking the 13th in Hubei Province in terms of per capita morbidity. India is a country with a population of 1.353 billion. As of June 13, 2021, there are only 116,280

confirmed cases and 5,283 confirmed deaths in China.⁸⁴ However, as of the same day, the total confirmed cases officially announced by India have reached 29,439,989 million and 370,384 confirmed deaths.⁸⁴ The number of confirmed deaths in India is about three times the number of confirmed cases in China.

In the author's opinion, firstly, from the perspectives of management and medical behavioral economics, despite China's successful experience of defeating this outbreak, India has showed a special lack of "the ability to transfer experience" (which senior management leaders must have) in fighting against COVID-19, and cannot effectively implement prevention in a large scope or large population. As a consequence, the number of people infected with SARS-CoV-2 has skyrocketed recently! Many companies shut down. Secondly, there is a serious deficiency in the cognition of COVID-19 treatment, and there may be a lack of effective measures to reverse a large number of patients with very slight or mild symptoms with temporary negative nucleic acid test results (For example, 45 year old male close contacts in Shenzhen. During the period of isolation and observation from May 21 to June 1, 2021, the results of 11 nucleic acid tests were all negative. But on June 5, his nucleic acid test was positive.⁹⁹), so that such patients become positive in nucleic acid tests in large numbers. Thirdly, there may be a lack of effective measures for the fast control and reversal of a large number of asymptomatic patients but with positive nucleic acid results and patients with mild symptoms, so that a large number of asymptomatic patients or patients with positive nucleic acid results but very mild symptoms cannot be quickly reversed and become mild patients, and many mild patients cannot be cured quickly and turn into severe patients. The severe or critical patients were not effectively controlled, which led to the overburden of medical institutions and the increasing number of deaths.

Such a tragic situation has led many people to question India's disregard of bioethics, administrative ethics and political ethics, as well as India's low governance capacity or flawed governance structure, which is far less capable of controlling the epidemic and caring for life in Pakistan and Bangladesh which used to be part of Greater India. (According to the proportion of the total population of the three countries, the number of new confirmed cases reported by Indian officials in 2 months from April 1 to May 31, 2021, is 9.86 times more than that of Pakistan (15,929,162 vs 253,096) and 10.01 times more than that of Bangladesh (15,929,162 vs 189,245).⁸⁴ For the official total confirmed cases proportional to the total population, India has six times as many as Pakistan and five times as many as Bangladesh; For the official total confirmed deaths proportional to the total population, India has 4.62 times as many as Pakistan (187,122 vs 6,345) and 6.24 times as many as Bangladesh (187,122 vs 3,563).⁸⁴ We hold that the numbers of cases with actual symptoms and total deaths may be two to five times as many as those from India's official announcement, but even that will put an intolerably high strain on the health system and the economic recovery.

We understand the embarrassment of the Indian government on the COVID-19 data, and the hard work of Indian politicians or statesmen or media personnel during this period of time. But if it continues to conceal the epidemic excessively and

publicizing that the SARS-CoV-2 infection can be prevented and controlled by cow dung or cow dung chip or cow urine,^{100,101} instead of seriously studying the differences and success or failure of medication behavior or prevention behavior of the countries with outstanding performance in COVID-19 prevention and control and learning from their strong points, it is not only hard to control the epidemic quickly and effectively, but also possible to expand the scope of the epidemic with the variant strain. It may also swamp the economy of India and the lives of ordinary people, and hinder the recovery of the world economy. Apart from this, Indian politicians engaged in election campaigns and religious rallies,¹⁰²⁻¹⁰⁴ resulting in a large number of civilians who were infected with SARS-CoV-2 and died after gathering, and caused many infected people with highly infectious mutant strains to spread to other countries, which seriously affected the hosting of the Tokyo Olympic Games and the pace of global economic recovery.

Besides, the outbreak in India has affected the economic recovery of individual regions in China. At the end of April 2021, 11 crew members on a cargo ship that arrived in Zhoushan, one of China's three major ship repair bases via ports in India and other countries, tested positive for nucleic acid. As a consequence, the Zhoushan municipal government issued excessively strict control measures, and the incoming ships were not allowed to detect nucleic acid in Zhoushan. According to preliminary statistics from the companies, about 240 ship repair orders have been cancelled in just over 20 days after nucleic acid testing in Zhoushan. The amount of lost orders exceeded 200 million US dollars.¹⁰⁵

What's more, it was reported that, because of COVID-19, India had more than 15 million unemployed people in May, and the unemployment rate has exceeded 11.9%.¹⁰⁶ More Indians are ready to immigrate to Europe and America etc. in order to avoid the third wave of epidemic.¹⁰⁷

Therefore, perhaps the people of India themselves should consider evaluating or motivating or mobilizing Indian government or local governments from the perspectives of preventive medicine, infectious diseases, epidemiology, econometrics, medical behavioral economics, and quantitative administrative ethics or quantitative public management ethics or quantitative political ethics or quantitative party ethics or quantitative politics (metrological administrative ethics or metrological public administration ethics or metrological public management ethics or metrological political ethics or metrological party ethics) etc. and exhorting politicians to value lives,^{7A-10A} correct mistakes, and return to the moral and right track; they should also urge the Indian government or state governments to improve the accuracy, authenticity and credibility of the information released on the COVID-19 epidemic in India, so as to benefit India and the international community in providing targeted support to the prevention and control of the COVID-19 in different regions of India, saving lives and contributing to world peace, stability and economic recovery. In addition, it is hard to say that the prevention and control of COVID-19 epidemic is not a political behavior or political party action of a government formed by different political parties. India should also reflect on itself from the perspective of political behavioral economics, party behavioral economics and government (public or state)

behavioral economics.^{11A-13A} China's success in controlling COVID-19 and achieving rapid economic recovery and positive growth can be said to be the success of political behavioral economy to a certain extent. But to a greater extent, it should be the success of government behavioral economy or party behavioral economy. In fact, the secret of China's rapid economic growth has also been closely related to the behavior of political parties or government in the past 40 years, which can be judged or evaluated by many empirical studies. After more than 40 years of reform and opening up, China has successfully lifted more than 700 million rural poor people out of poverty and become the country with the largest number of poverty reducing people in the world.¹⁰⁸ If we broaden this topic a bit, it is not difficult for many people to investigate and discover the following situation. In the past ten years, many Chinese students studying in the UK, Europe, and the United States may be the descendants of poor rural families who did not have enough food or were malnourished 40 years ago. In terms of subjective initiative, the formulation and change of any policy or system or institution is meaningless without the response and dedication of the citizens and units from all walks of life. When the masses and these units feel that the policy or institution released by the Chinese government is to guide them along the right path and have a bright and glorious future, their passion, enthusiasm, imagination, boundless creativity, diligence and spirit of fearing no difficulties and obstacles are enough to overcome thousands of difficulties and overcome ten thousands of obstacles, creating a brilliant and fabulous record for China's economic take-off, It has made immortal and marvelous contributions to the poverty alleviation of 700 million Chinese people and made them rich. This constructs a unique national behavioral economics of China's economic take-off, which can be confirmed by many empirical studies. In the last eight years, more than 1800 grass-roots poverty alleviation cadres have fixed their lives on the journey of poverty alleviation.¹⁰⁹ In addition to the dedication of grassroots cadres, it is hard not to say that it does not represent the success of agricultural behavioral economy, rural behavioral economy, enterprise behavioral economy, regional behavioral economy, trade behavioral economy, national behavioral economy, government behavioral economy, party behavioral economy, real estate behavioral economy, tourism economy, food behavioral economy, consumption behavioral economy, education, train, innovation, etc. (Relevant empirical research can be carried out from the following disciplines, such as national behavioral economics or enterprise behavioral economics or regional behavioral economics or trade behavioral economics or real estate behavioral economics).

^{14A-18A,110-147-166}Just like some soccer fans who like Cristiano Ronaldo may not like Messi, or vice versa. Maybe some countries or people don't like China's ruling party, but the unavoidable and undeniable figures are that China's GDP in 1978 was only 211.9 billion US dollars,¹⁶⁷ rising to 14.7 trillion US dollars in 2020,¹⁶⁸ ranking second in the world. Furthermore, 700 million people have been lifted out of poverty. In every five years, the government and the ruling party have issued many policies,¹⁶⁹ and a large number of staff at all levels of government agencies go to the front line to promote economic development and people's poverty alleviation. This has formed a huge resultant force with the broad masses of people's yearning for a better life and

the expectation of national development. The formation of different incentive mechanisms, the improvement of distribution mechanisms, the regulation of single price system, the stimulation of insufficient material supply, the learning and the transfer of good experience about economic development from various countries, the unceasing improvement of education level and personnel quality, the group stimulation of creativity, continuous creation of regional economic development zones, and the continuous innovation and adjustment of government policies to stimulate the sustainable development have promoted the development of manufacturing, trade and service industries in China.

11.2 The Secrets of China's rapid economic growth or fast economic recovery; comparative political economics; government behavioral economy or party behavioral economy etc. in China, the former Soviet Union and the U.S.

In terms of the broadening of the topics in the previous section, many people may be puzzled by the secrets of China's rapid economic growth or economic development or economic reform or fast economic recovery, and there were different opinions. Perhaps some of the previous explanations were neither comprehensive nor in-depth. However, this epidemic may let many people or countries see the secret of China's rapid economic recovery. If we deeply research China's social structure and current situation, it is not difficult to see that government behavioral economy, party behavioral economy, agricultural economy, rural economy, enterprise behavioral economy, food behavioral economy, regional behavioral economy, trade behavioral economy, national behavioral economy, real estate behavioral economy, tourism behavioral economics, advanced manufacturing economy, domestic peace, education, train, innovation, the establishment of capital markets, diligence, people's pursuit of happy life and self-discipline of the people are fairly important multi engines to promote China's economic reform and development, technological innovation and national prosperity.^{110-166, 170-179} In the early stage of reform and opening up, investment from Hong Kong and overseas Chinese in Southeast Asia played a vital role in promoting the development of China's real economy and regional economy. Usually, a country's economic policies are formulated by the government or the ruling party, no matter what kind of system or institution exists in it. Therefore, the effect or guiding force of the government's behavioral economy or the ruling party's behavioral economy is usually stronger than that of the institutional or system's behavioral economy. This may be due to the fact that the former Soviet Union and China have the same system or institution, but the former Soviet Union collapsed because of its low national governance capacity, while China's economy is still developing and growing.¹⁸⁰⁻¹⁸⁷ Although some of China's policies or economic policies are not perfect or rough or wrong etc., for example, a large number of apartments in cities are not suitable for a traditional family, the real estate policies have major flaws, some places are too dependent on the real estate economy, the real estate economy has a large bubble, and high housing prices restrict the development of regional economy or some industries, etc.¹⁸⁸⁻¹⁹⁷ [According to the survey of the people's Bank of China, in 2019, the housing ownership rates of urban households and households with the lowest income of 20% in China were 96.0% and 89.1% respectively,¹⁹⁷⁻¹ each

household owned 1.5 sets of housing, and the housing mortgage rate of families reached 43.39%.¹⁹⁷⁻¹ However, China has a housing surplus, with a vacancy rate of 11.3% - 26% (In 2015, Tencent.com conducted a sample survey of netizens in 196 cities across the country.¹⁹⁷⁻² The results showed that the overall level of housing vacancy rate in major cities in China was between 22% and 26%, including 22% in first-tier cities, 24% in second-tier cities and 26% in third-tier cities.).¹⁹⁷⁻² The real estate prices in some cities are still rising, far exceeding the purchasing power of residents. A large number of houses are in the hands of real estate speculators, and some people actually own more than 100 houses or apartments.¹⁹⁷⁻³ Regulators have failed to effectively reduce house prices for a long time, return housing to its original function and realize a virtuous circle. For more than a decade, the government's main measure has been to curb house prices by constantly restricting purchases,¹⁹⁷⁻⁴⁻⁷ but house prices have been soaring.¹⁹⁷⁻⁸ From the perspective of the transparency of the transaction and the basic rights and interests of the buyer, the transaction of each apartment according to the actual area was originally the most reasonable and fair.¹⁹⁷⁻⁹⁻¹⁵ However, China has long adopted the transaction mode of calculating the construction area of each apartment, which leads to the purchase of 100 square meters of apartments or offices, which can form up to 50% of the public share, and the homeowner can finally obtain the actual use area of the room of only 50 square meters.¹⁹⁷⁻¹⁵ This kind of real estate economic operation behavior, which is difficult for ordinary people to understand the property right structure, makes the real estate transaction opaque, forms unavoidable corruption, and seriously damages the construction of other necessary facilities, which is loved by real estate developers and hated by real estate buyers.¹⁹⁷⁻⁹⁻¹⁵ Knowing that it forms one of the biggest corruptions in this field, it is easy to be rectified at any time through legal documents by regulators, but it has not been corrected for decades. It can still be expected that in the future economic history, the government behavioral economy, the party behavioral economy, the regional behavioral economy, the trade behavioral economy, short video economics^{18A1}, short video behavioral economics^{18A2}, the live-streaming economics^{18A3}, the live-streaming behavioral economics (live behavioral economics), the tourism behavioral economics^{18A5}, traffic behavioral economics^{18A4}, the enterprise behavioral economy and the national behavioral economy will leave a thick and heavy in colours and patterns in promoting social progress and economic development. It is worth noting that the short video economy, livestreaming economy and traffic economy will not only help promote the economic recovery under the current epidemic, but also may bring huge growth to the regional economy. At present, in China, the relevant annual economic changes or economic growth has exceeded RMB ¥ 1 trillion yuan (\$157.1 billion). It is estimated that the relevant annual economic changes or economic growth in the world should exceed US \$1 trillion within three or four years.

The unavoidable problem is that the demographic structure and geographical environment of China are different from those of the United States or Europe. China's rural population is huge, and the economic conditions of different regions are obviously different. Whether from a political or moral point of view, the government

must spend a lot of energy to solve agricultural and rural problems. However, judging from the poverty alleviation measures and achievements in the past two decades, when the government's policies and actions are implemented in rural areas or agriculture, it can't deny that it is not the success of rural behavioral economy or agricultural behavioral economy, and that they will grow independently as a discipline in the future,^{19A,20A} which should also be demonstrated through empirical research. From the perspective of rural development and government behaviors, China has not simply formed a preliminary model of poverty alleviation based on food behavior economy,¹⁹⁸⁻²⁰¹ but is also exploring ways of deepening poverty alleviation by nutrition behavior economy or combination nutrition behavior economy and education.²⁰²⁻²¹⁰ This will bring a stage for full display of food behavioral economics and nutrition behavioral economics.^{21A,22A}

In the process of Chinese economic soaring, although right-seeking, accounting and auditing distortion, and the Luckin Coffee incident,²¹¹ there are also similar problems in Europe and America, such as Enron, Worldcom scandal, Xerox, etc. in order to maintain the healthy development of the global economy,^{212,213} especially to solve the issues of the authenticity of financial statements of listed companies, it is necessary to carry out the studies based on quantitative accounting or auditing ethics(metrological accounting ethics, metrological auditing ethics).^{23A,24A}

Many people may mistakenly argue that government behavioral economy or party behavioral economy can only be implemented under the Chinese system. However, in the market economy countries, especially in the United States, this kind of government behavioral economy or political behavior economy or party behavior economy is more intense or prominent in some fields.²¹⁴⁻²³⁷ If we need to verify or recognize from the perspective of discipline, we may as well analyze and judge from comparative politics or comparative partics or comparative economics or metrological comparative politics or metrological comparative partics or comparative economics or metrological comparative economics or metrological comparative political economics.^{25A-29A, 84,238-259}

The U.S. government has long subsidized the cultivation or breeding of genetically modified corn, soybeans and pork, strengthened the bulk trade of these commodities exported to China,²⁶⁰⁻²⁶⁴ and showed off these as their political achievements. But neither Trump's Republican government or Biden's democratic government now forbids not merely the US itself, but also the global suppliers, transporting advanced chips or 5G components to China Huawei, or not use US technology to make chips,²⁶⁵⁻²⁶⁸ restricting Chinese students to study in the US,^{269,270} and ordering the world's top 500 China Mobile' China Telecom and CNOOC to withdraw from the NYSE.²⁷¹ In addition, all previous US governments have vigorously promoted Boeing aircraft to the planet to compete with Airbus in Europe,²⁷²⁻²⁷⁴ selectively promoted F16 fighters to other countries.^{275,276} Thirdly, the pork raised with ractopamine in the United States has been allowed to enter the Taiwan market.²⁷⁷⁻²⁸⁰ Fourthly, many European and American governments prohibit Huawei,²⁸¹⁻²⁸³ a private enterprise, from participating in the construction of 5G network in their country, while China does not prohibit Ericsson or Nokia from

participating in the construction of 5G in China at the same time.^{284,285} In March 2021, China Mobile announced the bidding results of the large purchase order: Huawei has no revenue, ZTE is less than 10%, and Nokia ranks first.²⁸⁵ This makes many people feel that China is a market economy country, while many countries in Europe and America have regressed into a feudal imperial power country. It is not difficult to see that all of the above include strong and significant economic behaviors of the government or political parties or nation. The US government or the ruling party unilaterally adopted the policy of increasing import tariffs and banning the export of high-tech products to China, a trade war between China and the United States was triggered. As a result, the transaction costs and transaction expenses of relevant domestic enterprises and the public in the United States increased. Some American enterprises will even lose more than US \$8 billion in sales due to the decrease in exports.²⁶⁶

However, the seemingly rational and actually extreme self-interest behavior of the U.S. government and the ruling party will only force China's advanced manufacturing technology, including high-end chips, to make continuous breakthroughs, which will lead to the greater development of advanced manufacturing economy, the improvement of industrial chain economy, the continuous development of regional economy, and the improvement of internal consumption chain and internal circulation of regional economy. In this way, the United States will lose part of the Chinese market and become passive. If the United States continues to import a large number of goods from China, the trade deficit between China and the United States will continue to increase in the future. Frankly, some considerations of the Republican or democratic governments should be reasonable. Some industries should consider establishing a perfect industrial chain in the United States, forming an internal consumption chain, realizing regional circulation, stabilizing and expanding employment. However, it is not easy for the U.S. capitals to pursue high profits.

Historically, although the United States is a great country, in recent years, there seems to be a lack of farsighted, insightful, public minded and appealing political talents once in 60 years in the American government. It is also possible that these intelligent people have been suppressed or ignored for a long time and cannot stand out, leading to various short-sighted behaviors of the U.S. government and political parties for a long time. From the actual situation, the U.S. government or their main political parties lack enough effective negative feedback operation mechanism, which leads to the extremalization of the U.S. government's foreign economic policy and governance policy in recent years, which will inevitably form cumulative negative effects in the future.

From 1985 to 2015, China disarmed 2.3 million people five times,²⁸⁶ devoted its main energy to the development of industry, agriculture and economy, carried out scientific and technological innovation, and successfully solved the problem of poverty alleviation of more than 700 million people. It is a country that really has republican ideas with people. More importantly, the Chinese people develop the economy through their own hard-work, get rid of poverty and help their friends, rather than solve the passive issues of domestic economic backwardness or poverty and

unemployment through military aggression or plunder. Morally, such a nation or country should belong to a nation or country with noble sentiments. Such a culture should belong to a culture of peace and should be widely rewarded and respected, highly praised and promoted by educated or well-educated people on the earth. This can be seen in the collectables of the Palace Museum, China's largest museum, which were basically created by the Chinese themselves rather than from plunder! If we need to further study them by modern science, we might as well use metrological collection or collection ethics to carry out empirical studies.^{287,288}

11.3 Economic crisis and war behavioral economy, metrological military ethics, future behavioral economy and world peace

Looking back on history, when the world was facing an economic crisis, some Western politicians actually proposed to fight against China and plunder wealth to get rid of their own crisis. This is apparently turning military behavioral economics or defense behavioral economics or war behavioral economics into a discipline of plundering wealth.^{30A-32A} Chinese people are usually influenced by Taoism and Buddhism. Many people are fairly surprised and unbelievable when they hear that American politicians are going to war and plunder China. Isn't this an evil signal from criminals? Does the world still need justice, righteousness and ethics? It is even more surprising that such inferior politicians come from the United States, which has the highest quality of university education in the world, and that American society can tolerate them. It is almost completely subversive for many Chinese people to subvert their understanding of western freedom and democracy. In the author's values, military behavioral economics or defense behavioral economics or war behavioral economics should be designed to consider defeating evil with just military action at a low cost. It is now actually advocated by inferior politicians as a means to plunder the wealth of hardworking countries or people! Considering that westerners generally believe in religion, starting from the idea of righteousness and world peace, it has to make people feel that the religious beliefs in the United States and Europe have great defects and need to be further revised. Taking into account Taoist or Buddhist interpretations for justice, righteousness and ethics, and their ideas of persuading people to be good, delivering all living creatures, and their contribution to the solution of certain problems in modern quantum science or the formation of theories,²⁸⁹⁻²⁹³ the integration and development of Western religions and Taoist or Buddhist ideas are likely to be the inevitable trend of history. Otherwise, Western religious beliefs may become a moderator for some people who do bad things at night, go to church to regret during the day, and then do bad things the next night to seek psychological comfort or relief.

However, the political parties and governments in the United States and Europe have formed gangs and restricted everywhere in order to stop China's progress and development in advanced technology in recent years.^{265-270,281-283} This makes many kind-hearted or Chinese people who like Western religions feel that these behaviors are unjust and unethical. Does the earth have to go backwards to conform to the essence of western politics and economics? When China led the United States or Britain in GDP in the 19th century, it did not curb the economic development and

technological leadership of them. It is hard for us to imagine that in today's era of emphasizing freedom, equality and monogamy, on February 18, 2020, the Utah Senate passed a bill to legalize polygamy by a unanimous vote.²⁹⁴ It may also be difficult for all people to say that one system is absolutely good and the other is absolutely bad. Tolerance for people with different personalities or different systems or countries reflects one's cultivation and quality. Historians should come to a conclusion about the merits of a national system three hundred years later.

Unfortunately, the statesman once in 60 years in American society may still be suppressed and fail to stand out, while a few self-interest and selfish politicians who lack moral cultivation like to provoke conflict and war.²⁹⁵⁻³⁰³ These politicians may be confused by themselves, or they may be blinded by the funds of arms dealers to support the election and misunderstand the course of human development. They think that when the earth is destroyed, people leaving the earth must pass the 100 meter or 1500 meter track within the specified time. However, the competition between different countries in human society is not a race of 42.195 km marathon, nor a zero sum game. The backward people or countries will get nothing. As long as there are countries in human society, it is inevitable that different countries will catch up with each other in terms of technical level and economic scale in the long river of history. A situation in which one country takes the lead in a certain field for a period of time and another country takes the lead for a period of time. No country can always be at the peak in all fields. In particular, if an extremely self-interest country lacks common values and good moral standards, it may split itself when there are irreconcilable internal contradictions.

No one can swallow a cake as big as the earth! No country can lead in every field. When the United States prohibits the export of high-end chips and high-end chip technology to China, it will inevitably force China to increase the investment in high-end chip technology, leading to the continuous breakthrough and greater development of advanced manufacturing industry in China, without relying on the technology and market of the United States or Europe. At the same time, it also forces China to increase investment in other key technology fields, which will inevitably lead to the continuous breakthrough and development of new energy, new material technology and new information technology, etc.

At present, many Chinese enterprises are promoting energy-saving and emission reduction technologies related to solar energy and developing new energy technologies such as hydrogen energy with the support of policies. It can be predicted that when energy behavioral economics, material behavioral economics, chemical behavioral economics, advanced manufacturing behavioral economics, information behavioral economics, information technology behavioral economics and gene behavioral economics(including: transgenic behavioral economics) become independent disciplines in China for about 10-30 years,^{33A-36A} China is bound to gradually take the lead in relevant key fields. With the revolutionary progress of new energy technology, it is possible to make the Persian Gulf a sightseeing channel for many tourists in about 30-40 years. Some military industrial enterprises may consider not supporting politicians to sell more munitions to increase profits or economic

aggregate by promoting conflict or launching war or maintaining military confrontation, nor maintaining technological leadership by suppressing China, which is developing peacefully and not by launching wars of aggression and plunder. Instead, they should consider partial industrial transformation or increasing investment to develop new energy industry, new material industry, advanced technology manufacturing industry, information technology economy, new pharmaceutical industry and new agricultural economy, so as to take the lead or partial lead in the industry channel, share the downstream market to develop the economy and jointly build world peace.

11.4 Tracing the origin of the COVID-19, cultural levels or moral concepts and levels of Europe and America, the grading of politicians and statesmen, the grading evaluation criteria for statesmen as global peace fighters, and metrological military ethics etc., strategies to control the epidemic, the proposal to establish the Nobel Prize in Ethics

Because our article that disclosed false problems of CAPRIE trial's data was always rejected, in the process of discussing arguments and seeking opinions, overseas friends told the author that the practice in Europe and America is not to report such problems even if you know the truth, otherwise, you will be regarded as an informer, and you will probably not find a job. No company is willing to hire you, and this article may be difficult to publish. The author asks, don't they need to pay attention to the life safety of patients taking this drug? Friends are silent. Therefore, despite the submission and publication of this paper, no one in European and American professional institutions or regulatory agencies have taken the initiative to consider such issues, and the relevant economic management journals have not shown the minimum business ethics, and the relevant medical professional journals have not shown medical ethics and evidence-based medicine principles they emphasize every day, but have all rejected the manuscript. The actual behavior, oral and written all advocate that the medical ethics and moral standards seem to be manifested in two levels, namely, heaven and earth, and no matter the market or regulator, they all fail. This completely subverts the moral concepts and levels of Europe and America in the author's mind, and also subverts the European and American cultures and cultural levels in the author's mind. Before writing the article, the author always thought that the culture and morality in Europe and America had a most notable level, but now he has to come to the opposite conclusion. Although the process is hard or unbelievable, it arouses the author's desire to open a new discipline of ethics, economics or politics etc. from the level of moral culture, and promote the comparative study of between European, American cultural ethics and Chinese culture that has been circulating for thousands of years. The author also thanks for such hardships.

The author is not keen on politics, and is a non-party figure. He has not participated in political activities for about twenty years. But after seeing COVID-19 break out, the United States almost became a politicized country and society.^{295-299;304-308} Some European and American politicians even disregarded China in the principle of poison and basically disregard the laws and principles of science. The administrative inaction of some governments in the United States and Europe has

led to a large-scale outbreak of the epidemic in the countries. Instead, they pass the buck, plant, claim compensation and stigmatize China.³⁰⁹⁻³¹² These behaviors are rare in the world and completely violate the most basic moral concepts in Chinese culture such as Taoism, Confucianism and the moral qualities that human beings must have as a civilized person. All these shocked the author!

Some American scholars have mentioned that after the outbreak of the COVID-19 epidemic, the reaction of the United States to the epidemic is becoming more and more politicized, and the prevention of wearing masks has also been politicized.³⁰⁴⁻³⁰⁸ However, vaccination has played a key role in eliminating the pandemic and has been politicized by the media. Recently, dozens of countries have appealed to the WHO for opposing the politicization of the United States and other countries to trace the source of the novel coronavirus, rather than scientization.³⁰⁹⁻³¹³

The author does not know why the SARS-CoV-2 virus was framed for the Wuhan Institute of Virology in this way by western politicians? How much do politicians know about the Institute from the front or side? Because of the fake reports in the US media, the author's classmate working in the United States had several times thought that the Wuhan Institute of Virology had leaked the SARS-CoV-2 virus, and thought that three staff members were infected with the SARS-CoV-2, and suggested that the author ask the classmates working in the institute. The author joked with him that you had crossed the Pacific Ocean, arrived in the United States, which is known as the world's highest academic level, drank a Pacific ink and had a high degree of education. Why do you repeatedly believe a lie and ask about it? Since you are very disgusted that a famous American media lied every day during the Trump campaign, which led to his defeat, why do you stubbornly believe in the American media and there is a phenomenon of split thinking? Where is your "ability to transfer experience"? Because he is a good friend, the author can make fun of casually.

In February last year, we discovered that there were serious methodological problems in the origin-tracing of novel coronavirus in Wuhan Huanan seafood market, which was first discovered in China. The COVID-19 outbreak in Wuhan could not be caused by wild animals such as bats or pangolins or snakes. Every year, the author buys seafood in the Seafood Market irregularly, and walks around the stalls in the west of the market almost every time, and never sees bat. According to the distribution of infected patients, the infected employees in the seafood market are probably caused by the novel coronavirus in seafood or packages from cold chain. However, after the paper was completed in March last year, it was rejected many times. It was not until June to December last year that imported seafood products or their packages of cold chains with the SARS-CoV-2 broke out in other markets in China,^{314,315} which made China and the world widely aware of another possibility, but it delayed the truth for at least three months.

Because the first infected case and multiple cases were found to be employees of stalls selling seafood in this market, they were wrongly accused by many less rigorous articles that bats or imprecise lifestyles led to the outbreak of COVID-19 in Wuhan. As a result, China and even the whole world unanimously and incorrectly condemned bats at that time, and then China promulgated the law prohibiting the hunting of

almost all wild animals, including wild boars, snakes, bamboo rats, etc., and even bamboo rats or snakes bred in large numbers in many rural families were forced to be put to death, and some families lost all of their investment and suffered heavy losses, which was originally a means for these families to make a living. However, correspondingly, some states in the United States have allowed to eat snakes, wild boars, crocodiles, etc., the Florida government has called on people to eat pythons (which are made into first-class protected animals in China),³¹⁶ and Texas also holds the World Rattlesnake Food Festival every year,³¹⁷ which has a history of more than 35 years. In addition, Australians are crazy about eating kangaroos, although it is their national treasure.³¹⁸

A few years ago, after receiving a consultation from a veterinary friend of the author, African swine fever virus (ASFV) caused all the pigs under his management to die within four or five days after infection, all the pigs in some pig farms died, and the farmers suffered heavy losses. He requested guidance for the treatment of pigs. After emergency research, it is preliminarily found that about 6 of 10 sick pigs can be saved after treatment, but all of them die without treatment after onset. The cured sick pigs are full of vitality and healthy growth, and there are no new symptoms of infection when mixed with other fresh pigs infected by ASFV. Considering that the improved treatment scheme may be improved to cure 8-9 out of 10 sick pigs and change the wasteful practice of large-scale culling of sick pigs, the author discussed the possibility of cooperation with his classmate working at Wuhan Institute of Virology. Unexpectedly, it was very shocking that their unit did not have the qualification to carry out the animal experiment of ASFV. Although they applied for the research qualification, the Ministry of Agriculture did not approve it. Although ASF is a severe infectious disease, it does not infect people, and it has never been reported to infect people and other common animals. It can cause almost 100% of the deaths of sick pigs,³¹⁹ which has not been solved in the world for 110 years. For the research on a major severe infectious disease affecting the pig industry, a national Wuhan Institute of Virology was unable to apply for qualification. The author can't help feeling the serious disadvantages of China's scientific research system. The author has lived in the courtyard of the hospital since childhood. He has always believed that treating diseases and relieving suffering are the instinct and kindness of capable people, which is fully in line with the Hippocratic Oath. However, in reflection, a top National Institute of virus in China has even been unreasonable in its application for the prevention and control of ASFV. How can it be possible to synthesize the novel coronavirus without a documented normal research and approval process? It was reported that Shi Zhengli of Wuhan Institute of Virology provided the sequence of bat coronavirus to professor Ralph S Baric of North Carolina, who synthesized a new coronavirus that can be fatal to the human body.³²⁰ Moreover, the professor synthesized another novel recombinant bat coronavirus that can be fatal to the human body in 2008.³²¹

Furthermore, the results of studies in Italy show that the SARS-CoV-2 already exists in blood samples collected by volunteers or patients from October to November 2019.³²²⁻³²⁴ It may be quite shocking that, until now, more than 1,000 Americans

Fig 2. Research results and timetable of the origin-tracing of novel coronavirus

reported on Twitter that they had been infected with the novel coronavirus from October to December 2019. Their symptoms are very similar to those of COVID-19, including more than 100 real-name certified Americans, and some of their blood samples show positive anti-SARS-CoV-2 antibodies.³²⁵ For more research results and timetable of the origin-tracing of the novel coronavirus, see the report in Fig 2 from public literature.³²⁶

Politicization, not scientization.³⁰⁴⁻³¹³ From the logical level, many scholars, media practitioners and statesmen around the world subconsciously regard the above political behavior of American politicians in the face of public judgment of scientific problems as a behavior with strong randomness or full of lies, which is obviously different or far lower than scientific behavior, normal behavior or rational behavior. From the perspective of advantages and disadvantages, politics will undoubtedly be pulled into a low level. The feeling to the public is that there is a non scientific or moral lack of political leadership lower than the scientific class in today's society.

However, many people in the country's political class are in the leadership class. If these people suddenly become one level lower than those engaged in scientific work or normal behavior, is this a great irony and disrespect to the American political class and many famous universities that train political talents or political elites for the

United States? The country and people also look forward to prosperity, peace and development under their leadership. Arbitrary politicization of a problem that should have been dealt with according to the laws of natural science is either a disease caused by political myopia, or a morbid state caused by the dual defects of culture and morality in this society.

From the perspective of health behavioral management or medical behavioral management, first, the time when COVID-19 broke out on a large scale is that after the complete control of the epidemic situation in China, the American people, the medical community and governments at all levels have more adequate response time. Second, families in the United States are far more dispersed than those in China or Wuhan. From the perspective of preventive medicine or infectious disease control, the epidemic situation in the United States should be much better controlled than that in public literature China. Third, the most famous hospitals in the world are in the United States, among the top ten hospitals and medical colleges in the world in 2020.^{327,328} The United States has the largest number. From the perspective of the medical level in the United States, the epidemic situation in the United States should be better controlled. Fourth, the most famous management, health management and preventive medicine majors in the world are all in American universities or institutions. From the perspective of management, the crucial ability "the ability to transfer experience" should be very rich. The population of the United States is less than a quarter of that of China. Although the United States has the world's best high-quality medical resources, information technology resources, land resources, political resources and democratic resources, by August 5, 2021, the cumulative cases confirmed in the United States will exceed 3,617,000, and the cumulative deaths will exceed 631,290, far higher than 121,950 and 5,639 in China;⁸⁴ From August 1, 2021 to August 20th, the average number of confirmed cases per day in the United States

has now exceeded 100,000 again, while the data on the Chinese mainland was less than 100.⁸⁴ This shows that when the market mechanism fails, the American government mechanism, the moral mechanism, the cultural mechanism, the American political and democratic mechanism also fail at the same time.

This shows that there are serious problems in the management of health behavior or medical behavior by governments at all levels in the United States. On the other hand, the American dream boasted by politicians or statesmen in the past seems to have become an increasing number of infections or deaths that frighten Americans and rank first on the planet. It can be seen that the American dream, as the foundation of the country, is fairly superficial and very pale. It lacks depth in philosophy. On the contrary, it cultivates a large number of Americans who are difficult to self-discipline and self-righteousness. As a result, smart American politicians or statesmen used to have to make an amazing event to knead or consolidate or unite most Americans, especially at a crisis or important moment.

Many Chinese subconsciously believe that political figures should have good morality, cultivation and leadership, but not self-interested, which was attached to great importance in ancient China. In 684 B.C., according to the records of Guoyu Qiyu, Qi Huanggong would appoint Bao Shuya as prime minister after inheriting the throne.³²⁹ However, Bao Shuya refused and said, "I'm just a mediocre courtier of yours. You take care of me so that I don't suffer from cold and hunger, I'm already very lucky. If you want to govern the country, it's not what I'm good at. Only Guan Zhong can manage the country." He sincerely said to Qi Huanggong, "I am inferior to Guan Zhong in five aspects: I am inferior to him in pacifying the people with lenience and kindness; I'm not as good as him at governing the country without forgetting the root; I am not as good as him for being faithful and honest and gaining the trust of the people; Making etiquette is enough to make the world follow suit, and I'm not as good as him." Although Guan Zhong almost killed Qi Huanggong with an arrow not long ago, he was his enemy. After Bao Shuya persuaded him, Qi Huanggong happily worshipped Guan Zhong as prime minister. This makes Guan Zhong one of the famous prime ministers in Chinese history. Guan Zhong was firmly convinced that propriety, righteousness, honesty and shame are the foundation of governing the country.³²⁹ Today's Chinese people are deeply influenced by ancient Chinese historical figures and believe that political leaders or political groups should have a sense of justice, kindness or responsibility. It may be difficult for most people to imagine that a democratic country's political leaders or political groups or their main figures like to spread lies, launch unjust wars, or invade the territory of other countries. It is also hard to imagine that such a culture and civilization is at a high level and can lead the world to a healthy, peaceful and prosperous future. On the contrary, in the noise, they will naturally make historical comparisons, and may think that they are not even as good as a feudal dynasty in China 2000 years ago.

Although a large number of talents from all over the world have poured into the United States due to good treatment and loose scientific research environment, which has laid the foundation for the glory of the U.S. economy for more than 100 years, looking back at the American political arena from the perspective of comparative

politics or econometric comparative politics, we find that the number of assassinations and attempted assassinations of the president of the United States since its founding in 1829, it is fairly rare in the world. The assassins are basically American nationals, and their actions are not irresistible and just acts understood by Chinese culture. Moreover, some assassins died unnaturally subsequently, which is unimaginable in China. Since 1829, China has experienced several dynasties and great wars; although the people hated the emperor or the president at that time because the governments of individual dynasties signed some treaties of humiliation, there was no phenomenon that an emperor or president or chairman was assassinated to death, let alone assassinated to death by people of their own nationality. The head of state not only represents the leadership and cohesion of the country, but also shows the moral and cultural standards of this country. Despite the fact that China is not reunified, Chinese have not assassinated the leaders of the Taiwan region, let alone the Dalai Lama, who continues to cause trouble for China. It can be seen that the moral level of the two countries immediately reflects who is higher and who is lower.

Looking through history, you may find that the first diplomatic envoy in modern Chinese history was actually the American Anson Burlingame.³³⁰ On November 27, 1867, Prince Gong- Yiyi of the Qing Dynasty of China, appointed the outgoing American ambassador Anson Burlingame as Chinese envoy to various countries. When the news came out, all foreign ministers in Beijing were shocked. He signed the Burlingame mission with the United States on behalf of China in the following year.³³⁰ The author also marvels at Prince Gong Yi's employment vision, which should be recognized by Burlingame's excellent morality, professional ability, professionalism and the level of fully mobilizing social relationships.

After World War II, the United States liked to attract talents from other countries and used a large number of talents trained by other countries free of charge, which created today's leading technology in the United States. First of all, the author hopes that the United States can have many Anson Burlingames with excellent morality and appear in American leadership positions. Second, promote some political talents with excellent character buried in the American folks, not on seniority. Third, it is hoped that the American political arena will transform the thoughts of politicians who used to like to lie in the past in the spirit of making the best possible use of men, and return them to the right track through the method of curing the sickness to save the patient,³³¹ so that they can continue to contribute to the development of the United States. Fourth, if the United States is generous enough and lacks political talents, it may as well recruit and select some people with good political morality and management ability from China to enrich government institutions at all levels in the United States.

People engaged in natural science and applied sciences usually don't like to be extreme. However, the author often thinks of two opposite things. First, American scientist will Durant, the winner of the Pulitzer Prize and Medal of Freedom, said very extreme words. "Perhaps we will burn all books except Taoist *Tao Te Ching* and find the outline of wisdom in it."¹⁴ In the past, the author was difficult to understand why he said so absolutely and raised the cultural level of the *Tao Te Ching* to the highest

level." Second, the author did not fully comprehend why the former Chancellor of Germany Schroeder called on every German family to buy a Chinese *Tao-Te-Ching* to help solve people's ideological confusion.¹⁴ Isn't there a Bible in the West? Now, witnessing the politicization of the COVID-19 epidemic and calumniating China by some politicians or media in the US and the Western countries, the total numbers of death cases in their nations are far more than that of China, although politicians in these countries should usually have religious beliefs, and read the Bible or pray a lot, or go to church every week or every year. Therefore, the author deeply felt that the Pulitzer Prize and American scientist will Durant, winner of the medal of freedom, had fairly correct opinions, and the German chancellor was fully farsighted. The moral standards constructed by Chinese culture should be at least one level higher than the Western standards. The author boldly predicts that if Germany can voluntarily merge with one or two countries with a common language and cultural customs, and integrate the foundation of Chinese culture, just as Guan Zhong, the famous prime minister in Chinese history, said that etiquette, righteousness and integrity are the foundation of building a country and will become the most dazzling country in Europe.

Recently, when the author talked about "statesman" with American friends, they mentioned that the American people often use "politician" instead of "statesman" in daily life and think that politicians are liars. Many Chinese have long been conditioned to think of "statesman" as a purely commendatory term and the word "politician" as derogatory meaning from former English learning. A statesman is a man with a certain political vision and political ability, with altruistic thoughts, who can develop the country, seek welfare for the people, uphold world peace, and selflessly devote his youth and even his life to the country or humanity. This is the complete opposite of the Oxford English Dictionary(OED)'s self-serving pejorative interpretation in Article 2 about "politician".³³² The OED defines a politician as "a. A schemer or plotter; a shrewd, sagacious, or crafty person. In later use also (esp. U.S. derogatory, influenced by sense A. 2b): a self-interested manipulator, whose behavior is likened to that of a professional politician." However, a selfish politician can never be a virtuous person. Hillary Clinton's famous quote illustrates the difference between a politician and a statesman: "The difference between a politician and a statesman is that a politician thinks about the next election while the statesman thinks about the next generation."³³³

If according to such statement of Americans or the OED, politics, as a widely opened subject in many American universities, has turned into a subject to widely cultivate liars or self-interested manipulators, we still feel a little shocked and uncomfortable and then fall into deep thinking. The leadership of a region, nation or international organization in the world is nearly controlled by statesmen or politicians. The prevention and control of the current severe COVID-19 epidemic is being directed by them. Almost all of the world's situations, processes or economies are dominated or influenced by them. Judicial appointments or the administration of justice may also be dominated by them. More importantly, politics, statesmen or politicians generally dominate the military or military actions of a country or region.

Almost all of them are leaders. Military actions ultimately determine the life and death of innocent people and whether the world is peaceful or not. Political justice and conscience can contribute to military justice and maintain world order and peace, and prevent the out-of-control army from plundering wealth and killing civilians like bandit groups. Paying attention to administrative ethics or political ethics in daily work will help to further guide judicial behavior to conform to ethics, and to guide military behavior to conform to ethics, or to evaluate the legitimacy of politics or statesmen or politicians' behavior with the help of comparative ethics or comparative prisoners of war ethics or metrological judicial ethics or quantitative legal ethics or metrological military ethics or metrological war ethics or prisoners of war ethics or quantitative prisoners of war ethics (quantitative judicial ethics, metrological legal ethics, metrological military ethics) evaluates the legitimacy of politics or statesmen or politicians' behavior.^{37A-40A}

In addition, the politicization on the source-tracing of the novel coronavirus, rather than scientificization, is not pursuing scientific facts in nature, but trying to lie. If the public generally think that politicians are liars, aren't many American universities home to liars? Isn't that demeaning and unfair to those universities or to the discipline? Isn't the discipline of political science progressing slowly from this kind of view? Isn't it more necessary to change people's views on politics or politicians? Isn't it more necessary for this industry or field to be sorted out or replanned and distinguished from the past? Or is it necessary to change a common word and make the great statesmen, noble statesmen or their group stand out and enable real statesmen to be less constrained by capital to achieve their great or lofty ambitions or ideals and run the organs of power of government in order to make the world a more peaceful place with stable economies, orderly societies and people living in peace and contentment?

Human society needs a down-to-earth and universal evaluation standard for leaders based on justice, kindness and conscience, etc. We believe that these disciplines are helpful to evaluating the degree of justice, conscience, fairness, morality, integrity, rationality, efficiency, honesty, self-discipline, diligence, openness and transparency displayed by the government or political figures in the process of ruling, propagating their ideas or disseminating information. In recent years, it is a common phenomenon that some politicians, for their own self-interest or personal gain, like to make trouble of nothing, lie, create chaos, violate historical facts or distort the truth or deliberately conceal the truth. In addition, the unscrupulous media spread some information unscrupulously in violation of morality to confuse voters or the public. It is one of the root causes of regional economic decline or recession, regional instability, violence, conflict, military expansion or war outbreak. It will be conducive to maintain brotherhood among more countries. The goal of political swindlers is usually to be the leader of a team or region, and they are more accustomed to making lies, and frequently use economic interests to disrupt friendly relations between other countries, create contradictions and conflicts, and even lead to military expansion (instead of reducing the military) and wars in countries that originally belong to brotherhood or fraternity. Before that, however, these countries

may often hold friendly economic cooperation or peaceful development meetings.

If a team or a region is basically composed of a group of upright, kind-hearted, honest or hardworking people, but if forced to be led by political swindlers, what will happen, especially during the outbreak of COVID-19?

The building-up of these disciplines are conducive to the establishment of objective, just, fair and reasonable evaluation system and hierarchical management system or new political ecological civilization system, so as to polish the eyes of the public, quickly distinguish the great statesman, noble statesman, excellent statesman, honest statesman, diligent statesman, statesman, political staff, politician, political liar and political swindler etc. (Table 2), and combine the evaluation of quantitative military ethics or quantitative prisoner of war ethics. It is helpful to greatly reduce the threat to regional and world peace posed by the lies of politicians or political hooligans, reduce the number of global peace saboteurs, rapidly cultivate and increase the number of global peace fighters, widely promote culture of peace, significantly reduce the number or intensity of conflicts or wars, and reduce the number of refugees. It is expected that this will contribute highly to world peace and stability, as well as economic prosperity and people's well-being. In addition, the rapid establishment of metrological political ethics or the grading evaluation of politicians and statesmen should not only be conducive to the selection of World Peace Prize or the Nobel Peace Prize, reduce the long-standing disputes, but also enhance the governance level of some countries or regions.

Table 2. Classification of Statesman or Political staffs or Politicians*

No.	Different levels of Political staffs	Notes
1	Great statesman	Its contents may be more suitable for people to write.
2	Outstanding statesman	Its contents may be more suitable for people to write.
3	Noble or magnificent statesman	Its contents may be more suitable for people to write.
4	Excellent statesman	
5	Honest or upstanding statesman	
6	Diligent or practical statesman	
7	Statesman	
8	Political staff	
9	Politician	
10	Mosquito-level Political liar	(1) When a politician lied or spread rumors to the public 2 times/week, 4 times /3 months, or 5-6 times/ half a year.
11	Bedbug -level Political swindler	Politicians who meet any of the following (1) or (2). (1) When a politician lied or spread rumors to the public

		<p>3 times/week, 5-6 times /3 months, or 7-8 times/ half a year.</p> <p>Or (2) Politicians personally participate in or organize personnel to maliciously destroy or set fire to burn public property, or unjustly and illegally destroy or burn other people's property, once in 12 months, or twice in 36 months, resulting in total losses of 0.7-1 million yuan RMB or 0.2-0.4 million US dollars or 0.2-0.3 million Euros, or 1 deaths or 4-5 people injured.</p>
12	Hornet -level Political swindler	<p>Politicians who meet any of the following (1) or (2).</p> <p>(1) When a politician lied or spread rumors to the public 4 times/week, 7-8 times /3 months, or 9-10 times/ half a year.</p> <p>Or (2) Politicians personally participate in or organize personnel to maliciously destroy or set fire to burn public property, or unjustly and illegally destroy or burn other people's property, more than once in 12 months, or more than twice in 36 months, resulting in total losses of 1-4 million yuan RMB or 0.4-0.8 million US dollars or 0.3-0.7 million Euros, or 2 deaths or 6-10 people injured.</p>
13	Rat-level Political swindler	<p>Politicians who meet any of the following (1) or (2).</p> <p>(1) When a politician lied or spread rumors to the public 5 times/week, 8-9 times /3 months, or 11-12 times/ half a year.</p> <p>Or (2) Politicians personally participate in or organize personnel or incite others to maliciously destroy or set fire to burn public property, or unjustly and illegally destroy or burn other people's property, more than once in 12 months, or more than twice in 36 months, resulting in total losses of 4-7 million yuan RMB or 0.8-1.3 million US dollars or 0.7-1 million Euros, or 3 deaths or 10-15 people injured.</p>
14	Fox -level Political swindler	<p>Politicians who meet any of the following (1) or (2).</p> <p>(1) When a politician lied or spread rumors to the public 6 times/week, 10-11 times /3 months, or 13 -14times/ half a year.</p> <p>Or (2) Politicians personally participate in or organize personnel or incite others to maliciously destroy or set fire to burn public property, or unjustly and illegally destroy or burn other people's property for more than 2 times in 12 months, or more than 3 times in 36 months, resulting in total losses of 7-10 million yuan RMB or 1.3-1.9 million US dollars or 1-1.6 million Euros, or 4 deaths or 15-20 people injured.</p>

15	Crocodile -level Political swindler	Politicians who meet any of the following (1) or (2). (1) When a politician lied or spread rumors to the public 7 times/week, 12 times /3 consecutive months, or 15 times/ half a year, or more. Or (2) Politicians personally participate in or organize personnel or incite others to maliciously destroy or set fire to burn public property, or unjustly and illegally destroy or burn other people's property for more than 2 times in 12 months, or more than 3 times in 36 months, resulting in a total loss of more than 10 million yuan RMB or 1.9 million US dollars or 1.6 million Euros, or 5 or more deaths, or more than 20 people were injured.
16	Devil –level political swindler who is handsome or beautiful or articulate	Politicians who ignore the provisions of the Charter of the United Nations and engage in the organization or manufacture or order the use of biological or and chemical weapons, including bacteria or viruses. The manufactured biological and chemical weapons have killed or tried to kill humans at low cost or cause disasters in other countries.

★ Statesmen may be able to discuss the grading of statesmen and politicians. In order to better govern their respective countries, benefit the people, cultivate peace fighters, reduce conflicts and wars and maintain world peace, statesmen of various countries may be able to negotiate on the certification standards of level 13, 14 and 15 politicians that are easy to reach a consensus. If they can reach an agreement, they may gather together in the hometown of Laozi or Confucius, the ancient sage, jointly issue the Kuxian Declaration or Qufu Declaration on several standards of statesmen and politicians' classification to the world; or the Stockholm Declaration in the capital of peace.

★ If statesmen of various countries can reach consensus and issue relevant statesmen' declarations or consensus, it is possible to open a new era in global politics and a new era for world peace. If there is no consensus on what ordinary people think is very bad behavior, it indicates that there may be serious problems in the values of some statesmen or politicians, which is also an opportunity for the global public to improve their understanding of politics or statesmen and politicians.

It is suggested that the Swedish institutions consider setting up a Nobel Prize in Ethics, which specifically rewards the moral and ethical models of the planet except those outside the Chinese mainland. (Chinese population is very large and is influenced by Taoism, Confucianism, Mohist, Legalists and Buddhist culture. It is easy for moral models to spring up like mushrooms. These people will inevitably hope to win the prize, which may affect the enthusiasm of people in other countries or regions), even if the award ceremony is held once every two years or three or four years. It is believed that this will considerably enhance the global public's awareness of moral culture and moral level, cultivate more peace fighters, eliminate the research

of biological weapons such as deadly viruses, reduce the number of conflicts and wars, reduce the number of nuclear weapons and promote world peace. This prize may achieve more valuable practical results than the Nobel Peace Prize. It is believed that this will be very constructive to cultivate values and ethics with “propriety, righteousness, honesty and shame” and “Neither riches nor honours can corrupt him; neither poverty nor humbleness can make him swerve from principle; and neither threats nor forces can subdue him”,^{329,334} minimize the chance that chemistry, biotechnology and management talents etc. trained by universities will become tools for inferior politicians and army-ruffians to manufacture killing biological weapons, and let them take the initiative to unmask these politicians' heinous crimes against humanity.

11.5 Big waste in the current vaccination and medical behavioral economy in COVID-19's control, economic recovery

Vaccination with COVID-19 vaccine is a very important means to combat the novel coronavirus epidemic. However, some people in risk areas are afraid to be vaccinated because of rare severe coagulation reaction or deaths after receiving Covid-19 vaccine.³³⁵ In addition, part of the public refused vaccination, and many children in risk areas cannot be vaccinated for different reasons. Moreover, due to the morphological and structural characteristics of SARS-CoV-2, the virus is prone to mutation and strong disease-causing mutants may occur from time to time. Generally, the new vaccine re-modified with the variant strain can be marketed at least 3 months later than the emergence of the variant strain, while the variant strain may infect a larger range of people and have a more serious impact. At the WHO press conference on June 14, 2021, Director-General Dr. Tedros said that the mutant SARS-CoV-2 has accelerated the spread of the epidemic across the globe.³³⁶ The current spread of the novel coronavirus has exceeded the speed of vaccine distribution. All these determine that even though the majority of people in the world have gotten COVID-19 vaccination, there may still be continuous SARS-CoV-2 infection. Without the emergence of unexpectedly effective drugs in most countries around the world, if the COVID-19 prevention and control strategy of most countries in the world is not able to progress rapidly, the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games may not be held normally as in the past until next year, even if postponed again (The Games will have to be held this year because of concerns about the sports industry, sportsmanship, economy and politics, etc., but there may be few live audiences), and the road to global economic recovery this year will not be smoothly.

Nowadays, many countries around the world are implementing a national vaccination plan for the public, hoping to quickly obtain herd immunity. However, some countries, regions or the international community may neglect the issue of vaccinating the public within the region at a proper time and at a lower cost. At present, in areas of some countries where there have been practically no new cases of COVID-19 for seven or eight months or more than a year, volunteers or organizers have repeatedly urged the public to get vaccinated. Due to the limited production capacity of the vaccine, the increasing number of mutant strains, the limited period of protection after vaccination, and the need to continue to vaccinate after expiration, at

the same cost, the timing of vaccination becomes more important. How to make the public obtain the longest protection period and the best protection after vaccination in a safe situation should be considered in the implementation of vaccination. Otherwise, it may lead to the waste of vaccine resources and the excessive medical burden of the government. If a large number of people are still infected with the mutated virus after their vaccination, the public's confidence and desire for vaccination may be affected. Therefore, we suggest that vaccination strategies should be implemented in different regions, grades, groups and time periods according to the control mode, new confirmed cases, existing risk level, flow situation of people, and input status of high and low risk areas in the country or region. In this way, the epidemic prevention funds can be disbursed in stages and managed reasonably, so as to reduce the pressure on the epidemic prevention funds in the short term, prevent more people from being infected with less cost and achieve better social benefits, which should be more in line with the principles of health behavioral economics.

At present, China divides the risk level of regions and personnel into three categories: high, medium and low.^{337,338} It is suggested to further refine the classification according to the surrounding epidemic situation, the possibility of risk input, and the situation of people flow and logistics. The risk level of regions and personnel can be divided into at least five categories: very high, high, medium, low and very low. The county, township, village, community, building or floor can be the smallest unit. In order to reduce the burden of families, enterprises or the country, reduce costs, reasonable expenditure, so that the relevant regulations or measures as far as possible in line with the principles of health behavioral economics, and strive to achieve the best prevention and control effect at the lowest cost. The same may be done in other countries. At present, nucleic acid testing in China is very excessive. The author was forced to test nucleic acid three times in nine days in August this year, although nucleic acid detections were free and the author had been to different low-risk areas.

Due to the morphological characteristics of the novel coronavirus, mutant strains with stronger pathogenic capacity are prone to appear. The author predicts that depending on the current widely implemented defense measures, even 90% of the population in many countries or regions have completed the vaccination, which has achieved the initial idea of herd immunity. However, in the risk area, once the active physical isolation and social distance control are abandoned, approximately 10-70% or more infections are likely to occur in this area after exposure to the more pathogenic mutant strains, or the immunity may be entirely broken. This means that the prevention and control policies and measures for imported cases in a country or region may not be relaxed in a certain period of time. In China, the speed of vaccinating the COVID-19 vaccines is too rapid, there are too many populations of vaccination in a short time, and there is no plan to delay vaccination by division or group. It is likely that it will fall into a passive situation for some time in the future.

The author believes that the control of the current global COVID-19 epidemic is not effective and politicization is a major reason. Secondly, senior officials in some countries lack the ability to transfer experience. Third, a large number of funds are

invested in the vaccination, which is wrong direction or selectivity, which will increase the burden of medical insurance in most countries. The variability of novel coronavirus has led to the fact that the COVID-19 vaccines have become vaccines of reduction of severe patients, rather than traditional vaccines, which will increase a lot of control costs. This is inconsistent with the principles of health behavioral economics or health behavioral management. The author believes that relying on the existing discovery and medical technology is enough to control the global epidemic. The key is to promote capable people to an appropriate core position, so that all harmless and effective means can be implemented quickly in an emergency. In the absence of effective measures, it is wrong to cancel physical defense and coexist with the virus for a long time, which will inevitably lead to more infections and deaths, and at the same time disturb people's hearts or minds. The vast majority of the public have no medical background or effective measures, but the public is easily influenced by the speeches of people of status. In the absence of effective measures, it is proposed to cancel physical defense and coexist with the virus for a long time. In fact, this shows that the proposers themselves do not see the prospect that the intractable problem can be solved quickly and effectively, and breakthroughs can't be found. They don't see the serious consequences of this strategy, although they only need a simple calculation. If only 10 percent of Wuhan's 11 million people were infected with the SARS-CoV-2 as a result of a co-existing strategy, wouldn't the medical system of the city be more collapsed than when the first epidemic broke out in late 2019? If China implements the co-existence strategy with the novel coronavirus under the current model, which province or city can draw a large number of medical personnel to support Wuhan again? What's more, because of the variability and susceptibility to infection of the novel coronavirus, how can a population of 10% be infected once the city coexists with the virus? If there are more than 40% infected people in Wuhan, won't Wuhan become a hell on earth? To be fair, someone, his family and supporters should try first and let the public observe their infection rates and mortality, not the entire public.

The establishment of a new discipline usually brings a leap in the development of the field. Putting forward the establishment of these disciplines is not to find people's faults. We believe that everyone will make mistakes, so there is no perfect person or creature in the world. On the contrary, the author is in favour of tolerating small mistakes and self-correcting small mistakes at the same time. Human beings or creatures are constantly making progress and growth from small mistakes. There are two famous ancient poems in China, a thousand sails pass by the shipwreck, ten thousand saplings shoot up beyond the withered tree--new things come to the fore while old things die.^{339,340} If it is not for correcting the big mistake that brings problems to many patients and creates great economic burden to the society, and some patients who take drug according to the results of CAPRIE trial may be in trouble or danger of life, if it is not for the consideration of justice and conscience advocated by Taoism, the universal benefit of Buddhism, and the Oath of Hippocrates, and if it is not for the pain caused by the long-term rejection of this article, we would not have such an idea and article. All these are due to our past hardships and helplessness. The author declares that his opinions are merely to throw out a brick to attract a jade and

hopes more people will participate in the research or discussion. Many issues have not been studied or discussed systematically and deeply. However, there are some things in history that require someone to do the work. Furthermore, restricted by the theme of this paper, it is not convenient to expand and discuss too much. We will study and discuss the issues of different economic or ethical disciplines etc. from different angles, levels and views in the future.

6-1A Virtual currency ethics: an emerging interdisciplinary subject that takes the moral phenomenon in virtual currency as the research object, and covers all moral-related issues in virtual currency issuance, system, virtual currency organization and virtual currency relationship.

6-2A Token economic ethics: An emerging interdisciplinary subject that takes the moral phenomena in token economy as the research object, and covers all moral-related issues in token economic system, token economic organization and token economic relationship.

6-3A Token ethics or Token financial ethics: An emerging interdisciplinary subject that takes the moral phenomenon in token or token finance as the research object, and covers all the moral related issues in token or token financial system, token or token financial organization and token or token financial relationship.

6-4A Digital financial ethics: An emerging interdisciplinary subject that takes the moral phenomenon in digital finance as the research object, and covers all the moral related issues in digital financial system, digital financial organization and digital financial relationship.

6-5A Virtual currency behavioral finance: an interdisciplinary subject of finance, psychology, behavior, sociology and other disciplines, trying to reveal the irrational behavior and decision-making law of the virtual currency financial market.

6-6A Virtual currency behavioral economics: The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting or evaluating the economic issues, behaviors, economic planning, phenomena or economic laws related to virtual currency economic activities on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or supervise or promote the effective and reasonable allocation of virtual currency economic resources and the formulation of relevant policies in economic activities.

6-7A Token behavioral finance: an interdisciplinary subject of finance, psychology, behavior, sociology and other disciplines, trying to reveal the irrational behavior and decision-making law of the token financial market.

6-8A Token behavioral economics: The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting or evaluating the economic issues, behaviors, economic planning, phenomena or economic laws related to token economic activities on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or supervise or promote the effective and reasonable allocation of token economic resources and the formulation of relevant policies in economic activities.

^{7-1A} Chinese Medicine Behavioral Economics: The science of studying, analyzing, clarifying, predicting, evaluating or solving economic issues or economic behaviors or economic phenomena or economic planning or economic laws in Chinese Medicine R & D, Chinese Medicine production, quality control, application, marketing, sales, supervision, management, vigilance, delisting and its whole life cycle, Chinese medical treatment, Chinese medical prevention, Chinese medical nursing, Chinese medical insurance, Chinese medical management, Chinese medical decision-making, Chinese medical policy, or Chinese medical investment, etc. on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so that it can guide or coordinate or promote R&D, investment, production, clinical medication, supervision, marketing, prevention, treatment, medical insurance, and the formulation of public policies, etc.

^{7A} Metrological Administrative (Government) Ethics (quantitative Administrative Ethics): An applied discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to study ethical issues and moral phenomena in administrative activities, and to conduct quantitative research on administrative behaviors or moral levels such as loyalty, selecting and appointing the virtuous and capable, fairness, justice, conscience, honesty, diligence, integrity, work initiative, governance ability, governance efficiency, transparency, legitimacy, truth-seeking and pragmatic, innovation, promotion of social development, responsibility and inaction, foresight, timeliness and rationality of policies or institutions introduction, loving the people, maintaining social order, protecting the people, protecting the legitimate rights and interests of individuals, eliminating evil, unity and cooperation, coordination, accountability, self-cultivation, self-discipline, self-examination, correction of errors, negative feedback level in administrative activities.

^{8A} Metrological Public Management Ethics (quantitative public management Ethics): An applied discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to study ethical issues and moral phenomena in public management activities, and to conduct quantitative research on public management behaviors or moral levels such as loyalty, selecting and appointing the virtuous and capable, fairness, justice, conscience, honesty, diligence, integrity, work initiative, governance ability, governance efficiency, transparency, legitimacy, truth-seeking and pragmatic, innovation, promotion of social development, responsibility and inaction, foresight, timeliness and rationality of policies or institutions introduction, loving the people, maintaining social order, protecting the people, protecting the legitimate rights and interests of individuals, eliminating evil, unity and cooperation, coordination, accountability, self-cultivation, self-discipline, self-examination, correction of errors and negative feedback level in the process of public management.

^{9A} Quantitative political ethics(metrological political ethics): An applied discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to study political ethics issues or phenomena in social and political life, and to conduct quantitative research on political behaviors or moral levels such as justice, conscience, moral character, fairness, honesty, responsibility, legitimacy, efficiency, loving the people, maintaining social order, protecting the people, eliminating evils, correcting mistakes, negative

feedback level, rumor making, lying, dissemination of false information, deliberately creating disputes or conflicts and so on in the process of spreading or implementing political propositions.

^{10A} Metrological party ethics (quantitative party ethics): An applied discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to study ethical issues or phenomena of the party in modern social and political life, and to conduct quantitative research on its political behavior or moral level in the process of spreading or implementing political ideas.

^{11A} Political behavioral economics: The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting, evaluating or solving economic issues or economic behaviors or economic phenomena or economic laws in political or national governance activities on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or promote the adjustment of related political behavior, the formulation of relevant economic policies or public policies.

^{12A} Party behavioral economics: The science of studying, analyzing, clarifying, predicting, evaluating or solving economic issues or economic behaviors or economic phenomena or economic laws in political party or political activities on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or promote the adjustment of related party behaviors, the formulation of relevant economic policies or public policies.

^{13A} Government (public or state) behavioral economics: The science of studying, analyzing, clarifying, predicting, evaluating or solving economic issues or economic behaviors or economic phenomena or economic laws in public or government or state governance activities on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so that it can guide or coordinate or promote the adjustment of government behavior, the formulation of relevant economic policies or public policies.

^{14A} National behavioral economics: The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting, evaluating or solving the economic problems, economic operation, economic phenomena, economic planning, economic policies, economic growth, economic achievements or economic laws of national social activities on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or promote the adjustment of relevant economic operation behaviors, the formulation of relevant economic policies or public policies, the implementation of relevant management work, etc.

^{15A} Enterprise behavioral economics: The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting, evaluating the objectives, scale, planning, production, operation, management, investment and development strategies in enterprise development, as well as the problems, phenomena or laws therein on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or promote the economic development of enterprises.

^{16A} Regional behavioral economics: The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting, evaluating or solving regional economic problems, economic behaviors,

economic phenomena, economic planning or economic laws on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or promote regional economic development, the rationality of regional productivity distribution, geographical distribution and spatial structure of regional economic activities, the optimization of regional resource allocation, the adjustment of relevant behaviors in the region, and formulation of relevant economic policies or public policies, etc.

^{17A} Trade behavioral economics: The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting, evaluating or solving the problems, behaviors, phenomena, economic planning or economic laws in trade on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or promote the formulation of relevant economic policies or public policies and the development of trade economy, etc.

^{18A} Real estate behavioral economics: The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting, evaluating or solving the economic problems, behaviors, phenomena, planning or laws in real estate on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or promote formulation of relevant economic policies or public policies, etc., and development of real estate economy, etc.

^{18A1} Short video Economics: it mainly studies short video production, publicity and promotion, marketing and sales, consumption and demand, and the drainage of short video to enterprises or industries, and other links related to the economic operation of short video, so as to provide a theoretical basis for promoting the economic development and growth of short video industry and related enterprises or industries.

^{18A2} Short video behavioral economics: the discipline of studying, clarifying, predicting, evaluating or solving the economic behavior and economic phenomena in short video production, application, promotion, marketing, consumption, supervision and short video drainage by using its basic principles and methods on the basis of psychology, behavior or behavioral economics.

^{18A3} Live-streaming Economics: it mainly studies various links of economic operation such as the production, publicity & promotion, marketing & marketing, consumption & demand of livestreaming, and the drainage of live-streaming to enterprises or industries, so as to provide a theoretical basis for promoting the economic development and growth of live streams industry and related industries.

^{18A4} Traffic behavioral economics: the science of using its basic principles and methods to study, predict, clarify, evaluate or solve the economic behavior and economic phenomena in creating traffic or drainage in commercial activities on the basis of psychology, behavior or behavioral economics.

^{18A5} Tourism behavioral economics: The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting, evaluating or solving the problems, behaviors, phenomena, economic planning or economic laws in tourism on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or promote the formulation of relevant economic policies or public policies and the development of tourism economy, etc.

^{19A} Rural behavioral economics: The science of studying, analyzing, clarifying, predicting, evaluating or solving economic issues or economic behaviors or economic phenomena or economic laws in rural productivity, rural population and employment, rural construction, economic structure of rural society, rational utilization of rural resources, rural production departments, organization and management of rural production, rural economic management, rural residents' life, rural infrastructure construction and maintenance, rural ecological economy, rural policy, rural financial policy, rural investment, rural education, rural transportation economy, rural land economy, cultivated land vigilance, village tyrant economy vigilance, farmers' decision-making rights, rural insurance, rural medical insurance and medical care, rural pension, leisure rural, rural tourism economy, urban transfer rural settlement economy, rural cultural economy, rural traditional custom economy, geographical agricultural and sideline product economy, etc. on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so that it can guide or coordinate or promote the adjustment and formulation of relevant rural policies, or the continuation, improvement or adjustment of relevant rural work behaviors.

^{20A} Agricultural behavioral economics: The science of studying, analyzing, clarifying, predicting, evaluating or solving economic issues or economic behaviors or economic phenomena or economic laws in agricultural production, rational breeding and planting of agricultural products, agricultural planning, agricultural technology, genetically modified agricultural products, health food, 'processing, marketing, selling and quality supervision of agricultural products and agricultural by-products', agricultural financial policy, agricultural insurance, construction and maintenance of agricultural water conservancy facilities, agricultural policy, agricultural machinery, agricultural informatization, agricultural intelligence, agricultural manual tradition, food security and vigilance, seed cultivation, seed security, seed economy, rural land economy, cultivated land vigilance, agricultural eco-tourism, meteorological services, leisure agriculture, geographical agricultural by-product economy, etc. on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so that it can guide or coordinate or promote the adjustment and formulation of relevant agricultural policies, or the continuation, improvement or adjustment of relevant agricultural work behaviors.

^{21A} Food behavioral economics: The science of studying, analyzing, clarifying, predicting, evaluating or solving economic issues or economic behaviors or economic phenomena or economic laws in food production and processing, development and technology, demand and consumption, transportation, circulation and trade, market and sales, price and policy, management and supervision, safety and vigilance, genetically modified food, food types and choices, food distribution and supply, food structure, food and health, investment and finance, etc. on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so that it can guide or coordinate or promote R&D, production, processing, consumption, circulation, supply, supervision, safety, marketing, distribution, supply, investment, or policy formulation, etc.

^{22A} Nutrition behavioral economics: The science of studying, analyzing, clarifying, predicting, evaluating or solving economic issues or economic behaviors or economic phenomena or economic laws in nutritional structure, nutritional level, nutritional behavior, production, processing, marketing, quality, supervision, technology, policy, types and selection of nutrition, distribution and supply of nutrition, consumption, nutrition structure, improper nutrition, over nutrition, undernutrition, nutrition and health, nutrition safety and vigilance, nutrition investment and finance, etc. on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so that it can guide or coordinate or promote R&D, investment, production, processing, quality, supply, consumption, supervision, safety, marketing, or public policy formulation, etc.

^{23A-24A} Metrological accounting ethics(metrological auditing ethics): A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on the moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the field of accounting(auditing).

^{25A} Comparative political parties(comparative parties): A discipline that uses comparative methods to conduct comparative research on the theories, norms, problems, behaviors, phenomena, results or laws in different political parties or different aspects of the same political party.

^{26A} Metrological comparative politics(quantitative comparative politics): A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on the theories, norms, problems, behaviors, phenomena, results or laws in different political fields or different aspects of the same political field.

^{27A} Quantitative comparative political parties (metrological comparative political parties, or metrological comparative parties): A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on the theories, norms, problems, behaviors, phenomena, results or laws in different political parties or different aspects of the same political party.

^{28A} Metrological comparative economics (quantitative comparative economics, comparative econometrics): A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on the economic theories, economic policies, economic problems, economic behaviors, economic phenomena, economic growth, economic achievements or economic laws of different countries, or different regions or aspects of the same country.

^{29A} Metrological comparative political economics(quantitative comparative political economics): A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on the problems, behaviors, phenomena, results or laws in different political and economic fields or different aspects of the same political and economic field.

^{30A} Military behavioral economics: The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting or evaluating the economic problems, behaviors, economic planning, phenomena or economic laws related to military activities on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or promote the effective and reasonable allocation of military economic resources and the formulation of relevant military

policies in military activities.

^{31A} Defense behavioral economics(National defense behavioral economics): The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting, evaluating or solving the economic problems, economic behaviors, economic planning, economic phenomena or economic laws related to national defense security activities on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so that it can guide or coordinate or promote the effective and rational allocation and use of scarce resources in national defense activities, the formulation of relevant national defense policies, etc. in order to minimize the investment on the premise of achieving the established national security objectives, or maximize the national security benefits under the fixed conditions of national security investment.

^{32A} War behavioral economics: The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting or evaluating the economic problems, behaviors, economic planning, phenomena or economic laws related to war on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or promote the effective and reasonable allocation of military economic resources in war and formulate wartime policies, or prevent wars from happening.

^{33A} Energy behavioral economics: The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting or evaluating the economic problems, behaviors, economic planning, phenomena or economic laws related to new energy, on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or promote energy development, energy resource allocation, processing, storage, utilization, consumption, energy conservation, price mechanism, energy use effect, energy security, energy vigilance, as well as the formulation of relevant economic policies or public policies, and the development of energy economy.

^{34A} Material behavioral economics: The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting or evaluating the economic problems, behaviors, economic planning, phenomena or economic laws related to new materials, on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or promote the development, processing, utilization, consumption, energy conservation and environmental protection of new materials, as well as the formulation of relevant economic policies or public policies, the development of material economy.

^{35A} Chemical behavioral economics: The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting or evaluating the economic problems, behaviors, economic planning, phenomena or economic laws related to chemistry or chemical industry, on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or promote the development, processing, utilization, consumption, trade, energy conservation, environmental protection and technological innovation of chemical products, as well as the formulation of relevant economic policies or public policies.

^{36A} Gene behavioral economics: The science of studying, clarifying, analyzing, predicting or evaluating the economic problems, behaviors, planning, phenomena or economic laws related to genes and gene technology, on the basis of psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics and applying its basic principles and methods, so as to guide or coordinate or promote the development, utilization and vigilance of gene regulation or modification technologies or products, as well as the formulation of relevant economic policies or public policies.

^{37A} Metrological judicial ethics (quantitative judicial ethics): A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the judicial field.

^{38A} Metrological legal ethics (quantitative legal ethics): A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the field of law.

^{39A} Metrological military ethics (quantitative military ethics): An applied discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the military field.

^{40A} Quantitative prisoner of war ethics (metrological prisoner of war ethics): An applied discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the prisoner of war field.

Chinese Keywords: 药物行为经济学, 医学行为经济学, 卫生行为经济学, 健康行为经济学, 临床行为经济学, 中医(药)行为经济学, 计量或定量医学伦理学, 计量或定量媒体或传媒伦理学, 计量或定量新闻伦理学, 计量或定量经济伦理学, 计量或定量商业伦理学, 计量或定量管理伦理学, 计量或定量公共管理伦理学, 计量或定量行政或政府伦理学, 数字金融伦理学, 虚拟货币伦理学, 通证伦理学, 通证经济伦理学, 通证金融伦理学, 虚拟货币金融学, 虚拟货币行为金融学, 虚拟货币行为经济学, 通证行为金融学, 通证行为经济学, 计量或定量政党伦理学, 政治行为经济学, 政党行为经济学, 政府行为经济学, 公共行为经济学, 国民行为经济学, 企业行为经济学, 区域行为经济学, 短视频经济学, 短视频行为经济学, 直播带货经济学, 直播带货行为经济学, 流量行为经济学, 旅游行为经济学, 能源行为经济学, 材料行为经济学, 化学行为经济学, 先进制造业行为经济学, 信息行为经济学, (转)基因行为经济学, 受体或靶点或通道(行为)经济学, 房地产行为经济学, 军事行为经济学, 国防行为经济学, 战争行为经济学, 医学行为管理学, 健康行为管理学, 计量会计或计量审计伦理学, 比较政党学, 计量比较政治学, 计量比较政党学, 计量比较经济学, 计量比较政治经济学, 计量或定量政治伦理学, 计量或定量司法伦理学, 计量或定量法律伦理学, 计量或定量军事伦理学, 计量或定量战争伦理学, 战俘伦理学, 计量或定量战俘伦理学, 农村行为经济学, 农业行为经济学, 食品(或食物)行为经济学, 营养行为经济学

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author claims that his opinions are just to throw a brick to attract jade, hoping that more people will participate in the research or discussion. The author belongs to the nonpartisan or independent.

References

- 1 Liu L., Zeng, F.D., & Yang, X.Y. Revaluation of Drug with Abnormal Behavior, and Medical statistical-ethics,etc. *Chinese Medical Association Medical Genetics Branch, Chinese Society of Genetics Human and Medical Genetics Committee. Twelfth National Medical Genetics Conference Papers Compilation*, 2013,4, 281-282.
- 2 Liu Li, Zeng Fandian, Yang Xiaoyan (2021): Prediction on Clopidogrel's Abnormal Behaviors and Pharmacobehavioral Economics. figshare. Preprint. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.14173727.v26>.
- 3 Liu L, Zeng, F.D, Zeng, X.H, et al. Revaluation of clopidogrel: let the data speak for themselves. *J Huazhong Univ Sci Technolog Med Sci*. 2010;30(3):299-306. [doi:10.1007/s11596-010-0346-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11596-010-0346-3).
- 4 CAPRIE Steering Committee. A randomised, blinded, trial of clopidogrel versus aspirin in patients at risk of ischaemic events (CAPRIE). CAPRIE Steering Committee. *Lancet*. 1996;348(9038):1329-1339. [doi:10.1016/s0140-6736\(96\)09457-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(96)09457-5)
- 5 Wiśniewski A, Filipka K. The Phenomenon of Clopidogrel High On-Treatment Platelet Reactivity in Ischemic Stroke Subjects: A Comprehensive Review. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2020;21(17):6408. Published 2020 Sep 3. [doi:10.3390/ijms21176408](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21176408).
- 6 Guidelines for prevention and treatment of thrombotic diseases in China. *Chinese Medical Journal*. 2018,98(36):2861-2888. [DOI: 10.3760/cma.j.issn.0376-2491.2018.36.002](https://doi.org/10.3760/cma.j.issn.0376-2491.2018.36.002).
- 7 Forsyth MG. Post-truth era is destroying society and medicine. *BMJ*. 2019; 367: l6932. Published 2019 Dec 16. [doi:10.1136/bmj.l6932](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.l6932).
- 8 Heinrich S. Medical science faces the post-truth era: a plea for the grassroot values of science. *Curr Opin Anaesthesiol*. 2020;33(2):198-202. [doi:10.1097/ACO.0000000000000833](https://doi.org/10.1097/ACO.0000000000000833).
- 9 James L A. Antiscience and Vulnerability to False News in the United States: A Basis in the History of Geologic Theories. *The Professional Geographer*, 2019, 71(4): 595-603.
- 10 Brashier NM, Schacter DL. Aging in an Era of Fake News. *Curr Dir Psychol Sci*. 2020;29(3):316-323. [doi:10.1177/0963721420915872](https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721420915872).
- 11 Ozeke O, Cay S, Ozcan F, Topaloglu S, Aras D. Post-truth era and cardiology: After ORBITA, before CABANA. *Indian Heart J*. 2018;70(3):439-442. [doi:10.1016/j.ihj.2018.04.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ihj.2018.04.005).
- 12 Advocating morality and longevity -- an analysis of Taoism's thought of "keeping health with morality" Entries, Tencent Daoxue, Zhu Yalou. 2017-01-16 07:44. <https://foxue.qq.com/a/20170116/003991.htm>(in Chinese).
- 13 Why is the *Tao-Te-Ching* called the first of a hundred classics? Its influence is so profound that it has been translated into many languages. <https://new.qq.com/omn/20191121/20191121A0NF4A00.html>(in Chinese).
- 14 The comprehension and evaluation of Laozi s *Tao-Te-Ching* by foreign

- celebrities. <https://www.docin.com/p-2190773269.html>(in Chinese).
15. The Words and Wisdom of Will Durant, June 15, 2014Durant - Will,Wisdom. <https://reasonandmeaning.com/2014/06/15/an-encounter-with-will-durant/>.
 - 16 "Literature's "Images" from the Perspective of Modern and Contemporary Literature"- "The Tao Te Ching" in the eyes of foreigners. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1637389975577462722&wfr=spider&for=pc>(in Chinese).
 - 17 A chinese-english comparison of the Tao Te Ching by Lin Yutang2017-10-16. http://www.360doc.com/content/17/1016/09/235213_695322450.shtml.
 - 18 Benatar SR. Editorial ethics. *BMJ*. 1998;316(7125):155-156. [doi:10.1136/bmj.316.7125.155a](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.316.7125.155a).
 - 19 Vogel G. Editorial ethics questioned. *Science*. 1997; 275(5303):1055.
 - 20 DeBakey L. Editorial: Editorial ethics. *JAMA*. 1974; 228(6):693.
 - 21 Hoekelman RA. Editorial ethics. *Pediatr Ann*. 1992; 21(5):277-278. [doi:10.3928/0090-4481-19920501-05](https://doi.org/10.3928/0090-4481-19920501-05).
 - 22 Phillip Ebrall. Editorial Ethics. *Clinical Chiropractic*, 2004, 7(3):154.
 - 23 Lipschultz Jeremy Harris et al. Book Review: Media Ethics and Global Justice in the Digital Age, by Clifford G. Christians and Ethics for a Digital Age, by Deni Elliott and Edward H. Spence and Journalism's Ethical Progression: A Twentieth-Century Journey, by Gwyneth Mellinger and John B. Ferré eds.. *Journalism & Mass Communication Educator*, 2021, 76(1): 128-130.
 - 24 Robert Z. Cortes. A critical evaluation of Clifford Christians's media ethics theory: a précis. *Church, Communication and Culture*, 2020, 5(2):157-186. [doi: 10.1080/23753234.2020.1765694](https://doi.org/10.1080/23753234.2020.1765694).
 - 25 White C L, Boatwright B. Social media ethics in the data economy: Issues of social responsibility for using Facebook for public relations. *Public Relations Review*, 2020, 46(5): 101980. [DOI :10.1016/j.pubrev.2020.101980](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2020.101980).
 - 26 Stroud S R. Pragmatist Media Ethics and the Challenges of Fake News. *Journal of Media Ethics*, 2019, 34(4): 178-192. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23736992.2019.1672554>.
 - 27 Chandra Clark and Shuhua Zhou. Fake News? A Survey on Video News Releases and their Implications on Journalistic Ethics, Independence and Credibility of Broadcast News. *Journal of Resources, Energy and Development*, 2015, 6(1): 16-27. [DOI :10.15655/mw/2015/v6i1/55376](https://doi.org/10.15655/mw/2015/v6i1/55376).
 - 28 Berg T, Kati. Media Ethics, Fake News, Politics, and Influence in Public Life. *Journal of Media Ethics*, 2017, 32(3): 179-179. [doi: 10.1080/23736992.2017.1331015](https://doi.org/10.1080/23736992.2017.1331015).
 - 29 Quinn A. Fake News, False Beliefs, and the Need for Truth in Journalism. *International Journal of Applied Philosophy*, 2017, 31(1): 21-29.[doi: 10.5840/ijap.201771884](https://doi.org/10.5840/ijap.201771884).
 - 30 Ridout B, McKay M, Amon K, et al. Social Media Use by Young People Living in Conflict-Affected Regions of Myanmar. *Cyberpsychol Behav Soc Netw*. 2020;23(12):876-888. [doi:10.1089/cyber.2020.0131](https://doi.org/10.1089/cyber.2020.0131).
 - 31 Monsees Linda. 'A war against truth' - understanding the fake news controversy. *Critical Studies on Security*, 2020, 8(2): 116-129. [doi: 10.1080/21624887.2020](https://doi.org/10.1080/21624887.2020).

[1763708](#).

32 Al-Ramahi M, Elnoshokaty A, El-Gayar O, Nasralah T, Wahbeh A. Public Discourse Against Masks in the COVID-19 Era: Infodemiology Study of Twitter Data. *JMIR Public Health Surveill*. 2021;7(4):e26780. Published 2021 Apr 5. [doi:10.2196/26780](#).

33 Tapia L. COVID-19 and Fake News in the Dominican Republic. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*. 2020;102(6):1172-1174. [doi:10.4269/ajtmh.20-0234](#).

34 Butcher Paul. COVID-19 as a turning point in the fight against disinformation. *Nature Electronics*, 2021, 4(1): 7-9. [doi: 10.1038/s41928-020-00532-2](#).

35 Ratna HN. Exercise Caution When Sharing Medical Advice About Coronavirus on Social Media. *Popul Health Manag*. 2020;23(5):400. [doi:10.1089/pop.2020.0089](#).

36 Villani A, Bozzola E, Staiano A, et al. Facial masks in children: the position statement of the Italian pediatric society. *Italian Journal of Pediatrics*. 2020;46(1):132. Published 2020 Sep 15. [doi:10.1186/s13052-020-00898-1](#).

37 Atehortua NA, Patino S. COVID-19, a tale of two pandemics: novel coronavirus and fake news messaging. *Health Promot Int*. 2021;36(2):524-534. [doi:10.1093/heapro/daaa140](#).

38 Rovetta A, Bhagavathula AS. COVID-19-Related Web Search Behaviors and Infodemic Attitudes in Italy: Infodemiological Study. *JMIR Public Health Surveill*. 2020;6(2):e19374. Published 2020 May 5. [doi:10.2196/19374](#).

39 Thornley S, Jackson MD, Sundborn G. Danish mask study: masks, media, fact checkers, and the interpretation of scientific evidence. *BMJ*, 2020, 371. m4919. [doi: 10.1136/bmj.m4919](#).

40 Ferrara E, Cresci S, Luceri L. Misinformation, manipulation, and abuse on social media in the era of COVID-19. *J Comput Soc Sci*. 2020, 3(2): 271-277. [doi: 10.1007/s42001-020-00094-5](#).

41 Pennycook G, Epstein Z, Mosleh M, Arechar AA, Eckles D, Rand DG. Shifting attention to accuracy can reduce misinformation online. *Nature*, 2021, 592(7855): 590-595. [doi: 10.1038/s41586-021-03344-2](#).

42 Zhou C, Xiu H, Wang Y, et al. Characterizing the dissemination of misinformation on social media in health emergencies: An empirical study based on COVID-19. *Information Processing and Management*, 2021, 58(4):102554. [doi: 10.1016/j.ipm.2021.102554](#).

43 He designed the first mask in China. 110 years ago, he saved a city in the Northeast. 2020-04-01 22:44. https://www.sohu.com/a/384911221_115318.

44 British News Research Institution: Most Americans no longer believe in news media. Nan Bo Yi, a surging journalist 2021-06-23 09:24 source: surging news. https://www.thepaper.cn/newsDetail_forward_13265237.

45 Huang Xiaoyong. Loneliness of economic power--When will the Nobel Prize in economics bloom in East Asia.p26, Beijing,2018, China Social Sciences Press.

46 Meves SH, Schröder KD, Endres HG, Krogias C, Krüger JC, Neubauer H. Clopidogrel high-on-treatment platelet reactivity in acute ischemic stroke patients. *Thromb Res*. 2014;133(3):396-401. [doi:10.1016/j.thromres.2013.12.002](#).

47 Akinosoglou K, Perperis A, Theodoraki S, Alexopoulos D, Gogos C. Sepsis

- favors high-on-clopidogrel platelet reactivity. *Platelets*. 2018;29(1):76-78. doi: [10.1080/09537104.2017.1319919](https://doi.org/10.1080/09537104.2017.1319919).
- 48 Coddington A, Hollis M, Nell E J. Rational Economic Man. Philosophical Books, 2010, 17(343):127-129.
- 49 Cheng-Chung Lai. *The Taste of Economic Thought History* (Updated edition), May 2016, Hangzhou, Zhejiang University Press June.
- 50 Mihalache R P, Bodislav D A. Government failure vs. Market failure. The implications of incomplete information. *Theoretical and Applied Economics*, 2019, XXVI(2): 91-104.
- 51 Bourne R. 'Market failure' arguments are a poor guide to policy. *Economic Affairs*, 2019, 39(2): 170-183. doi: [10.1111/ecaf.12346](https://doi.org/10.1111/ecaf.12346).
- 52 Wang Guisheng. *Welfare Economics*. Beijing, 2020, China Human Resources & Social Security Publishing Group Co.,Ltd(in Chinese).
- 53 Dai Xuedong, Sun Tao, Huang Fanghua, et al. General considerations and issues of special concern about the nonclinical research of modified new drugs. *Chinese Journal of New Drug*. 2017, 26(18):2121-2127. doi: [CNKI:SUN:ZXYZ.0.2017-18-002](https://doi.org/CNKI:SUN:ZXYZ.0.2017-18-002)(in Chinese).
- 54 Rai SN, Singh P, Varshney R, et al. Promising drug targets and associated therapeutic interventions in Parkinson's disease. *Neural Regen Res*. 2021;16(9): 1730-1739. doi:[10.4103/1673-5374.306066](https://doi.org/10.4103/1673-5374.306066).
- 55 Jiang J, Ding FX, Zhou X, et al. Discovery of MK-8153, a Potent and Selective ROMK Inhibitor and Novel Diuretic/Natriuretic. *J Med Chem*. 2021;64(11): 7691-7701. doi:[10.1021/acs.jmedchem.1c00406](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jmedchem.1c00406).
- 56 Abbott JA, Popescu GK. Hydroxynorketamine Blocks N-Methyl-d-Aspartate Receptor Currents by Binding to Closed Receptors. *Mol Pharmacol*. 2020;98(3): 203-210. doi:[10.1124/mol.120.119784](https://doi.org/10.1124/mol.120.119784).
57. The classic gastric drug ranitidine has been recalled globally, leaving the Chinese market alive. 2019-12-13. <https://www.ulabmed.com/content-1431-11835 -1.html>(in Chinese).
- 58 FDA NEWS RELEASE, FDA Requests Removal of All Ranitidine Products (Zantac) from the Market, FDA Advises Consumers, Patients and Health Care Professionals After New FDA Studies Show Risk to Public Health,For Immediate Release: April 01, 2020. <https://www.fda.gov/news-events/press-announcements/fda-requests-removal-all-ranitidine-products-zantac-market>.
- 59 20 drugs with sales of over 50 billion US dollars in history, each of which can make you as rich as the rest of the world. https://www.sohu.com/a/227792644_484279 (in Chinese).
- 60 Top 10 U.S. drug sales, 1992-2017. 2018/5/16. https://med.sina.com/article_detail_103_2_45846.html (in Chinese).
- 61 Esomeprazole is worth more than 60 billion US dollars in the world, and domestic enterprises are competing with each other. 20-06-2210:30. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1670164553002815787>(in Chinese).
- 62 The competitive pattern of antineoplastic drugs from the change of top 100 global drug sales. 2020-03-09 11:06:16. <https://bg.qianzhan.com/trends/detail/506/>

[200309-f79b5efa.html](#)(in Chinese).

63 In 2019, the global market scale of liposome doxorubicin will reach 7 billion yuan.2020-09-08.<https://www.qyresearch.com.cn/information/liposomal-doxorubicin-i0248.html> (in Chinese).

64 Onyia VU, Ughasoro MD, Onwujekwe OE. The economic burden of malaria in pregnancy: a cross-sectional study. *J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med.* 2020 Jan;33(1):92-95. doi: [10.1080/14767058.2018.1487933](https://doi.org/10.1080/14767058.2018.1487933).

65 Onwujekwe O, Uguru N, Etiaba E, Chikezie I, Uzochukwu B, Adjagba A. The economic burden of malaria on households and the health system in Enugu State southeast Nigeria. *PLoS One.* 2013;8(11):e78362. doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0078362](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0078362).

66 Sachs J, Malaney P. The economic and social burden of malaria. *Nature.* 2002; 415(6872):680-5. doi: [10.1038/415680a](https://doi.org/10.1038/415680a).

67 From 30 million cases to zero: China is certified malaria-free by WHO. 30 June 2021. News release Reading time:4 min (1051 words).

<https://www.who.int/news/item/30-06-2021-from-30-million-cases-to-zero-china-is-certified-malaria-free-by-who>.

68 Tao Duanfang Qing xifa. Treating colds in Europe and the United States: as if facing a big enemy, but stingy prescription. *Family medicine. Happy health,* 2016 (10): 64-65. DOI: [CNKI:SUN:JTKL.0.2016-10-075](https://doi.org/CNKI:SUN:JTKL.0.2016-10-075)(in Chinese).

69 Dicipinigaitis PV, Eccles R, Blaiss MS, Wingertzahn MA. Impact of cough and common cold on productivity, absenteeism, and daily life in the United States: ACHOO Survey. *Curr Med Res Opin.* 2015;31(8):1519-25. doi: [10.1185/03007995.2015.1062355](https://doi.org/10.1185/03007995.2015.1062355). Epub 2015 Jul 20. PMID: 26073933.

70 van den Brand JM, Smits SL, Haagmans BL. Pathogenesis of Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus. *J Pathol.* 2015; 235(2):175-84. doi: [10.1002/path.4458](https://doi.org/10.1002/path.4458).

71 "Self healing" is the most conscientious "doctor". Six kinds of diseases can be cured without taking medicine! 2020-04-28 10:55. https://www.sohu.com/a/391858365_100000338(in Chinese)

72 Cold is a kind of exercise for children's self-healing ability. *Yangtze Evening News.* <http://baby.sina.com.cn/health/15/0911/2015-11-10/0708/0736304797.shtml>(in Chinese)

73 Wang mo. a small cold can also induce nephritis. *Jiankangbao,* December 8, 2017 (004) (in Chinese).

74 Zheng Yulian. Caution: nephrotic syndrome caused by cold. *Zhongguo zhongyiyabao,* 2008-04-11 (006)(in Chinese).

75 Bramley TJ, Lerner D, Sames M. Productivity losses related to the common cold. *J Occup Environ Med.* 2002 Sep;44(9):822-9. doi: [10.1097/00043764-200209000-00004](https://doi.org/10.1097/00043764-200209000-00004).

76 Putri WCWS, Muscatello DJ, Stockwell MS, Newall AT. Economic burden of seasonal influenza in the United States. *Vaccine.* 2018 Jun 22;36(27):3960-3966. doi: [10.1016/j.vaccine.2018.05.057](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2018.05.057). Epub 2018 May 22. PMID: 29801998.

77 Gong Hui, Shen Xin, Yan Han, Lu Wanying, Zhong Guangjie, Dong Kaige, Yang Juan, Yu Hongjie. Estimating the disease burden of seasonal influenza in China,

- 2006-2019. Chinese Medical Journal. 2021,101(8): 560-567. DOI: [10.3760/cma.j.cn112137-20201210-03323](https://doi.org/10.3760/cma.j.cn112137-20201210-03323)(in Chinese).
- 78 Yin R, Yin L, Li L, Silva-Nash J, Tan J, Pan Z, Zeng J, Yan LL. Hypertension in China: burdens, guidelines and policy responses: a state-of-the-art review. J Hum Hypertens. 2021 Jul 2:1–9. doi: [10.1038/s41371-021-00570-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41371-021-00570-z). Epub ahead of print. PMID: 34215840; PMCID: PMC8252986.
- 79 Xiang Jizhou, Pharmacolgy, Beijing, 2002, CHINA SCIENCE PUBLISHING & MEDIA LTD(in Chinese).
- 80 Wang Z, Hao G, Wang X, et al. Clinical outcomes and economic impact of the 2017 ACC/AHA guidelines on hypertension in China. J Clin Hypertens (Greenwich). 2019;21(8):1212-1220. doi:[10.1111/jch.13609](https://doi.org/10.1111/jch.13609).
- 81 Ostchega Y, Fryar CD, Nwankwo T, Nguyen DT. Hypertension Prevalence Among Adults Aged 18 and Over: United States, 2017-2018. NCHS Data Brief. 2020; (364):1-8.
- 82 Verghese B, Kashinath SK, Kiwalkar S, Henderson CM. Rapid Intervention Through Telephone Encounters for Blood Pressure Control by Residents in an Outpatient Resident Clinic. Cureus. 2018;10(8):e3118. Published 2018 Aug 8. doi:[10.7759/cureus.3118](https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.3118)
- 83 Dunbar SB, Khavjou OA, Bakas T, et al. Projected Costs of Informal Caregiving for Cardiovascular Disease: 2015 to 2035: A Policy Statement From the American Heart Association. Circulation. 2018;137(19):e558-e577. doi:[10.1161/CIR.0000000000000570](https://doi.org/10.1161/CIR.0000000000000570).
- 83-1 Bakris G, Ali W, Parati G. ACC/AHA Versus ESC/ESH on Hypertension Guidelines: JACC Guideline Comparison. J Am Coll Cardiol. 2019;73(23):3018-3026. doi: [10.1016/j.jacc.2019.03.507](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2019.03.507). PMID: 31196460.
- 83-2 NCD Risk Factor Collaboration (NCD-RisC). Worldwide trends in hypertension prevalence and progress in treatment and control from 1990 to 2019: a pooled analysis of 1201 population-representative studies with 104 million participants [published online ahead of print, 2021 Aug 24].Lancet. 2021; S0140-6736 (21)01330-1. doi:[10.1016/S0140-6736\(21\)01330-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(21)01330-1).
- 84 Novel Coronavirus pneumonia real-time epidemic tracking. https://news.sina.cn/zt_d/yiqing0121(in Chinese).
- 85 Indian court: it is a crime to cause the death of COVID-19 patients due to oxygen shortage, no less than genocide. 2021-05-05 10:25. https://www.sohu.com/a/464628853_162522(in Chinese).
- 86 WHO Expert: the number of novel coronavirus infections in India is seriously underestimated. 2 million tests per day is not enough. Issued on April 27, 2021. <https://v.qq.com/x/page/r3242jst2rx.html>.
- 87 May 21,2021.The Economic Times. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/>.
- 88 Chief scientist of who: the actual number of infections in India may be 20 to 30 times higher than reported. Editor in charge: Chen Sijia, 2021-04-27. https://m.guancha.cn/international/2021_04_27_589029.shtml?s=wapzwyxw.
- 89 India deliberately understated the death toll of the novel coronavirus. A mayor of the capital exposes: statistics are falsified.2021-04-29. <https://www.163.com/dy/article>

[/G8ON0FC505444H9V.html](#)(in Chinese).

90 Millions of cases of novel coronavirus in India in three days, US media: the real death toll is two to five times that reported. April 25, 2021. <https://news.ifeng.com/c/85iKZgHWmIo>(in Chinese).

91 "I have never seen so many corpses", the epidemic in India is out of control. 2021-04-27. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/G8JQ58510514R9P4.html>.

92 Indian media described the "novel coronavirus Massacre" in rural areas: the whole family died, bodies floating in the river and fields abandoned. https://www.360kuai.com/pc/98f05b15b785fe69d?cota=3&kuai_so=1&tj_url=so_vip&sign=36057c3bbd1&refer_scene=so_1(in Chinese).

93 The old man in India cremated more than 1,000 corpses of COVID-19 patients, but was ruthlessly ignored after contracting the disease and eventually passed away. 2021-06-07.

https://www.360kuai.com/pc/904836f87f271116f?cota=3&kuai_so=1&sign=36057c3bbd1&refer_scene=so_1(in Chinese).

94 Xu X, Sun J, Nie S, et al. Seroprevalence of immunoglobulin M and G antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 in China [published correction appears in *Nat Med*. 2020 Sep;26(9):1494]. *Nat Med*. 2020;26(8):1193-1195. [doi:10.1038/s41591-020-0949-6](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-0949-6).

95 Scientific understanding of the novel coronavirus pneumonia prevalence in COVID-19 population: a new epidemiological survey of pneumonia in the novel coronavirus pneumonia. 2020-12-28. http://www.chinacdc.cn/yw_9324/202012/t20201228_223494.html.

96 He Z, Ren L, Yang J, et al. Seroprevalence and humoral immune durability of anti-SARS-CoV-2 antibodies in Wuhan, China: a longitudinal, population-level, cross-sectional study. *Lancet*. 2021;397(10279):1075-1084. [doi:10.1016/S0140-6736\(21\)00238-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(21)00238-5).

97 Liu J, Zhang L, Yan Y, et al. Excess mortality in Wuhan city and other parts of China during the three months of the covid-19 outbreak: findings from nationwide mortality registries. *BMJ*. 2021;372:n415. Published 2021 Feb 24. [doi:10.1136/bmj.n415](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n415).

98 Wuhan's GDP in the first quarter of 2021 increased by 58.4% over the same period of last year. 2021-04-23 08:02 CNews. <http://hb.sina.com.cn/news/b/2021-04-23/detail-ikmyaawc1297548.shtml>(in Chinese).

99 11 NUCLEIC ACID tests of a confirmed COVID-19 case in Shenzhen were all negative, expert interpretation. 2021-06-07 18:34:14 source: Beijing daily client. <https://news.china.com/domestic/945/20210607/39650610.html>(in Chinese).

100 Can cow urine cure COVID-19? Members of the Council take videos to promote the use of cow urine for patients, revealing the secret of India's super medicine. May 18, 2021 13:07:17. <https://news.ifeng.com/c/86LMvqRqBAE>(in Chinese).

101 Surpass China, cow dung chip and cow urine prevention the novel coronavirus. What's India like? <https://www.bilibili.com/video/BV1Ch411U7Hy>.

102 The number of new cases in a single day exceeded 200000 for five consecutive

- days“ What happened to magic India? 2021-04-20 00:21:38. http://news.china.com.cn/2021-04/20/content_77421066.htm.
- 103 "The Lancet" said: difficult to understand, unforgivable! 05-10 06:43. <https://export.shobserver.com/baijiahao/html/366221.html>.
- 104 EDITORIAL. India's COVID-19 emergency. *The Lancet*, 2021, 397(10286): 1683. Published: May 08, 2021. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(21\)01052-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(21)01052-7).
- 105 The outbreak of COVID-19 in India caused the "shock" of Zhoushan's ship repair market: Foreign ships cannot enter, and it is difficult for the shipyard to receive orders. How to survive adversity? <https://finance.sina.com.cn/chanjing/cyxw/2021-06-08/doc-ikqciyzi8362059.shtml>(in Chinese).
- 106 India over 15 million unemployed in May, unemployment rate soars to 11.9%. June 10, 2021 15:35 CCTV. <https://finance.sina.com.cn/world/gjcj/2021-06-10/doc-ikqcfnca0270251.shtml>(in Chinese).
- 107 More Indians plan to move to Europe and the United States for fear of a third wave of epidemic. 2021-06-11 22:26:07. <https://news.china.com/international/1000/20210611/39665110.html>.
- 108 China's 40-year poverty reduction report: more than 700 million people have been lifted out of poverty, creating a world miracle. November 17, 2018 19:38 source: China News. <http://www.chinanews.com/gn/2018/11-17/8679384.shtml>.
- 109 Qingming Festival, commemorating the sacrifice of poverty alleviation people 04/01/2021 09:06 source: Guangming Daily. <http://yn.people.com.cn/n2/2021/0401/c372441-34652933.html>.
- 110 Xie Ping, Yang pinyou, Zhao Fei. Research on the history of agricultural science and technology, rural economic history and agricultural cultural heritage from a new perspective -- a summary of the 2016 annual meeting of China Agricultural History Society and the 10th academic seminar of Guangdong Agricultural History Research Society [J]. *Chinese agricultural history*, 2016,35 (05): 126-132(in Chinese).
- 111 Gao Ting, Chang Qiguo. Evolution of China's agricultural economic growth in the past 40 years of reform and opening up [J]. *Tropical agricultural science*, 2018,38 (11): 103-112(in Chinese).
- 112 Wang Hongru, Du Guangjie. Spatial distribution of geographical indications and agricultural economic growth in China [J]. *East China economic management*, 2021,35 (05): 82-90(in Chinese).
- 113 Zheng Shi, Yu Zhijian, Wang Zhigang. Centennial evolution of agricultural economic thought of the Communist Party of China: experience and prospect [J]. *Teaching and research*, 2021 (06): 57-69 (in Chinese).
- 114 Chen Yixin. New Views of the Agricultural Economy of Republican China: A Review Article[J]. *Twentieth-Century China*, 2021, 28(1) : 83-106.
- 115 Rawski Thomas G.. Ideas About Studying China's Rural Economy: A Comment on the Commentaries[J]. *Republican China*, 2021, 18(1) : 146-163.
- 116 Shuangshuang Guo, Jie Zhang, Haihui Liu. The Influence of Different Political Parties in The United States on China's Economy[J]. *International Journal of*

- Education and Economics, 2021, 4(1)
- 117 Kong Heng, Xiao Yong. Practice of innovation guiding enterprise economic development in the era of big data [J]. Green packaging, 2019 (06): 49-51(in Chinese).
- 118 Du Hongyan. Practical experience of promoting enterprise economic development with agricultural associations [J]. Farm economic management, 2016 (01): 21-23(in Chinese).
- 119 Quan Heng. The mystery of China's economic rise: system construction and the role of political parties [J]. Research on Mao Zedong and Deng Xiaoping theory, 2013 (02): 21-26 + 90(in Chinese).
- 120 Chen Caizhi. The goal and path choice of the construction of the ruling ability of the Communist Party of China [D]. The Party School of the CPC Central Committee, 2005(in Chinese).
- 121 Hu Chenghuai. Four historic achievements of the CPC's Centennial struggle [J]. Zhejiang journal, 2021 (04): 4-11(in Chinese).
- 122 Yang Wensheng, Li Xudong. Evolution and Enlightenment of the CPC's Centennial modernization thought [J]. Tianfu new theory, 2021 (04): 1-10(in Chinese).
- 123 Yan Jirong. China's modernization under the leadership of the Communist Party of China: exploration, achievements and experience [J]. People's forum academic frontier, 2021 (11): 18-29(in Chinese).
- 124 Tang Huangfeng. Historical process and basic experience of the Centennial great party's effective leadership of economic and social development [J]. Journal of Wuhan University (PHILOSOPHY AND SOCIAL SCIENCES EDITION), 2021,74 (02): 5-15(in Chinese).
- 125 Wang Yao, Guo Guanqing. Political economy analysis of the impact of Party System on economic policy -- a comparative perspective between China and the West [J]. Shanghai Economic Research, 2020 (12): 5-13(in Chinese).
- 126 Meng Jie. Migrant workers, competitive local governments and socialist political parties - the State - China's economic system and economic discourse since the reform and opening up [J]. Oriental journal, 2019 (01): 45-62 + 123(in Chinese).
- 127 The interview group of this journal. On the proposition and role of political parties in the innovation of global economic governance. Reviewing the achievements of Chongqing in the "2016 dialogue between the Communist Party of China and the world" [J]. Chongqing and the world, 2016 (12): 18-23(in Chinese).
- 128 Yuan Tinghua. China's political party system and national economic and social modernization [J]. Journal of the Central Institute of socialism, 2012 (01): 7-12(in Chinese).
- 129 Hu Hanqing et al. Fuzzy comprehensive evaluation on high-quality development of China's rural economy based on entropy weight [J]. Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems, 2020, 38(6) : 7531-7539. [DOI: 10.3233/JIFS-179825](https://doi.org/10.3233/JIFS-179825)
- 130 Ge Xiaowen. Research on the transformation of investment attraction function of local government [D]. Suzhou University, 2016.
- 131 Xu Yanfei, Liu Zaiqi. International comparison of government economic

- behavior in the process of modernization [J]. Jiangnan academic, 2015,34 (03): 55-61.
- 132 Chen Wenfu, Yu Nan. Innovation of government economic behavior in the reform of state-owned assets management system in Guizhou [J]. Journal of Guizhou University of Technology (SOCIAL SCIENCE EDITION), 2005 (04): 10-13
- 133 Luo Zhenjun. The relationship between rural financial development and rural economic growth -- Based on the data of Zhejiang Province from 1978 to 2016 [J]. Jiangsu agricultural science, 2020,48 (21): 328-332(in Chinese).
- 134 Yang Zhengrong. Building high-quality projects to create a century old enterprise -- practical exploration to promote the sound and rapid development of Hunan Dongfanghong Construction Group under the new economic normal [J]. China high tech Zone, 2015 (02): 42-45(in Chinese).
- 135 Gao Mingming. On the new highlights of enterprise economic growth -- Taking the operation cost and cost control management of long-distance oil pipeline as an example [J]. Business culture, 2014 (29): 49-50(in Chinese).
- 136 Ding Yuhua, Zhang Huirong. Empirical Study on the relationship between real estate investment and economic growth in Yunnan Province [J]. Modern commerce and industry, 2021,42 (03): 11-13(in Chinese).
- 137 Wang Bin. Cointegration and causality of China's export trade, economic growth and carbon emissions -- An Empirical Analysis Based on data from 1978 to 2012 [J]. Economic research reference, 2014 (20): 53-60(in Chinese).
- 138 Zhao Qiao. Empirical analysis on the economic growth effect of China's service trade [J]. Development and reform theory and practice, 2017 (09): 44-47(in Chinese).
- 139 Yang Zeyu. Statistical research on circulation soft power promoting consumption economic growth in large and medium-sized cities [J]. Mall modernization, 2015 (23): 30-32(in Chinese).
- 140 Liu Yihan. Research on the current situation and development trend of urban consumption in China in the era of consumer economy [J]. Modern commerce, 2016 (16): 99-100(in Chinese).
- 141 Du Haobo. Research on the relationship between government guidance and the development of consumer economy under the new normal [J]. Modern commerce, 2017 (30): 17-18(in Chinese).
- 142 Wang Ling, Wang Binyue, sun genjin. Study on the impact of the opening of high-speed rail on the development of tourism economy in Sichuan Province [J]. Western China, 2021 (03): 19-30(in Chinese).
- 143 Guo Jiayuan, Zhu Yayun. Study on sustainable development strategy of local tourism economy -- Taking yunshuiyao ancient town as an example [J]. Journal of Jilin Institute of agricultural science and technology, 2021,30 (02): 21-23 + 28(in Chinese).
- 144 Ding Ling, Yao Ping. Study on the impact of regional logistics on regional economic development in Anhui Province [J]. China water transportation, 2021 (07): 94-97(in Chinese).
- 145 Chen Bingyao, Guo Xueming, Wei Polu. Cooperation between government and social capital, coordinated development of regional economy and Spatial Spillover -- An Empirical Study Based on spatial Dobbins model [J/OL]. Management

- modernization, 2021 (04): 64-72 [2021-08-01]
<https://doi.org/10.19634/j.cnki.11-1403/c.2021.04.013>(in Chinese).
- 146 Wang JUANJUAN. The Centennial course of China's regional economic development -- combing based on the relationship between rationality and efficiency [J/OL]. Contemporary economic management: 1-14 [2021-08-01]
<http://kns.cnki.net/kcms/detail/13.1356.f.20210630.1713.002.html>.
- 147 Peng Ying. Interpretation of the relationship between talent management and regional economic development [J]. Science, technology and economy guide, 2021,29 (18): 172-173(in Chinese)
- 148 Zhang Zhenmin. The role of agricultural economic management in promoting rural economic development [J]. Agricultural development and equipment, 2020 (02): 15-16
- 148 Li Juan. Impact of green food industry on China's rural economic development [J]. Food industry, 2021,42 (06): 382-385
- 150 Huang Jikun, Shi Pengfei. Path, effect and driving force of rapid and inclusive rural economic transformation [J]. China Science Foundation, 2021,35 (03): 394-401
- 151 Zhao Yan. Path analysis of promoting coordinated development of rural economy with rural finance [J]. Economic management Abstract, 2021 (13): 18-19
- 152 Zhang Helin, Wu Tiankai. Structural decomposition and dynamic analysis of China's rural economic growth [J]. Statistics and decision making, 2021,37 (12): 108-111(in Chinese)
- 153 Wu JianZheng, Pang Lin. research on the relationship between Langfang supply and marketing cooperatives and rural economic development [J]. Journal of Beihua Institute of aerospace technology, 2014,24 (06): 40-42(in Chinese)
- 154 Wang Qian. Deepening the development of rural economy and helping to overcome poverty [J]. New agriculture, 2021 (12): 28-29(in Chinese)
- 155 Wang Yaming, Wang Ying. Analysis of farm economic development under the background of Rural Revitalization Strategy -- Taking Taoli village, Hancheng City as an example [J]. Rural science and technology, 2021,12 (06): 80-82(in Chinese)
- 156 Yan Jun. developing green agriculture and promoting high-quality development of rural economy [J]. China foreign investment, 2021 (08): 32-33(in Chinese)
- 157 Maila saiwuerding, sedura yusufu. The role of green food industry in promoting rural economic development in Xinjiang [J]. Xinjiang Agricultural Science, 2008 (S1): 259-261(in Chinese)
- 158 LAN xumin, Tan Xueliang. Vigorously developing food industry to drive rural economic growth [J]. Shanxi food industry, 2003 (02): 2-5(in Chinese)
- 159 Yi Jun, Huang Yong. There are "coups" for developing agricultural and rural economy in Luxi [J]. Jiangxi agriculture, 2015 (12): 36-37(in Chinese).
- 160 He Feng, Zhu Yougang. Qingdao West Coast New Area Supply and marketing cooperatives lead the revitalization of rural green food economy [J]. Food safety guide, 2019 (11): 48-49(in Chinese).
- 161 Anhui Changfeng building a strong food economy county [J]. Commodity and quality, 2008 (30): 9(in Chinese).
- 162 Zhang Shiyue. Research on the path of Rural Ideological and political education

from the perspective of Rural Revitalization -- Taking Aobao village, Gonghe town as an example [J]. Think tank era, 2020 (04): 138-139(in Chinese).

163 Wang Taoyuan, Zhu Zhiguo, GUI Meigen. Exploration on the role of new vocational farmer training in promoting rural economy [J]. Journal of Shandong Institute of agricultural engineering, 2019,36 (12): 9-10 + 29(in Chinese).

164 Yang Xiaodong. Promotion and exploration of new vocational farmer training on rural economy in Lingtai County [J]. Agricultural staff, 2020 (15): 19(in Chinese).

165 Luo Pansheng, Gong Xiaomei, Zhu Huojun. Strategies for e-commerce majors in local universities to help rural economic development under the background of "poverty alleviation through education" -- Taking Jiangxi Institute of engineering as an example [J]. Journal of Jilin radio and Television University, 2019 (06): 66-68(in Chinese).

166 Qi Guo, Shao Mingxu, Chang Qing. Training rural practical talents to help rural economic and social development -- Summary of the "one million technical secondary school students program" for training rural practical talents [J]. Farmers' science and technology training, 2017 (12): 7-8(in Chinese).

167 China's GDP and the exchange rate of RMB against the U.S. dollar over the years (1949-2014). <https://www.docin.com/p-2151581943.html>(in Chinese).

168 The latest global GDP in 2020 is released: China is 14.7 trillion US dollars, Japan is 4.8 trillion US dollars, and the United States? 2021-01-29 14:36:49. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/G1H23N720519EO06.html>(in Chinese).

169 Ma Xiuzhen. Promotion of China's economic modernization by the five-year plan [J]. Journal of Jiangnan University (SOCIAL SCIENCE EDITION), 2020,37 (01): 5-15 + 125(in Chinese).

170 Zheng L, Tian K. The contribution of ocean trade to national economic growth: A non-competitive input-output analysis in China[J]. Marine Policy, 2021, 130(4):104559. DOI: [10.1016/j.marpol.2021.104559](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2021.104559)(in Chinese).

171 Li Yongmei. Impact of sports industry on national economic development in Fujian Province -- An Empirical Analysis Based on logistic model [J]. Journal of Minnan Normal University (PHILOSOPHY AND SOCIAL SCIENCES EDITION), 2019,33 (04): 34-42.

172 Chen Aoyang, Li Gang, research group on hot economic situation of Institute of industry and economics, Chinese Academy of social sciences. The national economy continues to move forward steadily, and China's economy ushers in a new growth cycle -- Based on the analysis of the questionnaire of the Chinese economist [J]. China Economic and trade guide, 2021 (09): 31-34(in Chinese).

173 Chen Xiaoyan. An empirical analysis on the economic effect of Xinjiang Processing Trade [J] . China market, 2016(11): 179-183(in Chinese).

174 Mao Lijuan, Xia Jiechang. Study on the impact of tourism development on regional economic growth [J]. Journal of Hehai University (PHILOSOPHY AND SOCIAL SCIENCES EDITION), 2021,23 (03): 71-79 + 107-108(in Chinese).

175 Cao Qingyao, Li Jinhong. Study on the contribution of the construction of the first batch of national global tourism demonstration areas in Guizhou Province to regional economic growth [J/OL]. Operation and management: 1-14 [2021-08-01]

<https://doi.org/10.16517/j.cnki.cn12-1034/f.20210625.001>.

176 Hou Shiying, song Liangrong. The impact of intelligence on the quality development of regional economic growth and its internal mechanism -- Based on China's provincial panel data from 2012 to 2018 [J]. Journal of Guangdong University of Finance and economics, 2021,36 (04): 4-16(in Chinese).

177 Lv caifei, Tian ran. Analysis of the impact of changes in China's national savings rate on the national economy [J]. Journal of Jiangxi Electric Power Vocational and technical college, 2019,32 (11): 140-142. (in Chinese).

178 Pan Xiansheng, Wang Bo. Promoting consumption upgrading and leading economic development -- innovating a new stage of consumption economic development in Jiangsu [J]. Jiangsu business theory, 2020 (03): 3-9(in Chinese).

179 Bu Chunyu. Research on government behavior in the construction of small towns with Tibetan characteristics [D]. Tibet University, 2018(in Chinese).

188 Simon X.B.Zhao, Hongyu Zhan, Yanpeng Jiang, Wenjun Pan, Zhang Yixiao, Tang Qing Yuan. How serious is the real estate bubble in China? Why hasn't it erupted so far? [J] Urban and rural planning, 2017 (05): 117-118(in Chinese).

189 Huang an, Yuan Fen. Problems and solutions in China's real estate economic management [J]. Housing and real estate, 2018 (25): 1(in Chinese).

190 Zheng Tongwu. Rational discussion on China's real estate economy under the new economic situation [J]. Marketing circle, 2020 (24): 89-90(in Chinese).

191 Wang Wenqin, Jia Li, Wang Wei. Measurement analysis of real estate bubble in Hefei [J]. Shanghai real estate, 2020 (09): 41-45. (in Chinese).

192 Liu Mengwei, Zhou Xue, Geng Jin Qiang. Comparative analysis of the bubble situation in five cities of China, [J]. Economic Forum, 2020 (12): 148-152. (in Chinese).

193 Li Lun, Zhang Xiang, China. Real estate market price bubble and spatial contagion effect [J]. financial research, 2019 (12): 169-186. (in Chinese).

194 Guo Mingzhu, Zheng Xiaoyun, Gao Mei Yi. Research on the influence of housing lease on the real estate bubble under bounded rationality [J]. Anhui architecture, 2019,26 (12): 26-27+157 (in Chinese).

195 Zhou Xiaoliang, Li Guanghao. The impact of high house prices on workers' human capital accumulation: promotion or hindrance -- Also on the regulatory effect of economic development level and its regulatory factors [J]. Social science research, 2020 (03): 43-51(in Chinese).

196 Cui Baojun. Impact of high house price income ratio on urban economic development in Ningbo -- a comparative analysis based on trillion GDP cities in the Yangtze River Delta [J]. Ningbo economy (Sanjiang Forum), 2021 (04): 44-48(in Chinese).

197 Zhou Hongmin. Negative impact of high house prices on sustainable economic and social development [J]. China foreign investment, 2013 (13): 26-27 + 29(in Chinese).

¹⁹⁷⁻¹ Investigation on household assets and liabilities of Chinese urban residents in 2019 .April 24,2020.

<https://finance.sina.com.cn/money/lczx/2020-04-24/doc-iirczymi8099086.shtml>(in

Chinese).

197-2 Housing vacancy rate in China. 2020-06-12 00.

<http://www.doc88.com/p-46916905200958.html>(in Chinese).

197-3 Uncover the "financial first greed": hiding 270 million cash and owning more than 100 houses. Release time: 20-01-15,09:36.

<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1655757606495957330> (in Chinese).

197-4 Lin Mengling. Literature review on the impact of real estate purchase restriction policy on house prices [J]. Continental Bridge vision, 2021 (05): 54-55(in Chinese).

197-5 Zhao Fengjun. Loopholes and accidental injuries in real estate purchase restriction [J]. China real estate, 2021 (10): 10-11(in Chinese).

197-6 Liu Siyi. Analysis and Countermeasures of "false divorce" under the real estate purchase restriction policy [J]. Shanghai real estate, 2020 (12): 46-49(in Chinese).

197-7 Liu Lei. Research on lower limit purchase policy and sales restriction policy of long-term mechanism of real estate regulation [J]. Journal of Northeast University of Finance and economics, 2020 (06): 67-75(in Chinese).

197-8 Yin Zhongli. Reasons for the recent rapid rise of house prices in some cities and suggestions for regulation [J]. Tsinghua financial review, 2021 (06): 59-60(in Chinese).

¹⁹⁷⁻⁹ Huang Shen Gang, Yue de Liang. Lin Yi, representative: the pre-sale system and shared area are outdated and should be abolished [n]. Xinhua Daily Telegraph, 2011-03-05 (006) (in Chinese).

¹⁹⁷⁻¹⁰ Bian Wenzhi. Bidding farewell to the "sharing era" in residential sales will make the real estate market more transparent [J]. Shanghai real estate, 2019 (04): 20-22(in Chinese).

¹⁹⁷⁻¹¹ Lian Haiping. Shrinking pool area is also a kind of fraud [n]. Guangzhou Daily, 2012-12-07 (F02) (in Chinese).

¹⁹⁷⁻¹² Liu Shuduo, Niu Shuang. The error of real estate surveying and mapping is too large, and the false increase area is full of tricks [n]. China economic times, 2011-05-10 (004) (in Chinese).

¹⁹⁷⁻¹³ Zhang Yi. Shared area, dizzy to see flowers in the fog [n]. Shanxi daily, 2011-03-29 (C02) (in Chinese).

¹⁹⁷⁻¹⁴ Li Chenguang. The owner of the shared area is too shocking to sue the developer [J]. Democracy and legal system, 2010 (15): 36(in Chinese).

¹⁹⁷⁻¹⁵ Bi Zijia. There are seven chaos in the shared area: buy 100 flat and get only 70 flat[J]. life and partners (second half edition), 2018 (10): 40-41(in Chinese).

198 Zhang Huarong. Fully support the development of green food in poor areas [J]. Agricultural products market, 2019 (23): 12-13(in Chinese).

199 Zhang Peng. Improving the brand of potato industry and helping rural targeted Poverty Alleviation -- Thoughts on developing agricultural product brands and helping rural poverty alleviation in Anding District, Dingxi City [J]. Gansu Agriculture, 2020 (01): 79-82(in Chinese).

- 200 Extending the industrial chain and strengthening the interest chain -- a documentary on the poverty alleviation of modern mutton sheep industrialization in Hotan, Xinjiang [J]. *Animal husbandry industry*, 2020 (04): 38-43(in Chinese).
- 201 Wang Xinyou, Wang Xuqiang, Bai Meiting, Wang Fenghua, Lin Huilong. Advantages, difficulties and Countermeasures of ecological beef cattle breeding poverty alleviation in Linyuan Mountain Area -- Based on the survey of targeted poverty alleviation in three villages of Gansu Province [J]. *China Cattle Science*, 2018,44 (04): 61-64(in Chinese).
- 202 Li Jingya. Impact of targeted poverty alleviation on dietary structure and nutritional status of college students in poor areas of Gansu Province [J]. *Bulletin on disease prevention and control*, 2020,35 (01): 44-45(in Chinese).
- 203 Liang Xin. New direction of dairy Poverty Alleviation -- Taking the experience of healthy poverty alleviation of Inner Mongolia Yili Industrial Group Co., Ltd. as an example [J]. *China animal husbandry*, 2019 (24): 73-74(in Chinese).
- 204 Nutrition poverty alleviation - nutrition improvement project for children in poor areas [J]. *Health research*, 2020,49 (05): 873(in Chinese).
- 205 Zhu Yuchao, Li Shengping, Zhang Fan, Zhao Yong. Strategic thinking on nutrition promotion in rural areas in the new era [J]. *Research and practice of health medicine*, 2021,18 (03): 1-6(in Chinese).
- 206 LAN Xiaofang, Xia Yanqiong, Qin Guoguo, Liu guihao, Tang Jie. Evaluation of intervention effect of nutrition knowledge and behavior health education for rural primary and middle school students in economically underdeveloped areas of Guangdong Province [J]. *China health education*, 2013,29 (05): 441-444(in Chinese).
- 207 Zhao Wandi, Zhao Yan. Liaoning: full implementation of the nutrition improvement plan for students in compulsory education in 15 key poverty alleviation counties [J]. *China food*, 2019 (20): 89(in Chinese).
- 208 Liu Xiaojie, Su Yang, Guan Xiaohui, Huang Qiong, Zhang Tonghui, Cheng Shubo, zonggeng. Exploration on the theory and practice model of poverty alleviation through food and education in China in the new era -- Summary of the pilot project of poverty alleviation through food and education in Kulun banner, Tongliao City, Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region [J]. *Journal of the Chinese Academy of Sciences*, 2020,35 (10): 1298-1307
- 209 Give full play to the poverty alleviation function of forestry science and technology and help consolidate Poverty Alleviation -- the Provincial Academy of forestry went to the designated assistance village to carry out practical technology training [J]. *Tropical forestry*, 2020,48 (04): 84
- 210 Zhao Kuo, Zhao Dan. Effectiveness evaluation and long-term guarantee of poverty alleviation in rural schools in the "post poverty alleviation era" -- An Empirical Study Based on five counties in Qinba Mountain contiguous poverty-stricken areas [J]. *Contemporary education forum*, 2021 (02): 19-29
- 211 Peng, Zhe, A Ripple in the Muddy Waters: The Luckin Coffee Scandal and Short Selling Attacks (August 1, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3672971> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3672971> *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems* Volume 38, Issue 6. 2020. PP 7531-7539.

- 212 Kassem, R. and Higson, A.(2012) Financial reporting fraud: are standards' setters and external auditors doing enough? *International Journal of Business and Social Science*. 3(19), pp. 283290. 22191933.
- 213 Rockness, H., Rockness, J. Legislated Ethics: From Enron to Sarbanes-Oxley, the Impact on Corporate America. *J Bus Ethics* 57, 31–54 (2005). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-004-3819-0>.
- 214 Diao Li, Gao Yufang. Research on American government economic policy under the background of economic globalization [J]. *Management science*, 2004 (01): 17-20(in Chinese).
- 215 Lu Weifeng. Evolution and Enlightenment of economic development policies of state and local governments in the United States [J]. *Shanghai comprehensive economy*, 2004 (09): 29-31(in Chinese).
- 216 Li Guo. Characteristics of local government economic management in the United States [J]. *Macroeconomic management*, 1994 (11): 39-40(in Chinese).
- 217 Zhao Xiaolei. Review on the evolution of American government economic management system [J]. *Journal of Shanghai University (SOCIAL SCIENCE EDITION)*, 1990 (06): 16-20(in Chinese).
- 218 Mou Qiuxian. Research on U.S. government economic intervention policy under the background of financial crisis [D]. *Anhui University of engineering*, 2013
- 219 Gerard Joseph white. Research on the U.S. government's economic stimulus plan under the background of the financial crisis [D]. *Wuhan University*, 2013(in Chinese).
- 220 Sun Haiyong. Trump administration's economic policies and the growth prospects of US Treasury bonds [J]. *International financing*, 2020 (05): 40-44(in Chinese).
- 221 Zhan Baiming. Factors affecting US imports and the structural dilemma of the Obama administration's economic adjustment [J]. *World economic research*, 2011 (04): 81-86 + 89(in Chinese).
- 222 Song Guoyou. Analysis of the US government's economic crisis transfer behavior [J]. *Modern international relations*, 2011 (05): 34-40(in Chinese).
- 223 Gu Dengchen. Analysis of the characteristics of the U.S. government's economic policy towards Taiwan [J]. *Unification forum*, 2019 (02): 52-54(in Chinese).
- 224 Li Wan. How did the history of the U.S. government promote university technology transfer begin -- Based on the combing and investigation of establishing a market-oriented University: how academic research becomes an economic engine [J]. *Anhui Science and technology*, 2019 (04): 18-21(in Chinese).
- 225 Huang Shudong. The US government has been implementing economic intervention [J]. *Research on world socialism*, 2018,3 (07): 92(in Chinese).
- 226 Sun Yumin. How does the US government intervene in the economy——Interview with Yang Huijun, researcher of American Institute of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences [J]. *Shanghai state owned assets*, 2015 (10): 101-103(in Chinese).
- 227 Ma Xiaoxue, Ma Hao, Shi Shukai. Analysis model of American government procurement based on economic growth [J]. *JOURNAL OF LIAONING NORMAL*

- UNIVERSITY (NATURAL SCIENCE EDITION), 2015,38 (02): 269-274(in Chinese).
- 228 Rosemary foot, Amy king, Cui Zhinan. Assessing the deterioration of China US Relations: the view of the US government on the economic security nexus [J]. China International Strategy Review, 2019 (02): 34-44(in Chinese).
- 229 Zhong Maochu. Comparison of economic real debt and policy means of two major political parties in the United States during their administration -- Analysis of the impact of the U.S. election on economic prosperity [J]. World economic research, 2001 (01): 68-72(in Chinese).
- 230 Li Yanhui, the influence of political parties and interest groups on American diplomatic decision-making [J]. Journal of Social Sciences of Xiangtan University, 2003 (03): 24-26 + 30(in Chinese).
- 231 Gu Meihong, Zhang Mingju. Comparative study on the relationship between American interest group politics and party politics [J]. Journal of Harbin Institute of Technology (SOCIAL SCIENCE EDITION), 2003 (04): 26-29(in Chinese).
- 232 Lin FeiTing. Uncertainty of Trump's new economic deal -- Discussion from the perspective of traditional Republican values [J]. International economic cooperation, 2017 (04): 52-59(in Chinese).
- 233 John Dorrell and Keunjae Lee. The Politics of Wind: A state level analysis of political party impact on wind energy development in the United States[J]. Energy Research & Social Science, 2020, 69. DOI: [10.1016/j.erss.2020.101602](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101602).
- 234 Stephen M. Krason. Conservatism and the Republican Party on Economics[J]. Catholic Social Science Review, 2020, 25 : 275-278. DOI: [10.5840/cssr2020251](https://doi.org/10.5840/cssr2020251).
- 235 Zheng Liansheng. Economic and political roots of European negative interest rate policy and its impact on China [J]. International finance, 2014 (07): 57-61(in Chinese).
- 236 Aaron Reeves, Martin McKee, Sanjay Basu, David Stuckler. Political and economic austerity and health services -- a transnational analysis based on cost changes in 27 European countries from 1995 to 2011 [J]. China health policy research, 2014,7 (04): 73-80.
- 237 Elina Kestil ä Kekkonen and Peter Söderlund. Is it All about the Economy? Government Fractionalization, Economic Performance and Satisfaction with Democracy across Europe, 2002–13[J]. Government and Opposition, 2017, 52(1) : 100-130. DOI: [10.1017/GOV.2015.22](https://doi.org/10.1017/GOV.2015.22)
- 238 Zhang chunman, Guo Sujian. Chinese political research in mainstream American political science journals: context, issues, methods and prospects [J]. Political science research, 2019 (03): 69-80 + 127(in Chinese).
- 239 LV Tongzhou, Dong Mengyu, Zhou Youping. New progress in comparative politics research in China (2018) [J]. Comparative politics research, 2019 (01): 175-193 + 214-215
- 240 Li Luqu, Xia Meng. Discipline development, comparative historical analysis, political development and democratization of comparative politics [J]. Comparative politics research, 2016 (02): 194-242
- 241 Lin Qifu, Liu Shiyu, Ju Sicheng. New progress in American Comparative

Politics Research in recent ten years -- Based on the analysis of three major journals of Comparative Politics (2006-2015) [J]. Comparison of economic and social systems, 2016 (05): 183-197

242 Geng Shu, Chen Wei. Case study of Comparative Politics: Rethinking several methodological myths [J]. Social Sciences, 2013 (05): 20-29(in Chinese).

260 Super Plus enjoy! China and the United States have reached an agreement on the text of the first phase of the trade agreement, in addition to soybeans, wheat, corn and other agricultural products, China will expand imports of energy and manufactured products. 2019-12-14 06:58 Source: The Paper The Paper Media. https://www.thepaper.cn/newsDetail_forward_5238518.

261 An increase of nearly 200%, China once again imported 3.4 million tons of soybeans from the United States! Why do we still rely on American soybeans? 2020/11/29. <https://new.qq.com/rain/a/20201129A077SJ00> (in Chinese).

262 China imports the most wheat and corn from the United States, and rice becomes the only staple food that exports more than imports. 2020/10/26/21:19. <https://new.qq.com/omn/20201026/20201026A0HW2R00.html>.

263 After soybeans, ask China to buy ten million tons of corn? US media: China must purchase 2020-12-1221:54:19 Source: Straits Life Exchange. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/FTM81S6G0534NALQ.html>(in Chinese).

264 The first phase of China-US economic and trade agreement is reached. Can the cotton and cotton textile market meet the turning point in 2020? 2019/12/20 11:49:00. <http://www.sjfzxm.com/caijing/201912-20-558597.html>(in Chinese).

265 The US official announced that Huawei must not use US technology to make chips. 2020-5-16. <https://www.bilibili.com/read/cv6078781/>.

266 The chips cannot be sold to Huawei, and Qualcomm is also anxious? Posting a "warning" to the US government: The \$8 billion market is given away to its opponents every year! August 10, 2020 08:26. <http://news.sina.com.cn/o/2020-08-10/doc-iivhuipn7795681.shtml>

267 Burst! The U.S. bans the export of 5G components to Huawei. 2021-03-14 21:02:55. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/G531MJ1M0511CRN2.html>

268 Just! TSMC announced that it will cut off Huawei's supply: if the US ban remains unchanged, it will cut its supply from September 14. 20-07-16. 21:32. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1672380503209745065>

269 After the study ban, the Trump administration cancelled more than 1,000 Chinese student visas! 202009/1018:30 <https://new.qq.com/omn/20200910/20200910A0KT3Y00.html>(in Chinese).

270 Chinese students' visas to the United States were denied. Why does the Biden administration say something nice but not do it in fact? 2021-07-11. http://www.china.com.cn/opinion2020/2021-07/11/content_77619501.shtml

271 Three major telecom operators: New York Stock Exchange maintains its delisting decision. 2021/05/08/ 10:33:34. <https://tech.ifeng.com/c/864ZsW9yw3x>

272 Zhang Chaohan, Liu Jing. Empirical Study on American large aircraft subsidy under the framework of WTO -- Taking the "EU v. American large aircraft subsidy case" as an example [J]. Exploration of international economy and trade, 2020,36 (04):

89-99.

273 Ding Chun, Qiang Haofan, Yang Jiawei. US European Economic and trade conflicts during Trump's period: characteristics, causes and Prospects -- An Empirical Analysis from the perspective of US European trade imbalance [J]. European research, 2019,37 (03): 1-37 + 156.

274 Kou Jiali. Why the United States is keen on trade war [J]. Economy, 2019 (06): 52-56(in Chinese).

275 Li Guanyun, Xiong min, Yang Chao, Washington. War company: behind the scenes political and economic interest chain of the number one arms dealer in the United States [n]. 21st Century Business Herald, 2010-01-22 (004) (in Chinese).

276 Li Shi. The United States sells fighters to India and Pakistan: "one arrow and three eagles" [n]. China Aviation News, 2005-04-05 (003) (in Chinese).

277 The import of American pork with ractopamine has caused Taiwanese people to panic and dare not eat pork anymore! <https://v.qq.com/x/page/s3222zoty8y.html>

278 U.S. Senate hearing puts pressure on U.S. pork exports containing ractopamine to Taiwan. 2013-03-20 09:08.

http://www.fjsen.com/b/2013-03/20/content_10915363.htm?tag/vw0qf

279 Ma Ying-jeou: The U.S. Does Not Export "Clenbuterol" Pork to Taiwan 2015-05-19 10:38:12 Source: Weihai Daily.

<http://www.xinm123.com/html/n-pig/397979.html>(in Chinese).

280 Tsai Ing-wen's government opens imports of pork from the United States containing ractopamine, and Taipei City says it will ban sales in accordance with regulations. 2020-08-31 15:28. <http://www.soozhu.com/article/407064/>

281 In the five eye alliance, only Canada has not banned Huawei? Netizen Satire: should always follow the United States. 2020/07/15/. 16:41:53.

<https://news.ifeng.com/c/7y85Cb1smjQ>. (in Chinese).

282 Re-issued a ban, the United States has just announced a ban on the purchase of equipment and technologies such as Huawei, ZTE, Hikvision, etc. 2019-08-08 15:26.

<https://ee.ofweek.com/2019-08/ART-8120-2801-30402122.html>(in Chinese).

283 Britain admits that banning Huawei will delay the country's 5G construction progress by 2 to 3 years. 2020/07/15, 09:09.

<https://new.qq.com/omn/20200715/20200715A05ORW00.html>(in Chinese).

284 Ericsson earns 57.5 billion from China's 5G, but the local government has decided to ban Huawei! 20-10-2316:12.

<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1681329501387469264>(in Chinese).

285 China Mobile's large purchase order results: Huawei has no revenue, ZTE is less than 10%, Nokia is the first. 2021-03-17 04:05:02.

<https://www.163.com/dy/article/G58DCF2R0531JOTT.html>(in Chinese).

286 Summary of China's military disarmament data.2015-09-04 08:13.

https://www.sohu.com/a/30520027_121315(in Chinese).

287 Zhao Huijun. Acquisition, disposal and return: a discussion on Contemporary Museum collection ethics [J]. Chinese Museum, 2016 (04): 98-104(in Chinese).

288 Zhang Hanyu. Research on ethical issues of contemporary museums [D]. China Academy of art, 2012(in Chinese).

- 289 Zhang Yao, Xu Nan, Dang Xingju. On the guiding significance of Tao Te Ching to physics discovery [J]. Journal of Zhaotong University, 2014,36 (05): 43-46
- 290 Zhang Yingjie, Zhang Duanming. Research on Taoist culture and the new trend of contemporary science [J]. Journal of Huazhong University of science and Technology (SOCIAL SCIENCE EDITION), 2012,26 (03): 94-98
- 291 Zhong Yongsheng. On the identity of quantum induction, heaven and man and general relativity [J]. Journal of Dalian Maritime University (SOCIAL SCIENCE EDITION), 2018,17 (04): 87-92
- 292 Wang Meng. Contemporary dialogue between Buddhism and science -- Taking Buddhist emptiness theory and quantum theory as clues [J]. Dialectics of nature communication, 2004 (02): 19-24 + 110
- 293 Li Leyi. After going through ups and downs, he has no regrets and is willing to spread the truth to the world -- a record of China's folk scientist Zhang Kehai [J]. Strait science, technology and industry, 2012 (10): 80
- 294 The United States of Utah has passed the polygyny by unanimous vote
<https://zhuanlan.zhihu.com/p/111176084>
- 295 British media commented on the new book "*Destined for War: Can America and China Escape Thucydides' s Trap*" by American scholar Graham Allison: We must learn to accept China's power. 2017-07-04. 14:34:16
https://www.guancha.cn/america/2017_07_04_416434.shtml
- 296 Ding Danping. "Broken window effect" is one of the economic reasons for the war launched by American capital groups [J]. Times finance, 2012 (24): 292(in Chinese).
- 297 Tu Longli. Economic thinking on the Kosovo War -- Also on the economic motivation of the United States to launch the Kosovo war [J]. Journal of the school of Taxation of Yangzhou University, 1999 (02): 8-13(in Chinese).
- 298 Han Xue. United States: the probability of saving the market by war is increasing [J]. Market weekly (Theoretical Research), 2009 (05): 109-110(in Chinese).
- 299 After China refused the US Defense Secretary's call, the Pentagon showed a timetable for war against China, which caused an uproar. 2021-07-15 19:27.
<https://www.163.com/dy/article/GEVJ38IU0550HKO5.html>
- 300 Us think tank: China may become the preferred target for war to resolve the financial crisis. 09:57, October 24, 2008.
<http://mil.news.sina.com.cn/p/2008-10-24/0957526811.html>(in Chinese).
- 301 Professor Singapore can't watch it anymore: because the epidemic wants China to cede land and lose money! Did the United States pay? 2020/04/21 15:24.
<https://ishare.ifeng.com/c/s/7vqtaB8TE5d>(in Chinese).
- 302 Yang Bin. Analysis of economic crisis, financial turmoil and international security situation[J]. Heilongjiang Social Sciences, 2012(01):90-92 (in Chinese).
- 303 Kissinger: "A country in the world should support the United States, or there will be war!" 2020-05-07 00:57.
https://3g.163.com/dy/article_cambrian/FC03334K0525L98S.html(in Chinese).
- 304 Maki DG, Alter SM, Solano JJ, et al. COVID-19 control in the United States:

the case for masking. *Am J Manag Care*. 2021;27(7):e218-e220. Published 2021 Jul 1. [doi:10.37765/ajmc.2021.88670](https://doi.org/10.37765/ajmc.2021.88670).

305 Rabin C, Dutra S. Predicting engagement in behaviors to reduce the spread of COVID-19: the roles of the health belief model and political party affiliation [published online ahead of print, 2021 Apr 27]. *Psychol Health Med*. 2021;1-10. [doi:10.1080/13548506.2021.1921229](https://doi.org/10.1080/13548506.2021.1921229).

306 Republican Mask Manufacturer Says He'll Vote Biden After Trump 'Politicized' COVID-19. Hayley Miller Senior reporter, HuffPost. October 22, 2020 3 min read. https://www.yahoo.com/huffpost/republican-mask-manufacturer-biden-trump-161130153.html?guccounter=1&guce_referrer=aHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuc28uY29tL2xpbms_bT1icmRXQk9tRFVDSTQ3ZnVMZG9udG11TVZtVzIldGd2Y1VE9nUSUyRmY2SVIyU3JwJTJGVESlMkYzbo5oTGRhUkJIMEhkaGMIMkZPbTA4RIJrSGtrTWtuQ0x2M1ZYWFkxTVFCdHJLYVZUSFpSaEdRcVJmODNodU0lMkJSdmxDSkk3WVJzTUINdE5uTTElMkZzNk9UbUZnWUvNt0tMUmpuaXV3RXNhV29vUXIEMyUyRnVwWjIOdHhTSG9vM1QlMkYzOCUyRlZRUGs5UDZ0QUJXc2drcDEwZXFNU0JuNyUyQjZUajRRWmJDR0dxdzR3JTNEJTNE&guce_referrer_sig=AQAAAIqWD3Rwr7akGAKQ5SF9FY9JbaexQLqK6IulS4C3h4adxcpopajubzbtFa_gyWOCRQi6ikq-xAF3AF8O3sxxSVqDNK8qxvaFV2oQPkIXNI01zY5bZJ_zBLJDzKlcnFI3NxdHYMu8hDfvPAZTMnmhRRghxo56Pex03YzWu1c_NF5o.

307 Lee J, Kim Y, Kelsey JP. Beyond Wishful Thinking during the COVID-19 Pandemic: How Hope Reduces the Effects of Death Arousal on Hostility toward Outgroups among Conservative and Liberal Media Users for COVID-19 Information [published online ahead of print, 2021 May 3]. *Health Commun*. 2021;1-10. [doi:10.1080/10410236.2021.1921906](https://doi.org/10.1080/10410236.2021.1921906)

308 Kenworthy N, Koon AD, Mendenhall E. On symbols and scripts: The politics of the American COVID-19 response. *Glob Public Health*. 2021;16(8-9):1424-1438. [doi:10.1080/17441692.2021.1902549](https://doi.org/10.1080/17441692.2021.1902549)

309 Throughout the "may" and "maybe", the report for the origin-tracing of novel coronavirus of American politicians makes people laugh. Updated: 2021-08-10 18:23:12.

https://www.guancha.cn/internation/2021_08_10_602416.shtml(in Chinese).

310 POLITICAL MANIPULATION IS DOOMED TO BE UNPOPULAR -- as if the global war on disease must be purged of the "political virus".2021-08-05 12:39:01. https://www.guancha.cn/politics/2021_08_05_601760.shtml(in Chinese).

311 Ma Kaishuo refutes the claim Theory: Did the world ask the United States for compensation in the 2008 crisis? Updated: 2020-04-19 15:38:02 https://www.guancha.cn/internation/2020_04_19_547440.shtml(in Chinese).

312 Rebounds in COVID-19 infections in US raise alarm for low vaccination rates, politicization of origin tracing. *Xinhua*. Updated: July 28, 2021. <http://enapp.chinadaily.com.cn/a/202107/28/AP6100fc3ea310f03332fa5eb8.html>.

313 Urgent: Diplomats from 48 countries write to WHO chief opposing politicization of COVID-19 origin-tracing. Source: *Xinhua*| 2021-07-16 01:40:55|Editor: huaxia. http://www.xinhuanet.com/english/2021-07/16/c_1310063745.htm.

- 314 Wang Yifei, Xie Jinghe, Li Shuguang, Jiang Qingwu, Chen Bo. Risk Prevention and control of imported cold chain food under COVID-19 epidemic situation. *Shanghai Preventive Medicine*, 2021,33(05) : 397-403 (in Chinese).
- 315 Yu Fan, Shen Lingyu, Tian Yi, Wang Quanyi, Gao Zhiyong. Study on the transmission of novel coronavirus in imported cold chain aquatic products. *Chinese Journal of Epidemiology*, 2021,42(06) : 992-1001(in Chinese).
- 316 Giant boa constrictors flood the streets of Florida, scaring the people! Official: why don't you eat it!. 2020-12-23 23:23:23.
<https://www.163.com/dy/article/FUINFQJ2051484S5.html>(in Chinese).
- 317 At the Texas snake tasting, where thousands of King snakes are slaughtered for food. 2017-04-18 22:52:29.
<https://www.163.com/dy/article/CIBD624U0523AOGH.html>(in Chinese).
- 318 [picnic] when the Australian Food Festival arrives, there are roast kangaroo meat in addition to steak. 2016-05-26 17:07.
https://www.sohu.com/a/77387094_122223(in Chinese).
- 319 Ai Q, Lin X, Xie H, Li B, Liao M, Fan H. Proteome Analysis in PAM Cells Reveals That African Swine Fever Virus Can Regulate the Level of Intracellular Polyamines to Facilitate Its Own Replication through ARG1. *Viruses*. 2021;13(7):1236. Published 2021 Jun 26. [doi:10.3390/v13071236](https://doi.org/10.3390/v13071236)
- 320 Menachery VD, Yount BL Jr, Debbink K, et al. A SARS-like cluster of circulating bat coronaviruses shows potential for human emergence [published correction appears in *Nat Med*. 2016 Apr;22(4):446] [published correction appears in *Nat Med*. 2020 Jul;26(7):1146]. *Nat Med*. 2015;21(12):1508-1513. [doi:10.1038/nm.3985](https://doi.org/10.1038/nm.3985).
- 321 Becker MM, Graham RL, Donaldson EF, et al. Synthetic recombinant bat SARS-like coronavirus is infectious in cultured cells and in mice. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2008;105(50):19944-19949. [doi:10.1073/pnas.0808116105](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0808116105)
- 322 Italian media's tracing sword points to Fort Detrick, CNN is anxious: an obscure Italian tabloid. <http://www.myzaker.com/article/611540458e9f093545677d27>
- 323 Apolone G, Montomoli E, Manenti A, et al. Unexpected detection of SARS-CoV-2 antibodies in the pre-pandemic period in Italy[J]. *Tumori Journal*, 2020: 0300891620974755.
- 324 Gianotti R, Barberis M, Fellegara G, Galvan-Casas C, Gianotti E. COVID-19-related dermatosis in November 2019: could this case be Italy's patient zero? *Br J Dermatol*. 2021;184(5):970-971. [doi:10.1111/bjd.19804](https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.19804).
- 325 A large number of Americans tweeted to expose: they were infected with the novel coronavirus in December 2019 or even earlier. August 10, 2021.
<https://mil.news.sina.com.cn/2021-08-10/doc-ikqcfnc2106976.shtml>
- 326 COVID-19 origin tracing timeline: Studies show earlier emergence worldwide. 2021-06-24 10:13.
https://www.360kuai.com/pc/94db0d315fc99d365?cota=3&kuai_so=1&tj_url=so_vip&sign=360_57c3bbd1&refer_scene=so_1.
- 327 The latest ranking of the world's top ten hospitals in 2020.
<https://xw.qq.com/cmsid/20200311A0N8YW00>(in Chinese).

- 328 Ranking of the world's top ten medical universities and the world's top medical schools. Gao Wu. 2021-08-12 00:40:45.
<http://www.i35.com/i62437.html?iitovy=mobbs3>(in Chinese).
- 329 Guan Zhong: an extremely pragmatic and meritorious statesman. 2016-03-26 15:20. <https://cul.qq.com/a/20160326/023655.htm>
- 330 Anson Burlingame. <https://baike.so.com/doc/5999037-6212012.html>(in Chinese).
- 331 English Chinese comparison of the full text of the constitution of the Communist Party of China. 2007-10-31 17:31
https://www.chinadaily.com.cn/hqzg/2007-10/31/content_6220595_8.htm.
- 332 Politician. Oxford English Dictionary, 2021 (Oxford online English Dictionary).
- 333 The 25 Most Inspiring Hillary Clinton Quotes. By Hallie Gould, Oct 26, 2014.
<https://www.marieclaire.com/career-advice/tips/a11373/best-hillary-clinton-quotes/>
- 334 Both Chinese and English | “Neither riches nor honours can corrupt him; neither poverty nor humbleness can make him swerve from principle; and neither threats nor forces can subdue him”, 2017-05-23 06:31.
https://www.sohu.com/a/142720970_528910
- 335 Marcucci R, Marietta M. Vaccine-induced thrombotic thrombocytopenia: the elusive link between thrombosis and adenovirus-based SARS-CoV-2 vaccines. Intern Emerg Med. 2021 Jun 30:1–7. [doi: 10.1007/s11739-021-02793-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11739-021-02793-x).
- 336 WHO warns: the spread of the novel coronavirus exceeds the speed of vaccine distribution. Video included. June 15, 2021 08:44. <http://www.chinanews.com/gj/2021/06-15/9499695.shtml>.
- 337 According to recent travel history and residence history, personnel are divided into three categories: high risk, medium risk and low risk. Time: March 2, 2020 16:11:34 source: china.com Author: Wu Jiatong. http://news.china.com.cn/txt/2020-03/02/content_75765113.htm(in Chinese).
- 338 Development and Reform Commission: Classified by county level! Completely remove restrictions on access to low-risk areas.2020-02-26 08:36. https://www.sohu.com/a/375899326_696946(in Chinese).
- 339 Premier Wen's English Translation "Become Famous in a Meeting". March 20, 2007. <http://news.sohu.com/20070320/n248831488.shtml>(in Chinese).
- 340 <https://www.douban.com/group/topic/1500851/>.